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D.5.3 Protocol to monitor objects and environment for preventive conservation and concept of digital platform infrastructure for preventive conservation

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Abstract

The scientific understanding of the degradation of cultural heritage objects, caused by external and internal factors, is increasing. However, we are still far from having a comprehensive material–object–environment–building model that would enable us to predict the outcomes of preventive conservation scenarios. This deliverable represents a step forward in detecting, understanding, and monitoring changes, crucial for preventive conservation. It targets oil paintings and addressing various internal and external factors. The deliverable is organized into three topics, each containing subprojects, and covers protocols development for chemical and structural painting changes (Topic 1), monitoring indoor environmental conditions (Topic 2), and a digital platform with decision support tools (Topic 3). Twenty-five partners from 13 countries contributed to the deliverable and each subproject is coordinated by a project leader.

Topic 1, the first project focuses on the development of a protocol for assessing light-induced color changes in specific pigments within oil binder, utilizing non-invasive imaging and single-point techniques as well as micro-destructive molecular and elemental methods. Objectives include evaluating different white-light sources' impact on mock-ups and defining critical parameters for monitoring paint film color changes. The second project introduces the monitoring of lead soap protrusion formation. It combines non-invasive imaging and spot-point techniques resulting in a ten-step protocol for long-term condition monitoring. For varnish analysis (project 3), a toolkit of non-invasive chemical and structural techniques is applied, showing promising advances in sensitive equipment, but necessary development for effective museum implementation. The fourth project aids in interpreting multimodal methodology results for sensitive modern oil paint surfaces. While some techniques provide initial insights, conclusive findings require cross-referencing with additional non-invasive methods. The topic's final project explores non-invasive imaging for determining and monitoring delaminating and flaking paint layers. Most of techniques discussed in topic 1 are offered via the IPERION HS catalogue of services.

Topic 2, the first project in this topic 2 aims at developing a toolkit for simple environmental monitoring techniques. It specifically examines formic and acetic acid, known risks to collections during storage or display and validated them with samplers for SO₂ and NO₂. The developed method is offered as an IPERION HS service. The second project carried out an interlaboratory comparison of the Oddy Test to assess its reproducibility and progress toward standardization. In addition, it compared protocol variations and shares more objective assessment approaches and best practices. The third project offers a concise protocol and overview of instrumental techniques available through IPERION HS for analyzing the chemical composition of collected airborne particles. This analysis aids in identifying pollutants, understanding their sources, evaluating their impact on artworks, and devising protection strategies for cultural artifacts. The last project demonstrates the value of incorporating different mass spectrometry approaches for the detection of organic compounds harmful to oil paintings and optimized their protocols.

Topic 3 focuses to enhance and openly share a digital platform of specialized apps for preventive conservation, including HERIE, DISCOLL, IMPACT, Collection Demography apps. In addition, it describes the requirements of ideal apps for the end-user and includes a validation on the dust deposition model for the case-study the cloister of the Monastery of Santa María

del Paular (Rascafría, Spain). The digital apps are presented in a single website, the E-RIHS - Digital Tools, Services and Resources, <https://e-rihs.io/resources.html>, planned to be merged in E-RIHS - ERIC DIGILAB open services.

To conclude, topic 1 protocols are based on mock-ups, serve as the foundation, and starting point for actual implementing in authentic paintings. The various protocols developed under topic 1 and 2 serving as 'monitoring toolkit' which can be offered to E-RIHS users in the future and the concept of the digital platform presented here will be fused in E-RIHS - ERIC DIGILAB open services.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
3D	Three dimensions
AA	Acetic acid
AER	Air exchange rate
AGH	AGH university of science and technology
ATR	Attenuated total reflection
C2RMF	National Centre for Research and Restoration in French museums
CC	Cosine corrector
CCD	Charge-coupled device
CCD/CMOS	Charge-coupled device/complementary metal oxide semiconductor
CCI	Canadian conservation institute
CENIM-CSIC	Centro nacional de investigaciones metalúrgicas
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CIELAB	International commission on illumination (CIE)
CNR-SCITEC	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche
CNR-IFAC	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Fisica Applicata
CNR-INO	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto Nazionale di Ottica
CNR-ISPC	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale
DART-MS	Direct analysis in real time-mass spectrometry
DIGILAB	Platform of digital laboratory
DP	Degree of polymerisation
DISCOLL	Digital tool discoloration of paper-based collection
DSPI	Digital speckle pattern interferometry
E _v	Illuminance

EPR	Electron paramagnetic resonance
ERIC	European research infrastructure consortium
E-RIHS	European research infrastructure heritage science
ER-FTIR	External reflection FTIR
FAIR	Findable accessibly interoperable and reusable
FIXLAB	Platform of fixed laboratory
FORS	Fibre optics reflectance spectroscopy
FOV	Field of view
FPA	Focal plane array
FTIR	Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy
GA-FTIR	Grazing-angle Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy
GC-MS	Gas chromatography mass spectroscopy
GPU	Graphics processing unit
HERie	Digital decision-supporting platform
IKiFP PAN	Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry Polish Academy of Sciences
IMPACT	Innovative modelling of museum pollution and conservation thresholds
I/O	Indoor/Outdoor
IPCE	Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España
IPCHS	Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia
IPERION HS	Integrating platforms for the European research infrastructure on heritage science
IQFR-CSIC	Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano
IR	Infrared
IUPAC	International union of pure and applied chemistry
HS	Heritage science
HS-GC-MS	Headspace sampling coupled to gas chromatography mass spectrometry
LA-ICP-MS	Laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
LE	Lifetime explorer
LED	Light-emitting diode
LIF	Laser-induced fluorescence
LOD	Limit of detection
MFT	Microfading tester
MOLAB	Platform of mobile laboratory
MPEF	Multiphoton excitation fluorescence
MS	Mass spectrometry
NCU	Nicolaus Copernicus university
NIR	Near Infrared
NIST	National institute of standards and technology
NLOM-MPEF	Nonlinear optical microscopy in the modality of multiphoton excitation fluorescence
NTU	Nottingham Trent university
OCT	Optical coherence tomography
OF-ADC	Ormylia foundation, art diagnosis center

OT	Oddy test
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PbS	Lead sulfide
PC	Personal computer
PDA	Photo diode array
PM	Particulate matter
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
Py-DART-MS	Pyrolysis direct analysis in real time-mass spectrometry
RAA	Swedish National Heritage Board
RCE	Rijksdienst Cultureel Erfgoed
RH	Relative humidity
RI	Research infrastructure
RIJKS	Rijksmuseum
RL	Ranking light
RSD	Relative standard deviation
Sd-OCT	Spectral domain optical coherence tomography
SEM-EDS	Scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy
Si	Silium
SNR	Signal to noise ratio
SPME	Solid phase microextraction
SRM	Standard reference material
SSL	Split/splitless
SVP	Small volume prover
SWIR	Short wavelength infrared spectroscopy
SWNIR	Short wavelength near infrared spectroscopy
Sq	Root mean square roughness
T	Temperature
TNA	Transnational access for heritage science
TTL	Through the lens
UA	Uncertainty analyzer
UCL	University College London
UiO	University of Oslo
UL	University of Ljubljana
UniPg	University of Perugia
UV	Ultraviolet
UV-B	Ultraviolet-B
UV-C	Ultraviolet-C
Vis	Visible
VOC	Volatile organic compounds
WLED	White light emitting diode
XRD	X-ray diffraction
XRF	X-ray Fluorescence

Narrative (technical) description

Introduction

The understanding of the degradation of cultural heritage objects, caused by external and internal factors, is increasing. However, we are still far from having a comprehensive material–object–environment–building model that would enable us to predict the outcomes of preventive conservation scenarios. This deliverable is a step forward in enhancing our capacity to detect, better understand and monitor changes, enabling us to effectively facilitate passive conservation measures. It focuses on traditional as well as modern oil paintings that are subjected to changes overtime caused by internal as well as external factors.

This deliverable develops *protocols to monitoring* the changing of oil paintings and their environment in the context of preventive conservation. Several protocols have been developed to serve as reference guides for enhancing the preventive conservation of paintings, with the ultimate goal to make the acquired expertise and data accessible to the “end user of cultural heritage” through a digital portal. This deliverable presents the *concept of digital platform* infrastructure for preventive conservation.

Oil painting degradation phenomena

Focusing on the preventive conservation of oil paintings raises a variety of complications due to the widespread chemical and physical processes and their interconnection that take place over time. A change in visual appearance of a painting can be caused by many factors, such as degradation of pigments, formation of secondary degradation products, decrease of transparency of varnishes or paint layers and structural alterations of the paint surface and/or layers. Moreover, these processes are mostly highly interconnected, e.g., the degradation products of emerald green pigment can migrate into the varnish layer forming new crystalline materials resulting in altered, darkened varnish layer¹ or zinc soap formation may lead to delamination.² The different causes of degradation and their different manifestations poses many challenges for the conservation field.

Being aware of the complexity of oil paint degradation phenomena, for this deliverable a selection of urgent degradation phenomena encountered in oil paintings is made. The degradation phenomena selected are:

- A. Color changes of paint – intrinsic properties of the paints and different environmental factors (i.e., light, relative humidity, temperature, air pollutants) influence the propensity of the paint surface towards color change (Clarricoates et al. 2016; Monico et al. 2019; Miliani et al. 2018)

- B. Metal soap formation – metal soaps form because of reactions between some pigments and the oil binder, thus disfiguring the appearance and affecting the internal structure of paintings. (Casido 2019)
- C. Changing varnishes – cracking, hazing, loss of gloss, yellowing, and darkening over time of varnishes as consequences of aging of the varnish and continuous exposure to environmental conditions (De La Rie 1989)
- D. Water-sensitive surfaces – especially modern oil paints are sensitive to water due to internal and environmental factors (Van den Berg et al. 2014; Van den Berg et al. 2020)
- E. Delaminating paints – cracking or deformation of ground and paint layers due to fluctuating environmental and/or paint composition (Mauny-van den Burg et al. 2016)

The deliverable focuses on technique and methodology development for these degradation phenomena with the aim to monitor the paint degradation over time, preferably *in situ* in the gallery or museum.

Organization structure of deliverable

The deliverable is divided into three topics that cover crucial methodological elements for the preventative conservation of oil paintings. The topics are:

1. Monitoring chemical change and physical structural changes of paintings (issue A-E);
2. Monitoring of environmental indoor conditions (relevant for issues A-E);
3. Development of digital platform with focus on decision supportive tools (relevant for issues A-E).

Figure 1 depicts the structure of deliverable. The knowledge and data generated in topic 1 and 2 feeds topic 3.

Figure 1: Schematic scheme of structure topics in deliverable D5.3.

Each topic is subdivided into several projects, each focusing on a specific aspect of preventive conservation for oil paintings. Topic 1 is focused on the monitoring of chemical as well as surface physical changes and interlayer structural changes in oil paints due to time and environmental conditions. This topic develops methodologies to detect and monitor changes over time, which can be seen as part of a *multi-instrumental object monitoring toolkit* for assessing changes in objects. The methodologies are developed based on the five defined oil paint degradation phenomena issues (A-E), which are accommodated in separate projects.

Topic 2 explores the development of methods for monitoring environments and material emissions in museum settings. These methods aim to be user-friendly for non-experts and maintain comparability across various institutions and laboratories. The totality of these methods, some of which might require specific scientific expertise and facilities, and some of which might require low-cost field techniques of monitoring, can be seen as a *preventive conservation toolkit*.

Topic 3 developed a digital preventive conservation toolkit – a digital platform for remote preventive conservation decision making. The *digital preventive conservation toolkit* contains decision supporting tools for practitioners, museum professionals and object owners. These tools were developed specifically for risk factors to predict behaviour when exposed to them. The objective is to employ this knowledge to enhance the rationale behind decision-making processes. This requires significant reduction of complex set of data, dependences and uncertainties into simplified models that can be used by professionals responsible of decisions relevant for preventive conservation, which do not necessarily have specialized subject knowledge.

The core of this document delineates the protocols established within each respective project. It encompasses a comprehensive description of the project's scope and objectives, the analytical techniques and methodologies employed, practical and instrumental details, an elucidation of the protocol's advantages and limitations, and a prospective assessment of the subject matter. Furthermore, the accessibility of the techniques is denoted for each project through the IPERION HS catalogue of services. It is noteworthy that all projects within topic 1 were executed using mock-ups, with the intent of their potential applicability to authentic paintings. Numerous forthcoming publications covering most projects are in progress.

2.1 Topic 1: Monitoring chemical and physical structural changes of paintings

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- 2.1.2 Monitoring of lead soap formation in multilayered system
- 2.1.3 Monitoring of surface changes and interlayer structural changes of varnishes
- 2.1.4 Monitoring of water sensitive paint surfaces
- 2.1.5 Monitoring of flaking and delaminating in modern paint

2.1.1 Monitoring of light-induced changes of color of painted surfaces

I: Concept

This protocol aims at describing the monitoring of light-induced color changes of selected pigments in the oil binder, *via* a combination of complementary non-invasive imaging and single-point techniques and elemental speciation methods. The aim will be achieved by targeting the following objectives: (i) determination of the effects of different types of commercial white-light sources during microfading tests and conventional accelerated lightfastness tests; (ii) definition of key-parameters of lighting sources and experimental outputs important for monitoring the color (chemical) change process of the paint film. The outcomes of the research, through the building of a database of photoaged paints, will contribute to improve the interpretation of data from historical paintings and to develop a digital tool to predict colour modifications in historical paintings (cf. section 2.3).

II: Case study

1 Paint mock-ups preparation

Raw linseed oil paint mock-ups (ca. 200 in total; Figure 2) were prepared using the following commercial pigments: (i) red lead; (ii) carmine lake; (iii) strontium yellow; (iv) Prussian blue in mixture with lead white (weight ratio \approx 1:50).

Figure 2. Photographs of the analyzed oil paint mock-ups.

Pigments were selected based on their variable photochemical reactivity in the oil binder, as reported in previous studies. (Otero et al., 2017; Eastaugh et al., 2007; Yanuri et al., 2019; Vanmeert et al., 2015; Ferrer et al., 2019; Samain et al., 2013; Miliani et al. 2018). The oil:pigment mixtures (weight ratio \approx 1:4) were layered on a polycarbonate support, such as to obtain a paint film with an average thickness of about 200 μ m. Samples were then left dried in the dark for about two months. A series of samples made up of pure raw linseed oil were also prepared.

Each paint mock-up so prepared was studied according to the protocol described in section III.

III: Protocol

The protocol for monitoring of light-induced color change in painted surfaces involves the study of different sets of paint mock-ups (see section II) irradiated via microfading tests and conventional accelerated lightfastness tests. Overall, it consists in the steps 1 to 8 described here below (Figure 3 and section VIII for further details).

Figure 3. Scheme of the protocol of monitoring of light-induced changes of color of painted surfaces.

1 Multi-technique characterization of paint mock-ups before irradiation.

Different set of non-irradiated samples (ca. 10-20 in total) are distributed among each partner and analyzed by employing the following non-invasive and micro-destructive techniques (see sections VI and VIII for further details): UV-Vis-NIR-SWNIR spectroscopy (reflectance mode), colorimetry, FTIR spectroscopy (reflectance and transmission modes), Raman, OCT, XRF, XRD, UV Laser Induced Fluorescence, EPR. The same group of methods are also used to characterize the raw paint materials (i.e., pigment powders and pure raw linseed oil). Such a multi-technique approach provides an in-depth knowledge of the physico-chemical properties of the paint film, thus giving the possibility to perform a more accurate evaluation on the role of its component (pigment, additives/fillers of the pigment's formulation, binding medium, eventual compounds arising from pigment-oil interactions) during the photochemical process and the changes of color of the painted surfaces.

2 Characterization of the illumination source.

To make a reliable evaluation of results arising from microfading tests and conventional accelerated lightfastness tests, it is imperative that the source illumination is properly characterised in each case. Notably, the following parameters should be provided:

- spectral distribution of the light source;
- type of filter used for modulating the spectral emission of the light source;
- average irradiance (expressed in $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and illuminance (expressed in $\text{lux}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) measured at the sample's position;
- average temperature (expressed in $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{K}$) and relative humidity percentage measured at the sample's position;
- color temperature of the source;
- optical setup, focussing time and spot size of the lighting source [only applicable to microfading testers (MFTs)];
- total exposure time.

Within this project, the following lighting devices were selected: xenon light filtered in the UV-C, UV-B and IR spectral range; two cold WLEDs (color temperature: 4000 K and 5500 K); two warm WLEDs (color temperature: 2700 K) (Figure 4). The selection was based on the different emission of each source in the violet-blue range of the visible light; in addition, it is known that 4000 K and 2700 K WLEDs systems are installed in many museums nowadays.

Figure 4. Spectral irradiance profiles of the sources employed during A) conventional accelerated lightfastness test and B) microfading tests.

3 Preliminary microfading tests to define the total irradiance to stop the irradiation.

MFTs permit to perform experiments at fluence rates that are typically some orders of magnitude higher than conventional lighting sources installed in aging chambers (cf. Figure 3), thus remarkably shortening the irradiation and monitoring times. Preliminary microfading tests are therefore performed on the paint mock-ups. Irradiation are stopped until meaningful changes are not visible anymore in the reflectance spectra and values of CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ color coordinates.

Irradiation time of conventional accelerated lightfastness experiments are then calculated, such as to obtain comparable total irradiance values among each lighting devices (for the experiments here described: *ca.* 0.2 W/cm²·h).

4 Acquisition of diffuse reflectance spectra versus irradiance.

After white calibration of the spectrophotometer with a specific standard (e.g., spectralon), visible spectra in diffuse reflectance mode and corresponding color parameters are recorded before, during and at the end of the photoaging experiments.

The time interval acquisition is selected depending on the measured irradiance at the sample position (Figure 4). For a defined light source, microfading tests and conventional accelerated lightfastness experiments, when possible, are performed by keeping similar total irradiance values.

Microfading experiments are repeated on two-three spots of the same sample, while conventional accelerated lightfastness tests are carried out on two different sets of paint mock-ups.

Figure 4 shows a selection of the spectra recorded with increasing irradiance from one of the sets of paint mock-ups subject to a conventional accelerated lightfastness test with the xenon UV-IR filtered lamp. While very tiny differences are visible in the 600-700 nm range of the spectral reflectance of the red lead and carmine lake paint mock-ups, significant changes are observable in the spectra of strontium yellow and Prussian blue-based paints. Notably, with increasing irradiance, the reflectance increases between 520 and 560 nm and 430 and 460 nm for strontium yellow and Prussian blue, respectively. For the latter, changes of the reflectance are also visible for wavelengths above 1000 nm.

Similar spectral modifications are also observed for the sets of paint mock-ups aged with the 4000 K and 2700 K WLEDs as well as for the samples irradiated by MFTs (data not shown).

Figure 5. UV-Vis-NIR diffuse spectral reflectance spectra of oil paint mock-ups acquired at different irradiation steps of the conventional accelerated lightfastness test carried out with the xenon UV-IR filtered xenon lamp (Figure 3).

5 Calculation of various monitoring outputs versus irradiance.

Total color change (i.e., ΔE_{2000}) and spectral reflectance change ($\Delta R_{\lambda}(t)$) are calculated from the visible diffuse reflectance spectra recorded from samples irradiated by MFTs and conventional photoaging set-ups (Figure 4 for a selection of results). Such data are then compared each other's.

*Method based on CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ color space with irradiance:* calculation of ΔE_{2000} is performed using a D65 daylight illuminant and 2° standard observer. (CIE 2004; McLaren 1976) Figure 5 illustrates the plots of ΔE_{2000} versus the total irradiance for sets of paint mock-ups irradiated under different white lights emitted by conventional sources and MFTs. As expected, at any irradiance values, no meaningful color changes are visible for red lead and carmine lake mock-ups. Regardless from the white light source and experimental set-up used for aging, a

meaningful color change is instead visible for strontium yellow and Prussian blue paints. Modifications are faster during the first steps of irradiation.

Figure 6. Plot of ΔE_{2000} versus total irradiance/dose for the analyzed paint mock-ups during A) conventional accelerated lightfastness tests and B) micro-fading tests performed using different light sources and MFTs (cf. Figure 3 and section VIII for further details).

There are two aspects which must be underlined:

- (i) Among the light sensitive paints subject to conventional accelerated lightfastness tests, strontium yellow paints show the same tendency towards color change during exposure to the three selected light sources (final $\Delta E_{2000} \approx 5$). The final total color change of Prussian blue paint irradiated using the 2700 K WLEDs ($\Delta E_{2000} \approx 3$) is instead lower with respect to those irradiated with the 4000 K WLEDs and xenon lamp ($\Delta E_{2000} \approx 4$). In line with previous research, (Lerwill et al., 2015) such result highlights the effect of the amount of the blue component of the visible light (450-500 nm) on the color change process of Prussian blue.
- (ii) Despite the trend of ΔE_{2000} vs total irradiance obtained from samples subject to conventional photoaging and microfading tests under similar lighting conditions is comparable for each sample, final ΔE_{2000} values are different. Such difference, possibly

attributable to the dependency of ΔE calculation to different technical features of the employed experimental set-ups, requires further research.

b) Method based on visible spectral reflectance changes with irradiance.

Considering that the instantaneous spectral reflectance changes under irradiation at a given wavelength can be calculated according to eq. 1:

$$\Delta R(\lambda, t) = R(\lambda, t) - R(\lambda, 0) \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

with:

$R(\lambda, 0)$: vis diffuse reflectance spectrum before irradiation

$R(\lambda, t)$: vis diffuse reflectance spectrum at a given time step of irradiation

The mean change in the reflectance over a narrow spectral wavelength band versus time $\Delta R_\lambda(t)$, is given by eq.2:

$$\Delta R_\lambda(t) = \int_{\lambda-\delta\lambda}^{\lambda+\delta\lambda} \Delta R(\lambda, t) d\lambda / 2\delta\lambda \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

When there are multiple wavelength bands where changes are detected, the color change rates between samples are calculated by choosing the spectral window where the maximum reflectance change in spectra is occurring. In the specific case of the selected pigments, the wavelengths around which the average reflectance change was taken for red lead, carmine lake, strontium yellow, and Prussian blue-based paint mock-ups were 660 nm, 660 nm, 515 nm and 440 nm, respectively (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Plot of ΔR versus wavelength for the analyzed paint mock-ups irradiated by MFT (xenon UV-IR filtered source; total irradiance= 0.187 W/cm²·h) and a conventional lighting set-up (xenon UV-IR filtered source; total irradiance= 0.21 W/cm²·h; cf. spectra of Figure 4). The wavelength at which there is maximum reflectance change for each pigment can be determined from these plots and used to track reflectance evolution with irradiance.

Comparison between ΔR_λ obtained from microfading tests and conventional accelerated lightfastness experiments of paint mock-ups are very similar. This is more clearly appreciable

by looking to the plot of ΔR_{λ} versus total irradiance (in Figure 8, only that of Prussian blue is reported as an example). As already observed before (Figure 6A), ΔR_{λ} reaches lower values for the sample aged with 2700 K WLEDs. On the other hand, ΔR_{λ} values are comparable for samples irradiated using the MFT and conventional aging set-up, thus revealing that ΔR_{λ} might be a more specific parameter for describing the color change with respect to ΔE_{2000} . In addition, the result also indicates that, under the employed conditions, the higher intensity of MFT than that of the conventional photoaging set-up (ca. 20 times) does not affect the overall color change process.

Figure 8. Plot of ΔR_{λ} versus total irradiance for Prussian blue-based paint mock-ups subject to a microfading test (NTU MFT; xenon UV-IR-filtered) (blue), and to three different conventional accelerated lightfastness tests with different lightening devices (orange cross: xenon UV-IR-filtered source; green circle: WLEDs 4000 K; red cross: WLEDs 2700 K).

Forthcoming steps (to be concluded by January 2024)

6 Multi-technique characterization of paint mock-ups after irradiation.

The entire set of analytical techniques used in (1) is employed to measure the sets of paint mock-ups aged by conventional accelerated lightfastness experiments (see above and section VIII for details). Samples are circulated among laboratories of each partner involved in the activity and measurements are planned based on the potential radiation damage that might be induced by the analysis.

7 Assessment of the reciprocity principle and wavelength dependency.

Further tests can be performed on a not exposed set of paint mock-ups by repeating steps (2) – (6). They will permit to assess:

- the reciprocity principle of light exposure by varying the intensity/dose of the source;
- the wavelength dependency of the color change process using selected monochromatic sources.

8 Exploitation of research outputs on historical paintings.

Data obtained in (1-7) are then compared with those already available from historical paintings in order: (i) to improve their interpretation; (ii) to optimize the paint mock-ups preparation and protocol above described.

IV: Protocol limitations and advances

1 Advances

- Large number of samples that gives the possibility to perform also micro-destructive analysis and to enhance the statistical significance of the results;
- Flexible and controlled preparation of samples (composition, thickness, type of support, sizes...), which opens their investigations to a wide range of analytical techniques and allows performing more accurate investigations;
- the characterization of the illumination source, via accurate knowledge of its spectral irradiance and irradiance, allows limits of illuminance to be overcome, thus offering new insights into potential effects of the violet-blue component of the light on the overall photochemical process of the analyzed painting systems.
- ΔR_λ provides more direct information on the chemical changes of a specific pigment with respect to ΔE_{2000} , by reducing differences that may arise from technical features of the employed experimental set-ups;
- the exploitation of a wide range of analytical techniques before and after irradiation may contribute to identify chemical changes that cannot be detected by colorimetry and diffuse visible reflectance spectroscopy.
- for each technique, the potential identification of specific spectral markers/experimental outputs associated to the color changes can improve the interpretation of knowledge available from historical paintings.

2 Limitations

- limited representativeness of paint mock-ups, especially in terms of chemical composition, which may restrict the full exploitation of research outputs, being paintings exhibited in museums more complex systems;
- Local inhomogeneities of the analyzed samples (i.e., differences in the thickness of the paint, concentration of pigment, roughness of surface). They may affect the reproducibility of results, being even more critical in the case of MFTs experiments, during which smaller spots of the samples are probed.
- potential breaking down of reciprocity principle of light exposure within certain intervals of irradiance values.

V: Perspective and future directions

Next steps proposed are a systematic use and extension of the protocol here described to a wider set of paint mock-ups to increase the representativeness of results. Secondly, new parameters to define the safest levels of lighting conditions in museums should be defined. The proposed protocol here, via definition of safe doses and wavelength thresholds for exposure for light-sensitive painting materials, will help to define new parameters that allows overcoming limits of illuminance (that does not consider properly the spectral emission of a specific source, especially in the blue region).

Thirdly, building up of a database of photoaged painting materials is needed. This will be done by a systematic monitoring of color change during irradiation of paint mock-ups via an approach that combine a broad range of analytical elemental and molecular techniques. The datasets so obtained will be used for the interpretation of data from historical paintings of similar composition. At the same time, data from historical paintings will be exploited for improving the preparation and aging of paint mock-ups. Lastly, necessity for contribution towards optimization of measurements by MFTs on historical paintings. The systematic and preliminary study of a wide set of paint mock-ups by microfading tests (integrated, when possible, with conventional accelerated lightfastness experiments) will support the optimization of the protocol of analysis of historical paintings by MFTs.

VI: Access offered

CXRF/XRD, FORS, OCT, Raman, UV-laser induced fluorescence spectroscopy and Vis hyperspectral imaging, are offered by the MOLAB and FIXLAB and can be found in the catalogue of services (see also section VIII-4 for further details).

2.1.2 Monitoring of lead soap formation in multilayered system

I. Concept

This protocol aims to describe the monitoring of metal soap protrusions in easel paintings. Metal soap protrusions are the result of saponification of oil paint, a reaction between metal ions originating from metal salt pigments and free fatty acids that have formed in the oily binding medium (Hermans et al., 2019). Protrusions are aggregating metal soaps that push through the paint layers towards the surface (20-500 µm in diameter), while causing unwanted structural and aesthetic change to the paint layers (Noble, 2019). Abundantly present in works of art all over the world, metal soaps have been the topic of substantial fundamental research. However, remaining questions about the growth process of the protrusions, and the influence of environmental factors and remedial treatments make it hard to predict their trajectory. Therefore, condition monitoring can contribute significantly to our knowledge and aid conservators in their decision-making process. In this protocol steps for long-term, quantitative monitoring of metal soap protrusions in situ are discussed.

II. Case study – model systems

Multi-layered model systems were used to evaluate eight non-invasive monitoring techniques. The model systems were developed to form lead soap protrusions in situ in a relatively short time of a few weeks to months. In order to meet these criteria, high concentrations of reactive components were added to the model systems in the form of a so-called active layer. These reactive components are lead acetate heptahydrate and margaric acid. The reaction between these two components yields lead heptadecanoate, referred to here as a lead soap, and acetic acid. The active layer was applied on top of a stretched canvas that was prepared with a glue-sizing and a chalk-glue ground layer to represent a typical easel painting substrate. Two different types of model systems were created by applying two different oil-based paints on top of the active layer: one containing smalt, a translucent blue cobalt-glass pigment, and another iron oxide, an opaque red pigment. This was done in order to represent a variety of paint properties to test the limitations of the eight monitoring techniques.

The model systems were created by adding reactive components at the start to form protrusions in a very short time. These conditions, high concentrations of fatty acids and lead ions in a very fresh, even liquid, oil layer, are not representative of the conditions under which metal soaps generally form in paintings. The process is generally thought of as more gradual, where fatty acids are released from the binding medium over time and react with lead ions (Hermans et al., 2019). Therefore, the kinetics and chemical pathways of metal soap formation in these model systems may not be realistic. For the purpose of evaluating the techniques, however, the model systems show sufficient chemical, optical and structural similarities with real lead soap protrusions.

Figure 9. Schematic representations of the model systems when freshly prepared ($t = 0$) and after the 6-month monitoring period ($t = 6$ months). Three morphologies were observed: areas where the active layer had mostly disappeared; areas where the active layer had thickened and formed local domains of crystalline lead soaps; and areas with distinct protrusion-like structures containing crystalline lead soaps.

The model systems were prepared in Amsterdam and sent out to six partners of the IPERION-HS consortium for a 6-month monitoring campaign. The samples were kept in each laboratory at constant RH and T (50% and 30 °C). The non-invasive monitoring techniques are evaluated in their suitability to answer three questions: Can the technique detect protrusions? Can it detect change in the protrusions? Can it detect early-warning signs? Here, early-warning signs are defined as sub-surface indications that a protrusion will form before the surface is visibly affected. Comparison between the techniques is performed on the basis of quantitative data on the growth of the lead soap protrusions in the model systems. The monitoring data is also compared to cross-sections of the model systems.

Figure 10. Overview of the evaluated monitoring techniques and the research questions. In the centre is an image of a large lead soap protrusion in Rembrandt’s *Night Watch*.

III. Protocol

Eight techniques were evaluated for their suitability to monitor metal soap protrusions in situ and non-invasively in a monitoring experiment. Monitoring goes beyond the detection of a certain condition phenomenon. It requires multiple captures of the phenomenon over time and the assessment of change. In this experiment, change assessment was approached in a quantitative manner. The findings of the experiment are summarised here per technique. Furthermore, a general protocol is presented for long-term, quantitative condition monitoring.

The eight techniques were selected because they are non or minimally invasive, portable or transportable, available in the conservation science field, and because they are theoretically suited to detect metal soap protrusions. Optical coherence spectroscopy, x-radiography and external reflection Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy have previously been applied for the detection of metal soap protrusions in works of art. Table 1 contains key references per technique. Here follows a short discussion of the results of the 6-month monitoring of the model systems. Table 2 summarises the findings per technique.

Technique	Key references
External Reflection Fourier-Transform infrared spectroscopy	(Gabrieli et al., 2017 ; Garrappa et al., 2021 ; Rosi et al., 2019)
Colorimetry	(Fontana et al., 2015)
Visible to near-infrared multispectral imaging colorimetry	(Striova et al., 2018)
Technical photography (visible light; raking light; ultraviolet-induced luminescence)	(Dyer et al., 2013 ; Frey et al., 2017)
X-radiography	(Boon et al., 2002; Padfield et al., 2002)
Acoustic microscopy	(Karagiannis et al., 2011)
Optical coherence tomography	(Cheung et al., 2015; Targowski et al., 2020; van den Berg et al., 2019; Vichi et al., 2019)
Micro-profilometry	(Fontana et al., 2004)

Table 1. Key references per monitoring technique.

External Reflection Fourier-Transform infrared spectroscopy

Macro-external reflection infrared spectroscopy, despite its high specificity for metal soaps, could not detect metal soaps in the model systems. This was due the relatively large measuring area (20 mm²) and the relatively low concentration of metal soaps in the model systems. Using cross-section analysis and micro-external reflection infrared spectroscopy the presence of metal soaps in the model systems was confirmed. The limit of detection, therefore, is important to consider for macro-external reflection infrared spectroscopy. Furthermore, this technique is sensitive to surface morphology.

Colorimetry

The colorimetry was not a suitable technique for detection of metal soap protrusions in the model systems, because it has a large measuring area and therefore detects bulk color change. The scale of the metal soap protrusions is too small. In the monitoring experiment, the detected color change in the model systems was mainly associated with the oil paint itself, not with the protrusions. In addition, colorimetry measurements are affected by surfaces that are shiny or superficially rough.

Visible to near-infrared multispectral imaging colorimetry

Innovative coupling of three-dimensional surface maps obtained with micro-profilometry to multispectral images obtained with the visible to near-infrared multispectral imaging allowed for the detection and quantification of local color change, specifically associated with the protrusions in the model systems. In the monitoring experiment sufficient reproducibility between measurements was achieved to follow individual protrusions over time.

Technical photography (visible light; raking light; ultraviolet-induced luminescence)

Ultraviolet-induced luminescence photography did not visualise protrusions in the model systems. The protrusions in the model systems were best visible and raking light photography. The protrusions in the smalt model system were better visible than in the red oxide model systems, because the whitish protrusions could be distinguished in the translucent smalt paint layer. The method for quantification of change used for this technique was based on the contrast between the lighter protrusions and the darker surroundings. The specificity for protrusions was low, as non-related surface phenomena (shiny/matte areas in the paint, dust and the canvas structure) interfered. Furthermore, it is challenging to achieve reproducible results with technical photography, as it is sensitive to changes in setup in terms of distance, illumination, acquisition parameters, angle.

X-radiography

X-radiography was successful in detecting protrusions in the model systems. The suitability of this technique to detect metal soap protrusions depends on the electron density of the surrounding materials. The best results were obtained for the smalt model systems, as good contrast was achieved between the protrusions and the surrounding paint layer. When sufficient contrast is obtained, quantification of the area covered by protrusions is possible.

Acoustic microscopy

This technique was able to detect the structure of the protrusions in the model systems, including the sub-surface portion. An advantage of this technique is that the acoustic waves can penetrate a wide range of materials. However, the application of a coupling gel on the surface of the object is necessary for measurements. Furthermore, the depth resolution was not sufficient for quantification of changes in dimension (height and width) of the protrusions in the model systems.

Optical coherence tomography

Two types of optical coherence tomography were evaluated, with two different laser wavelengths (850 and 1300 nm). Both systems were suitable for the detection of the structure of the protrusions in the model systems, including their subsurface portion. The 1300 nm system was able to penetrate the opaque iron-oxide paint layer whereas the 850 nm system could not. Both systems have sufficient depth resolution for quantifying the change in dimensions (height and width) of the protrusions in the model systems. However, not only depth resolution was found to be of importance. Sufficient lateral resolution is needed to analyse exactly the same position over time. A low lateral resolution may lead to an unreliable monitoring result, as line scans can be shifted several tens of micrometres laterally from one measurement to another, potentially slicing the protrusion differently and obtaining a different measure of its dimensions. The 850 nm system did not have sufficient lateral resolution for the determination of change in individual protrusions due to the experimental setup. Therefore, a different method of quantification was opted for, where the surface area associated with protrusions was calculated individually for each time step. For this approach alignment in z-direction (baseline correction) of the three-dimensional surface profiles is critical.

Micro-profilometry

This technique was able to detect the structure of the protrusions in the model systems. The lateral and depth resolution were sufficient to follow individual protrusions over time. The reproducibility of the measurements is impacted by changes in angle and position of the detector and by vibration. Signal-to-noise ratio is dependent on the color the sample.

Technique	Summary of findings	Points of attention	(Trans)portable/ non-invasive
External Reflection Fourier-Transform infrared spectroscopy	Did not detect protrusions, despite its high chemical specificity for metal soaps. This was due to the limit of detection and the	This technique is sensitive to surface morphology.	Transportable and non-invasive.

	relatively low concentration of lead soaps in the model systems.		
Colorimetry	Did not detect protrusions, as the bulk colour change overpowered the local color change corresponding to the protrusions. The technique therefore has low specificity for metal soap protrusions.	Measurements are affected by surfaces that are shiny or superficially rough.	Portable and non-invasive.
Visible to near-infrared multispectral imaging colorimetry	Did detect protrusions with high specificity. Innovative coupling to micro-profilometry allowed assessment of color change at the micro-scale specifically corresponding to protrusions.	Quantification of change in VIS-NIR maps is sensitive to reproducibility of the measurements (position, angle).	Transportable and non-invasive.
Technical photography (visible light; raking light; ultraviolet-induced luminescence)	The protrusions were best visible in raking light and visible light photography. The technique has low specificity to protrusions, as other surface features can be mistaken for protrusions. Quantification of change challenging due to low specificity to metal soaps.	Challenging to achieve reproducible results (sensitive to changes in setup in terms of distance, illumination, acquisition parameters, angle).	Portable and non-invasive.
X-radiography	Able to detect protrusions with high specificity. Quantification of the	Specificity will depend strongly on the properties of the	Non-portable and non-invasive.

	surface covered by protrusions was achieved.	materials that surround the protrusions.	
Acoustic microscopy	Able to detect protrusions. In addition, it has the capability to detect protrusions sub-surface as it is a tomographic technique.	Assessment of changes in dimensions of the protrusions was not possible as the depth resolution was insufficient. Horizontal geometry preferred due to coupling gel.	Transportable and invasive as it requires the application of a coupling gel on the painted surface.
Optical coherence tomography	Able to detect metal soap protrusions. Penetration to reveal sub-surface structure of protrusions depends on wavelength of laser and properties of paint. Quantification of surface covered by protrusions was possible using obtained three-dimensional surface profiles.	Quantification of dimensional change of individual protrusions was only reliable when lateral resolution was sufficient.	Transportable and non-invasive.
Micro-profilometry	Able to detect protrusions. Quantification of changes in surface covered by protrusions and dimensional change of individual protrusions was possible.	Reproducibility of the measurements are impacted by changes in angle and position of the detector and by vibration. Signal-to-noise ratio is dependent on the color the sample.	The microprofilometry is transportable and non-invasive.

Table 2. Summary of findings of the 6-month monitoring experiment using model systems.

The developed protocol for monitoring metal soap protrusions in paintings contains 10 steps (Figure 11). Here follows a brief discussion of the steps applied to monitoring of metal soap protrusions.

Figure 11. Protocol for long-term quantitative monitoring.

1. Question-led monitoring

As with any type of research it is essential for monitoring to define a question and develop a hypothesis. An example of a question related to metal soap protrusions could be about the effect of aqueous cleaning on the rate of zinc soap protrusion growth considering the recent insights into the role of water as a catalyst for zinc soap crystallisation (Hermans et al. 2023).

2. Frequency of measurements

How often one should measure depends on the expected rate of the change of the monitored phenomenon. To know the expected rate, a hypothesis is necessary about the underlying mechanisms that are responsible for this change. Furthermore, evidence of past change can be reviewed. In contrast to the model systems developed for this project, metal soap protrusions are generally considered to form in a time frame of several years to decades (Noble 2019). Capturing a slow process may require long-term monitoring over decades.

3. Scale: resolution and sensitivity

Metal soap protrusions in easel paintings are small phenomena, generally between 10-500 mm in diameter (Noble 2019; Boon et al. 2002; Salvant et al. 2019, Centeno and Mahon 2009). For monitoring, techniques with appropriate resolution should be selected. Depth resolution is particularly important to consider when quantifying changes in dimension of the protrusions. Lateral resolution of three-dimensional imaging techniques is important to consider when attempting to follow exactly the same protrusion over time. In addition to resolution, the limit of detection should be considered.

4. Specificity

It is important to understand how specific a technique is to the phenomenon that is to be monitored. If the technique is measuring the phenomenon indirectly or with low specificity, this may complicate quantification. An example of this was encountered during the monitoring of the model systems with raking light photography. Several surface features interfered with reliable quantification.

5. Measurement conditions and reproducibility

Reproducibility is key for monitoring. Especially during long-term, in-situ monitoring it is extremely challenging to avoid changes in the setup and measurements conditions (position, angle, rotation, lighting conditions). Monitoring small-scale phenomena such as metal soap protrusions is sensitive to changes in setup. Determining changes in individual protrusions requires sufficient depth and lateral resolution. In case sufficient reproducibility between subsequent measurements is not achievable, one can opt for different data analysis methods for change assessment. For example, subtracting two mapped surfaces that are not aligned perfectly will result in significant error. Conversely, calculating the fraction of the total surface associated with protrusions independently for each time point is less sensitive to changes in lateral alignment. Calculating a surface fraction, does not give spatial information, i.e., where the changes occurred on the surface.

6. Complementary techniques

Condition phenomena may have more than one property that can be measured. Examples of measurable properties of metal soap protrusions are color, three-dimensional structure, and chemical composition. Therefore, using a combination of complementary techniques for monitoring aids interpretation of the measured changes.

7. Statistical relevance

Is one individual example of a protrusion followed over time or is the response of a group averaged? Following specific locations over time is challenging and prone to error due to reproducibility issues. Averaging the response of a group, therefore, could produce more reliable trends. However, it is possible that protrusions in different parts of a painting exhibit different behaviour, for example due to local availability of reactants or nonuniform treatment application in the past.

8. Quantitative change assessment

Two approaches for quantifying change in the model systems were explored during the monitoring experiment: assessing changes in dimensions of the protrusions (height and width) and assessing changes in surface area covered by protrusions. The first approach was only possible for three-dimensional imaging techniques with sufficiently high spatial and depth resolution. The latter was applied for three- and two-dimensional imaging techniques. In addition to imaging techniques, colorimetry is an example of a technique that provides point-based quantitative assessment of change, in this case of color.

9. Connecting condition to external factors

Changes in condition very often occur under the influence of external factors, such as conservation treatment or the environment. Examples of environmental parameters are relative humidity, temperature, light, pollution, air flow, etc. Connecting changes in condition to external factors is central in the investigation of the mechanism responsible for the change. This can be done by comparing different data sets, for example coupling condition monitoring to environmental monitoring. Establishing in advance which data sets are going to be compared will help synchronising the monitoring strategies, for example in terms of measurement frequency.

10. Data management

Data management has not been the topic of Project 2 in Task 5.1, but nevertheless is critical. Long-term monitoring will result in large quantities of data that need to be organised, stored and maintained properly, for example according to the FAIR (Findable Accessibly Interoperable and Reusable) Data Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016). In addition to the organisation and storage of the acquired data, proper documentation of the measurements themselves (setup, settings, conditions, frequency, etc.) is key to ensure long-term consistency. Furthermore, instruments are continuously improved and replaced, which can have an effect on the reproducibility of the measurements. Practical aspects such as the aforementioned should all be part of a long-term monitoring strategy.

The final important step of this protocol aimed at long-term quantitative condition monitoring is a *pilot study*. Each monitoring programme will pose unique challenges as no work of art is the same. A pilot study entails performing two consecutive measurements as one would when monitoring, including setting up the equipment twice (ideally by two different competent operators) and performing the data analysis. An experiment like this serves two purposes. Firstly, many issues will undoubtedly be encountered that can be resolved before the start of the actual monitoring, for example regarding positioning of the instrument or accounting for different lighting conditions depending on the time of day. Secondly, the analysed trial data will provide an indication of the error introduced by reproducibility issues. This error can be compared to the expected scale of the phenomenon in question to ensure that the desired sensitivity is achieved.

IV. Protocol limitations and advantages

The protocol presented here is a general protocol for long-term quantitative condition monitoring. The steps can be applied to the monitoring of any condition phenomena. Each work of art has unique requirements for monitoring and for that reason will require specific experimental conditions. This protocol aims to guide conservators in their design of a monitoring campaign by presenting lessons that were learned during the monitoring experiment.

V. Perspective and future directions

This study could be expanded with more non-invasive techniques. An example of a technique that is commonly used in the cultural heritage field and that could be explored for the monitoring of metal soaps is X-ray fluorescence mapping. Furthermore, the study could also be expanded in terms of the model systems. Testing different paint layer pigmentations could

provide additional insights into the suitability of the monitoring techniques. Lastly, it would be very interesting to explore more sophisticated techniques for the recognition of metal soap protrusions.

VI. Access offered

All techniques reviewed in this project are accessible via MOLAB or FIXLAB, apart from colorimetry and technical photography. The latter two are generally considered accessible as they require (adapted) equipment that are widely available.

Technique	Access
External Reflection Fourier-Transform infrared spectroscopy	MOLAB
Colorimetry	-
Visible to near-infrared multispectral imaging colorimetry	MOLAB
Technical photography (visible light; raking light; ultraviolet-induced luminescence)	-
X-radiography	FIXLAB
Acoustic microscopy	MOLAB
Optical coherence tomography	MOLAB
Micro-profilometry	MOLAB

VII. Additional references

Manuscript with title “Developing a non-invasive toolbox for quantitative monitoring of metal soap protrusions in paintings for preventive conservation” is expected to be published open access in 2024.

2.1.3 Monitoring of surface changes and interlayer structural changes of varnishes

I: Concept – description of the aim and objectives of the project

This project aims at monitoring/assessing the chemical and physical (morphological and mechanical) changes induced both on the surface and in-depth of varnished painting layers upon artificial ageing, a question of high relevance for designing adequate preventive conservation actions of varnished paintings of the historic/artistic heritage. The monitoring of changes was addressed both in the presence and in the absence of the pigment-based paint layers.

II: Case study – object/ mock-ups

The mock-up samples used in the framework of Project 3 were prepared by partners from Nicolaus Copernicus University (NCU), Poland. They consist of 36 samples based on single and double varnish layers, with and without oil paint layers underneath. Also, in some cases, a partial black layer, simulating a dirt layer, is inserted between the varnish layers, to get as close as possible to real cases (Table 3). The mock-up samples were divided into three similar sets with 12 samples each one, representing a large variety of possible paint systems. The considered varnishes were dammar (natural varnish glossy 081, Talens) and acrylic (Varnish glossy 114, Talens), and the oil-based paints used were Titanium white (TiO_2) and ochre yellow ($\text{FeO(OH)} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$) from Rembrandt, Talens. The varnish samples, consisting of single and double layers, were laid on glass substrates with dimensions of $80 \times 30 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ and left to dry for the necessary time. The thickness of the varnish layers determined by Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) was in the range of $30\text{-}115 \mu\text{m}$ (Table 3). For the preparation of paint layers, the oil-based paints were laid as a film on the same substrates as those used for the varnish samples with thicknesses between 100 and $200 \mu\text{m}$ and allowed to dry under ambient conditions (temperature and relative humidity) for 3-4 months. After preparation and subsequent drying of the pigment-based paint mock-ups, the samples were varnished using both dammar and acrylic varnishes, forming a single and/or double-varnish layer on top of the paints with similar thicknesses as those applied on glass substrates with a dirt layer intentionally and partially embedded in between the two layers of varnish. Both the varnish and the varnished paint mock-up samples were submitted to accelerated photo and thermohygrometric ageing by exposure to artificial solar radiation and in controlled environment conditions (temperature/relative humidity) for 15 days (Figure 12). Details of these two ageing procedures are as follows:

- Photoageing (Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Italy ISPC-CNR): Filtered Xenon lamp emitting at $\lambda > 330 \text{ nm}$, environmental temperature and relative humidity with an average flux of $2 \times 10^5 \mu\text{W/s} \times \text{cm}^2$.

- Thermo-hygro-metric ageing (Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Italy SCITEC-CNR): Environmental test chamber to artificially control the temperature and humidity conditions and to accelerate the effects of exposure to the environment by cycle stress. Temperature range -10 °C to 80 °C and relative humidity range from 0% to 90%.
- Natural ageing for 128 days: Samples stored in laboratory conditions (in the dark with ambient temperature and humidity) are considered as a reference.

The samples prepared present smooth, very flat air/varnish and varnish/paint interfaces when compared to real samples (Figure 12). They represent a high variety of cases of mock-up painting systems, aiming to get as close as possible to real cases.

	samples	sample no/label	Varnish thickness range by OCT (µm)
A		A1	57-58
		A2	55-59
		A3	46-50
C		C1	45-48
		C2	50-51
		C3	51-55
E		E1	50-53
		E2	49-51
		E3	42-48
G		G1	75-78
			58-59
		G2	82-90
			42-45
		G3	110-115
			30-40
I		I1	57-61
			55-63
		I2	61-69
			41-45
		I3	92-94
			38-40
K		K1	50-86
			33
		K2	66-71
			15-18
		K3	66-69

			40
B		B1	45-48
		B2	45-48
		B3	49-50
D		D1	55-59
		D2	54-59
		D3	51-57
F		F1	48-50
		F2	48-49
		F3	51-53
H		H1	63-65
			54-55
		H2	55-58
			50-53
		H3	75-78
82-87			
J		J1	54-57
			51-55
		J2	54-57
			51-54
		J3	58-59
69-70			
L		L1	55-58
			51-55
		L2	58-61
			57-62
		L3	55-59
59-65			

Table 3. Summary of the 36 prepared mock-up samples with the varnish thickness and their corresponding labelling before ageing.

Figure 12. Sets of mock-up samples SET 1, SET 2 and SET 3, after thermo-hygrometric, photo and natural ageing (reference), respectively.

III: Protocol

The changes associated with the artificial degradation of the varnishes (by thermo-hygrometric, photo and natural ageing) were assessed using a combination of non-invasive chemical and structural analytical techniques. For monitoring the development and degree of ageing processes on the varnish layers, the analytical strategy proposed consisted of using Colorimetry and Fluorescence Spectroscopy.

Figure 13 shows the total color changes induced by artificial and natural ageing on varnished mock-up samples indicating higher variation values in the presence of TiO_2 -based paintings than in the case of the varnish alone or in the presence of yellow ochre-based paintings.

On the other hand, as an example of the results from the artificial photo-ageing, the mock-up samples based on dammar varnish show higher fluorescence emissions and red shifting than those based on acrylic resin, indicating higher ageing effects on dammar varnish and higher stability of acrylic resin. Besides, varnished titanium dioxide-based mock-ups show higher fluorescence intensities than those based on the ochre yellow pigment due to the contribution of the TiO_2 -based paint to the varnish's own fluorescence (Figure 14).

Figure 13. Total color changes ΔE^* recorded on the varnished mock-up samples after artificial (15 days) and natural (128 days) ageing.

Figure 14. Changes in the fluorescence maxima at 450 nm upon photo-ageing indicating the formation of degraded species (chemical changes).

Table 4 shows a summary of the chemical changes induced on the considered mock-up samples upon artificial and natural ageing.

Ageing type	Varnish samples	Varnish on TiO ₂ based painting	Varnish on ochre yellow based painting
Thermo-hygrometric ageing (15 days)	ΔE^* and fluorescence higher for dammar	Higher ΔE^* and fluorescence increase for both dammar and acrylic with red shifting.	Lower ΔE^* values and low fluorescence intensity increase for both dammar and acrylic (autoabsorption affecting the emission, but the general trend is that with this pigment the effect of the ageing is slight)
Photo-ageing (15 days)	ΔE^* higher for dammar Fluorescence intensity increase for both dammar and acrylic	Higher ΔE^* and fluorescence increase for both dammar and acrylic with red shifting.	Lower ΔE^* values and low fluorescence intensity increase for both dammar and acrylic (autoabsorption affecting the emission, but the general trend is that with this pigment the effect of the ageing is slight)
Natural ageing (128 days)	ΔE^* values similar for dammar and acrylic, Fluorescence intensity increases only for dammar	Higher ΔE^* and fluorescence increase for both dammar and acrylic with red shifting.	Lower ΔE^* values and low fluorescence intensity increase for both dammar and acrylic (autoabsorption affecting the emission, but the general trend is that with this pigment the effect of the ageing is slight)

Table 4. Summary of the main changes observed during artificial and natural ageing monitored by colorimetry and fluorescence spectroscopy.

Once the different ageing processes were completed, the chemical and structural changes of the varnish and varnished paint mock-ups, were assessed using different analytical techniques available in the laboratories of the partners taking part in the round-Robin test (see Table 5 below). The techniques chosen were: optical coherence tomography OCT (Ford et al., 2021)(Liang et al., 2017), colorimetry, UV-Vis spectroscopy, multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography, Spectral domain-OCT, laser scanning microprofilometry (Fontana et al., 2015), hybrid combination of OCT (1250 nm) and microscopic hyperspectral imaging (405-845nm) for varnish extinction coefficient determination, laser-induced fluorescence LIF (Kokkinaki et al., 2021), Raman spectroscopy and nonlinear optical microscopy in the modality of multiphoton excitation fluorescence NLOM-MPEF (Liang et al., 2017)(Martínez-Weinbaum et al., 2023)(Theodorakopoulos et al., 2007).

Partners and order of Participation	Available techniques
(1) Magdalena Iwanicka and Piotr Targowski, NCU, Poland	Optical Coherence Tomography OCT
(2) Cristiano Riminesi, ISPC-CNR, Italy	Hyperspectral imaging; UV-Vis spectroscopy; Colorimetry
(3) Francesca Rosi, SCITEC-CNR, Italy	Hyperspectral imaging in the mid-IR; UV-Vis spectroscopy reflection and emission; Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)
(4) Raffaella Fontana and Alice Dal Fovo, INO-CNR, Italy	Optical coherence tomography (Spectral domain-OCT); Laser scanning microprofilometry; Multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography
(5) Haida Liang, Patrick Atkinson and Sammy Cheung, NTU, England	Combination of OCT (1250 nm) and Microscopic hyperspectral Imaging (405-845 nm)
(6) Paraskevi Pouli, Kristalia Melesanaki et al., FORTH, Greece	Raman Spectroscopy; Laser Induced Fluorescence; LED Induced Fluorescence
(7) Mohamed Oujja, Paula Carmona, Marta Castillejo, IQF-CSIC, Spain	UV Laser Induced Fluorescence; 3D-Multiphoton excitation fluorescence (MPEF)

Table 5. Partners with the order of their participation in the round-Robin test and available analytical techniques.

Spectral domain-optical coherence tomography, with a high lateral and in-depth resolution, was used to provide information on the exact thickness of varnish layers, and interlayer structural changes after ageing. Changes in the roughness and reflectance maxima were also measured (Table 6). The obtained results indicate a decrease in the thickness of the varnish layers upon artificial ageing. OCT allowed also detecting the dirt layer inserted intentionally in between the varnish layers (Figure 15).

Figure 15. OCT image from a mock-up sample (G1) composed of two varnish layers (acrylic resin on dammar) with a dirt layer in between on a glass substrate.

Laser scanning microprofilometry measurements revealed an increase in the roughness of the artificial aged varnish mock-up samples (Table 6). The thermo-hygrometric ageing induces more effects than photo and natural ageing with R_q values of 2.6, 2.3 and 1.2, respectively. Multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography measurements indicate higher ageing effects under thermo-hygrometric ageing than when it comes to photo and natural ageing as can be seen in Table 4. A decrease in the maximum reflectance at 1292 nm is observed (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography from varnish mock-up samples composed of synthetic varnish on ochre yellow based paint after thermo-hygrometric (F1), photo (F2) and natural ageing (F3). The obtained spectra were averaged over an area of 2 mm diameter.

As a general observation, the effects induced by artificial ageing are more pronounced in the case of thermo-hygrometric ageing than photo and natural (reference) ageing.

Techniques	Analysis output	F1 sample Thermo- hygrometric aged	F2 sample Photoaged	F3 sample Natural aged
Multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography	Max Reflectance % at 1292 nm	42.19 %	52.14 %	52.25 %
Optical Coherence Tomography	Synthetic varnish thickness in μm . After aging (black) Before aging (red)	37 \pm 7 49 \pm 4	45 \pm 7 48 \pm 2	61 \pm 5 52 \pm 3
Laser Scanning Microprofilometry	Roughness - Ra (μm)	1.9 \pm 0.2	1.8 \pm 0.1	1.6 \pm 0.1
	Roughness - Rq (μm)	2.6 \pm 0.6	2.3 \pm 0.2	1.2 \pm 0.1

Table 6. Results obtained on a selection of aged samples (samples F1, F2 and F3) using OCT, laser scanning microprofilometry and Vis-NIR reflectography.

A hybrid combination of OCT (1250 nm) and microscopic hyperspectral imaging (405-845nm) was also used for varnish extinction coefficient determination to assess the effects induced on the varnish optical properties after artificial ageing. Using this hybrid technique, the varnish thickness map can be extracted and the extinction coefficient of the varnish layers can then be calculated by combining the spectral reflectance and varnish thickness per pixel. Figure 17 shows an example of using this technique to obtain the varnish extinction coefficient spectra of two different mock-up samples composed of dammar varnish on TiO_2 and ochre yellow-based paintings under thermo-hygrometric ageing (samples C2 and E2, see Table 3). The obtained results indicate almost similar absorption coefficient spectra for C2 and E2 samples, independently of the underneath paint substrate.

Figure 17. Varnish extinction coefficients of dammar varnish from mock-up samples C2 and E2 based on TiO_2 and ochre yellow paints, respectively, were obtained using the hybrid technique combining OCT and microscopic hyperspectral imaging.

To continue investigating the effects induced by artificial ageing on the considered varnish and paint-varnished mock-up samples, LIF and Raman spectroscopies were also used. It is observed that the artificial ageing results in higher LIF intensities accompanied by a red shift of the λ_{max} of the fluorescence emission. These modifications were indicative of the

participation of different ageing processes. Specifically, the increase in fluorescence intensity and the red-shifted bands are associated with the presence and formation of new fluorophores (i.e. new C=C bonds show increased fluorescence at longer wavelengths) and can be linked with the production of oxidized and cross-linked products occurring during ageing induced polymerization. The LIF results indicate more accentuated effects when it comes to thermo-hygrometric artificial ageing (J1) than photo (J2) and natural (J3) ageing (Figure 18). However, the Raman results have not been able to detect important chemical changes induced in the different varnishes and varnished paint mock-up samples due to artificial and natural ageing, apart from a slight increase in the intensity of the varnish bands and a decrease in those corresponding to the TiO₂ pigment indicated in blue and red colors, respectively, in Figure 19.

Figure 18. LIF measurements on varnished mock-up samples (J) indicating higher chemical effects induced by thermo-hygrometric ageing with red-shifting of the maximum emission from 450 to 472 nm.

Figure 19. Raman bands from samples J1, J2 and J3 corresponding to mock-up samples composed of dammar varnish on acrylic with a dirt layer in between applied on TiO₂-based paint. In blue are indicated the bands corresponding to the varnish and in red those corresponding to the TiO₂ pigment.

Finally, the non-linear optical microscopy in the modality of multiphoton excitation fluorescence (NLOM-MPEF) was used to determine non-invasively the thickness of the different varnish layers and to get in-depth information on the degradation gradient induced upon artificial ageing of the considered varnishes. The latter can be assessed by in-depth monitoring of the MPEF signal from the more aged regions (superficial areas of the varnish) with regard to the non-aged ones (internal bulk areas) taking into account that the varnish does not age homogeneously throughout its layer thickness (Martínez-Weinbaum et al., 2023).

As an example, Figure 20 shows the MPEF profile of the dammar varnish artificially aged with information on the in-depth evolution of the degradation gradient (exponential evolution) and on the thickness of the degraded varnish (32 μm).

Figure 20. MPEF in-depth profile artificial aged dammar varnish mock-up sample. The grey stripes display the in-depth affected region obtained using a Lorentzian fit of this part of the MPEF profile. A top-hat fit of the total profile (red line) serves to determine the total thickness of the varnish layer.

A complete report, after each partner's participation in the round-robin test, with a detailed explanation and interpretation of the obtained results has been prepared.

IV: Protocol limitations and advances

During the project development, different limitations and challenges have been encountered as those mentioned below. Approaches to overcome some drawbacks are also described. In thermo-hydrometric ageing, the first 5 days have not been able to induce measurable chemical changes in the mock-ups. To overcome this, the thermo-hygrometric ageing conditions were varied during the ageing treatments for more time to induce higher and deeper ageing effects. This approach overcomes the detection limit for each experimental technique to be used.

Monitoring in-depth the chemical and structural induced changes in aged varnishes is challenging. The use of analytical techniques allowing in-depth chemical monitoring such as NLOM-MPEF are promising to overcome this challenge.

The hybrid "OCT + microscopic hyperspectral imaging" method works well on real paintings, but it was somehow challenging for some of the mock-ups due to a very flat air/varnish and varnish/paint interface.

The laser induced fluorescence (LIF) emission from varnish on yellow ochre-based paint is lower due to self-absorption processes. NLOM-MPEF with high sensitivity and in-depth resolution allowed overcoming this issue.

It is still challenging to make all analytical techniques presented in this project suitable for monitoring in a museum environment. However, the use of portable analytical techniques working in a remote and non-invasive way such as laser induced fluorescence and multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography with OCT, is suitable and helpful.

In the case of using mock-up samples to be checked by different analytical techniques, appropriate graduated masks to delimitate the areas to be checked were prepared. It is important to stress that for monitoring studies the instrumental settings are critical to keep consistent in reproducing the obtained results. In this project, the obtained results are based on averaging procedures to minimise the errors.

V: Perspective and future directions

The analytical techniques used in the framework of this project applied in different laboratories have shown high sensitivity and efficiency to determine and monitor in a non-invasive way the chemical and structural changes induced on natural and artificial aged varnish and varnished paint-based mock-up samples both on the surface and in-depth.

To make varnish monitoring in paintings successful and ready to be implemented in museums more advances in the field of analytical methods, with a special focus on non-invasive approaches and portable equipment, hybrid instrumentation, or hyphenated techniques, methodologies, and strategies operating in remote mode with high sensitivity are needed. This will allow for improving the implementation of preventive and non-invasive conservation procedures including new tools for managing and accessing data.

In the field of paint conservation, the knowledge of the thickness of the degraded varnish is of high importance for its removal and replacement processes. In this sense, the NLOM-MPEF technique has shown great versatility and flexibility for the determination of the chemical changes, the thickness and the degradation gradient of the varnish material in a totally non-invasive way. However, this technique is currently applicable at the laboratory level, although we believe that due to the rapid advances in femtosecond laser technology, optical component arrangements, and signal detection systems, it will not take long to dispose of portable systems to carry out NLOM-MPEF measurements on varnished painting objects in a museum.

VI: Access offered:

The Optical Coherence Tomography (NCU, Poland), the laser scanning microprofilometry and multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography (INO-CNR, Italy), and the hyperspectral imaging system (NTU, England) are offered as MOLAB services.

UV Laser Induced Fluorescence and 3-D Multiphoton excitation fluorescence (MPEF) (IQF-CSIC) are offered as a FIXLAB service.

2.1.4 Monitoring of water-sensitive paint surfaces

I: Concept

This project aims to assess the surface of modern oil paints particularly related to phenomena of water-sensitivity. To this end, the impact of a range of external factors was studied that will impact the curing and ageing of oil paints on linseed oil paint formulations containing different pigments and additives. The factors were elevated temperature in combination with low and high relative humidity, strong indoor daylight and light with a relatively high UV component, as well as gaseous sulphur dioxide. By exposing the forementioned paint formulations to these elevated environmental conditions, their visual properties and chemistry were expected to change significantly.

Several analytical techniques, and further empirical testing, were evaluated on their effectiveness and practicality in detecting the molecular changes in the curing and ageing process in relation to water sensitivity and other possible visual phenomena. Non-invasive methodology was employed that is already used, for example within MOLAB, on painted objects in museum. The project aims to aid in interpretation of analysis result with these techniques.

II: Case study

Ten experimental paint formulations were produced, with all formulations using cold-pressed linseed oil (Kremer #73054) as the medium. Two distinct pigments were employed: synthetic ultramarine blue (Holiday pigments #33849) and yellow ochre (sourced from the RCE's reference collection). Ultramarine blue was selected due to its inherent hydrophilicity and its potential to promote the photo-catalytic degradation of the binding media, as observed by De la Rie et al. 2017. Another factor was its sulphur content, known to form magnesium sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) crystals, especially if magnesium carbonate is present in the composition of the paint, as noted by Harrison et al. 2021. In contrast, yellow ochre, although less reactive than ultramarine, might contribute to the degradation of the binding medium. To understand the influence of common additives in modern oil paints, two common extenders (magnesium carbonate hydroxide and calcium carbonate), a siccative/dryer (cobalt decanoate), and a dispersing agent (zinc stearate) were added, partly in combinations. Magnesium carbonate hydroxide can react with SO_2 , leading to water-soluble magnesium sulphate hexa- and heptahydrate, causing water-sensitivity in modern oil paints, as found by Silvester et al. 2013. Siccatives, specifically cobalt decanoate, enhance the drying of oil paint by inducing photopolymerization of linseed oil in sunlight without air. The reconstructions produced in the project provide insight in the role of siccatives in the water-sensitivity of oil paints. Paint formulations produced are specified in table 7.

Paint films were produced in a manner resembling traditional paint production. Dry ingredients were initially weighed and added to an automatic muller (from Old Holland).

Linseed oil was gradually mixed with these dry components until a consistent paste was formed, which was further ground using the muller. These films were uniformly spread on Melinex support with a thickness of 200 μm . The paints developed thin skins of paint medium, which was monitored in the ensuing ageing process. A transparent medium skin layer is often observed on the surface of modern oil paintings (Burnstock and Van den Berg 2014). These delicate surface skins usually consist of medium and exudates. They are one of the degradation issues which arise from the formation on, or migration of polar elements towards the painted surface. These polar element are for instance dicarboxylic and hydroxylated fatty acids deriving from in insufficiently matured polymeric networks” (Bonaduce et al. 2019). While this skin provides a protective barrier, it also introduces complexities in the paint's drying and ageing processes. In addition, the removal of the degraded skins of medium during cleaning can cause significant loss of surface gloss (Bonaduce et al. 2019).

Due to the specific acquisition requirements of Grazing-Angle reflectance FTIR analysis, a separate batch of extremely thin paint films was prepared on gold-coated substrates. It's worth noting that only formulations containing ultramarine blue were prepared for this technique.

	PIGMENT	%	BINDER	%	ADDITIVE 1	%	ADDITIVE 2	%
PAINT 1	Ultramarine blue	50.0	Cold-pressed linseed oil	50.0	-	-	-	-
PAINT 2	Ultramarine blue	33.3	Cold-pressed linseed oil	52.4	Calcium carbonate	14.3		
PAINT 3	Ultramarine blue	25.0	Cold-pressed linseed oil	49.5	Magnesium carbonate hydroxide	25.0	Cobalt decanoate	0.5
PAINT 4	Ultramarine blue	20.6	Cold-pressed linseed oil	50.0	Magnesium carbonate hydroxide	20.6	Zinc stearate	4.1
PAINT 5	Ultramarine blue	33.3	Cold-pressed linseed oil	52.4	Magnesium carbonate hydroxide	14.3	-	
PAINT 6	Ultramarine blue	50.0	Cold-pressed linseed oil	49.5	Cobalt decanoate	0.5	-	
PAINT 7	Yellow ochre	72.4	Cold-pressed linseed oil	27.6	-		-	
PAINT 8	Yellow ochre	36.3	Cold-pressed linseed oil	49.5	Magnesium carbonate hydroxide	15.5	Cobalt decanoate	0.5
PAINT 9	Yellow ochre	36.5	Cold-pressed linseed oil	47.8	Magnesium carbonate hydroxide	15.7	-	
PAINT 10	Yellow ochre	72.5	Cold-pressed linseed oil	27.0	Cobalt decanoate	0.5	-	

Table 7. Paint formulations used in the study (%wt.).

The ageing process was studied under five distinct artificial regimes:

- A dry environment with 10% relative humidity at 65 °C inside a climate chamber (artificial ageing regime 1);

- A high humidity setting close to 100% at 65 °C, achieved by placing paint-outs in sealed containers with a sodium chloride solution, within the same climate chamber (artificial ageing regime 2);
- Exposure to daylight using fluorescent tubes (artificial ageing regime 3);
- UV light exposure following a similar protocol as daylight exposure (artificial ageing regime 4);
- Incubation with gaseous SO₂ at elevated humidity levels (artificial ageing regime 5). This experiment was influenced by findings from Silvester et al. (2013). After observing significant changes in some paint-outs post 750 hours, this specific ageing process was terminated.

After paints were exposed to the different ageing regimes, significant optical changes could be clearly observed. Some of the most severe are showed below, as an example (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Paint formulations 4 and 5 unaged and after exposed to the different artificial ageing regimes.

Due to the fact that samples had to travel to the IPERION-HS partners to be analysed and all the ageing was to be done at the RCE (Amsterdam), different stages in ageing were created by cutting each paint-out in three different parts: one to be kept in laboratory conditions (control, Stage I), one that was removed from ageing after 750 hours (Stage II), and the last ageing for 1,500 hours (Stage III). This methodology proved to influence some of the results,

decreasing their reproducibility and possibility of accurately comparing, for example, differences in thickness of roughness due to ageing.

The structure of the research that preceded the protocol presented here is summarised in the chart below (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Structure of the research conducted.

III: Protocol

The assessment and monitoring of water sensitivity in modern oil paintings is a complex endeavour that requires a multifaceted approach. This protocol introduces a multi-modal methodology to identify and monitor changes in modern oil paintings that could result in water sensitivity. A set of non-invasive analytical tools was selected for their potential in assessing optical, topographical and chemical changes both on and below the surface, in paint samples that were artificially aged in a such a way that water-sensitivity was likely to have been promoted (Table 8). Additionally, swab rolling with water, a commonly used method for determining the water sensitivity of paint surfaces, was employed to assess the susceptibility of paint surfaces to water in a semi-standardized manner.

Technique	Information retrieved	Reference	Partner
Swab rolling with deionised water	Water sensitivity test	Mills et al. 2008 Tempest et al. 2013	RCE
Colorimetry	detect colour differences	Brokerhof et al. 2018 Cimino et al. 2022	RCE
Laser scanning micro profilometry	detect topographical changes (such as changes in the degree of roughness)	Dal Fovo et al. 2021	CNR-INO
Optical coherence tomography	detect tomographical changes, e.g., medium skins on the surface of the paint	Targowski et al. 2006 Szkulmowska et al. 2007	NCU
Spectral-Domain OCT	measure paint film thickness	Dal Fovo et al. 2023	CNR-INO
External reflection FTIR spectroscopy	identify chemical changes on the surface	Meilunas et al., 1990 Bonaduce et al. 2019	CNR-SCITEC
Grazing-Angle reflectance FTIR spectroscopy	identify chemical changes	Meilunas et al. 1990 Bonaduce et al. 2019	IPCHS

Table 8: Overview non-invasive analytical techniques and swab rolling with water.

Water sensitivity tests

Swab roll tests with deionised water are an example of a direct empirical method used to assess water sensitivity of paint surfaces. This semi-standardised method, used in previous studies (Mills et al. 2008; Tempest et al., 2013, p. 108), consists of swab rolling the paint surfaces using a deionised water, mimicking the procedure for surface cleaning used by conservators on unvarnished paint surfaces. After the cotton swab is dampened in deionised water, it is rolled on the paint surface with minimal mechanical pressure, until any pigment pick-up/paint removal is visible. The number of swab rolls until any pigment pick-up/paint removal is counted and the water sensitivity can be categorised, for example, as follows: **extremely sensitive**, pigment/paint removed within 5 swab rolls; **very sensitive**, paint removed within 6–15 swab rolls; **moderately sensitive**, paint removed within 16-30 swab rolls; slightly sensitive, paint removed within 31–50 swab rolls; **not sensitive**, paint not removed or removed after more than 50 swab rolls. Swab roll tests are generally performed

twice or three times on each paint, and the evaluation of sensitivity is based on the average number of swabs rolls.

In this study, the highest degree of water sensitivity seemed to relate to artificial ageing regimes 5, 2 and 4, with 5 showing the highest water sensitivity of all (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Percentage of paint formulations exposed to artificial ageing regimes 5, 2 and 4 (respectively) showing different degrees of water sensitivity.

While this method is not non-invasive, as pigment pick-up is generally observed, it was employed to determine water-sensitive paints and correlate with findings from various analytical techniques.

Colorimetry

Colour measurements are performed using a spectrophotometer set to give results in CIELAB1976 colour space. Colorimetric coordinates recorded provide a quantitative evaluation of colour change, expressed in the L*a*b* coordinates and ΔE parameter between control samples and those of the same composition after subjected to 1500h of each artificial ageing regime. Measurements were taken on each paint sample by using a mask, developed for this purpose to ensure repeated readings at the same spot, designed with three areas. Thus, the colour coordinates of each paint sample corresponded to the mean value of five measurements. The mask was also used for repositioning the instrument on the same areas.

Colour measurements were found to provide valuable insights into both water-sensitivity and the development of medium skins. Although with some exceptions, most paints showing the highest degree of colour change were also the ones showing the highest degree of water-sensitivity. This was, however, dependent on the paint composition and the artificial ageing regime to which the paint had been subjected to. For example, paints subjected to artificial ageing regime 2 (high temperature combined with high relative humidity) showed the highest relative degree of colour change (ΔE^*) and the highest relative degree of water-sensitivity. On the opposite side, ageing regime 3 (exposure to strong daylight), lead to both the lowest degree of water-sensitivity and colour change.

With artificial ageing regime 5 (SO₂ incubation), however, this link between water-

sensitivity and colour change was not as clear, as most paints became extremely water-sensitive, but the relative degree of colour change was much lower than, for example, that of the paints subjected to artificial ageing regimes 2 or even 1 (Figure 24).

Figure 24. ΔE^* values of all paint formulations after exposure to the five different artificial ageing regimes.

Colorimetry proved to give strong indications regarding the presence of a skin of medium on the paint surfaces. A decrease in the ΔL^* value (paints becoming darker) and an increase in the Δb^* value (samples becoming more yellow, in the case of the ultramarine blue paints) were observed in most paints developing a skin of medium.

Optical Coherence Tomography and the formation of skins of medium

OCT permits localization of all the discontinuities and other rapid changes of the refractive index of the tested medium. The results are usually presented as cross-sectional views.

For the present study and protocol, OCT was explored in its possibilities of detecting transparent or semi-transparent layers of skins of medium of the surface of paints, as well as of measuring their thickness and degree of transparency.

The OCT setup tested proved to be capable of detecting skins of medium spread across the paint surfaces and those confined to smaller areas of the surface. In both situations, the thickness was successfully measured, with the thinnest layer detected measuring $5 \mu\text{m}$, which is the thinnest that can be detected with this set-up, and the thickest measuring $38 \mu\text{m}$. Most of the skins of medium spread across the paint surfaces were heterogeneous in their thickness, with differences in the degree of over $10 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 25 shows an example of an OCT tomogram of paint 6 after exposure to artificial ageing regime 5, showing a moderately scattering skin of medium with a thickness between 23 and $25 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 25. OCT tomogram (corrected for refraction) of paint 6 after exposure to artificial ageing regime 5.

In this study, the presence of a skin of medium seemed to relate to a lower degree of water-sensitivity. Although with a few exceptions, on paints categorised as “extremely water-sensitive” (pigment pickup visible within 5 swab rolls) no skin of medium was detected, or only thin, local layers. For example, after artificial ageing regime 2 (high relative humidity, high temperature), which lead to the highest degree of water-sensitivity, with all but one paint formulation becoming extremely water-sensitive, only on one paint was a skin of medium detected. That paint was paint 6, which developed a skin of medium after all artificial ageing regimes, independently of the degree of water-sensitivity.

In conclusion, while being indicated by both colourimetry and OCT, the presence of water sensitivity has to be confirmed with direct swab rolling tests.

Another factor that seems to relate to the presence of skins of medium on painted surfaces is gloss change. Gloss change was observed by eye after swabbing with deionised water and the trend showed it was more severe on paints exposed to artificial ageing regime 2, but also on paints containing thin skins of medium. In general, on paints where a thicker layer of skins of medium was detected, gloss change was less visible.

Layer thickness measurements with Spectral-Domain Optical Coherence Tomography (Sd-OCT)

Layer thickness measurements can be performed, for example, with spectral domain-OCT (Sd-OCT). From the 2D tomograms (XY slices) of each paint, thickness values can be obtained by measuring the geometrical distance, based on the signal intensity plotted as a function of depth (the two main peaks correspond to the air/paint and air/support interfaces), as the average over 5 axial measurements on the XZ slice.

Even though it was possible to measure the thickness of all samples before and after each artificial ageing regime, it was not possible to make a clear link between loss or gain of thickness and water-sensitivity or formation of skins of medium. The results were very scattered most likely due to the fact that the measurements were not done on the same sample area. Due to the experimental set up of the paint-outs, different samples areas of the artificially aged paints were measured with OCT. Even though the paint-outs were prepared

always using the same draw-down bar, it is very likely that small irregularities were present that could influence these results especially if the measurements were done on different areas (samples subjected to the different ageing regimes) of a paint-out.

One example of layer thickness measurement with Sd-OCT on unaged paint 8 can be found below (Figure 26).

Figure 26. OCT results on sample unaged 8: a) micrograph of the sample showing the position of the XZ section (red arrow); b) XZ section allowing for the visualization of the sample's stratigraphy; c) signal intensity plotted as a function of depth; the two main peaks correspond to the air/paint interface and the light blue line indicating the paint/plastic support interface.

Topography and surface roughness measurements with laser scanning micro profilometry

Laser scanning micro profilometry provides faithful, high-resolution topographic maps of the measured surface, which may be displayed either as a 3D model or an image. The latter can be further processed through the application of digital filters and rendering techniques to obtain the equivalent of raking light images, which allows enhancing micrometric details and improving their readability. In addition, roughness measurements can be performed to highlight changes due to the different ageing regimes and stages.

This technique proved very useful in characterising the topography of each paint sample prepared from a different paint formulation and subjected to a different ageing regime. However, at this stage, it did not give clear insight into the development of surface roughness either or not related to water-sensitivity or skins of medium.

Figure 27 shows two colour maps of paint samples with distinct topographies (due to the presence of different additives), showing the possibilities of laser scanning microprofilometry in clearly detecting topographical differences.

Figure 27. Color maps (a) and raking light images (b) of unaged paint samples 6 (1) and 8 (2).

For surface roughness measurements of each sample, roughness values (S_a and S_q) were calculated on an area of around 8 mm^2 (the size was selected depending on the signal to noise ratio, SNR, of the 3D maps). The roughness was computed on the conditioned surface (without any shape information) after removing the bad pixel from the colour map using a proper filter and after best plane subtraction. See Appendix 2.1.4 for further information and an example of the procedure is shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28. Microprofilometry results for sample unaged paint sample 10 (ochre paint): a) unconditioned color map with red square indicating the area ($251 \times 251 \text{ pix} = 1.2 \text{ mm}^2$) selected for roughness measurement; b) unconditioned surface; c) best plane; d) conditioned surface.

Grazing-angle Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (GA-FTIR) and External-Reflection FTIR (ER-FTIR)

Two different mid-FTIR techniques were evaluated on their suitability and effectiveness in identifying chemical changes in oil paints possibly linked to water sensitivity and colour change: External Reflection FTIR spectroscopy (ER-FTIR) and Grazing-angle Reflectance FTIR spectroscopy (GA-FTIR). These are both powerful tools in the realm of chemical analysis, particularly for materials like oil paints. However, they differ in their approach and sensitivity to surface phenomena and, especially, in their sample preparation requirements.

It has to be noted that the ER-FTIR technique is portable, non-invasive and is employed on a range of painting studies (Giorgi et al. 2019). GA-FTIR cannot be used on actual paintings since it requires extremely thin layers of material (between 2 and 5µm) to be applied on gold-coated substrates.

Rather, GA-FTIR is employed in this project to obtain more detailed mechanistic information on the paint surface in comparison with ER-FTIR.

Indeed, GA-FTIR proved, on some instances, to be slightly more sensitive to the detection of oxalates than ER-FTIR. Nevertheless, the outcomes were generally comparable. Both techniques proved to be effective in detecting the presence of free fatty acids, oxalates, and extra bands at 1734, 1716 cm⁻², likely related to the degradation of the oil. Spectral changes possibly due to chemical changes in the surface layer were also detected mainly with ER-FTIR.

Regarding water-sensitivity, some clear links were possible to be extrapolated:

- Presence of free-fatty acids in the FTIR spectra was in general linked to a higher degree of water-sensitivity. The intensity of the free fatty acid signals on ER-FTIR also suggested a connection with the degree of water-sensitivity: paints showing lower (or no) degrees of water-sensitivity showed only weak or no signals of free-fatty acids. The presence of free fatty acids may be due to a higher extent of hydrolysis, a higher content of dicarboxylic acids (from oxidation), or both (la Nasa. et al 2019), which play an important role in the development of water-sensitivity;
- Presence of oxalates in the FTIR spectra was also linked to a higher degree of water-sensitivity. All the paints categorised as “extremely water-sensitive” showed increased intensities of oxalate bands. The presence of metal oxalates can be indicative of oxidative degradation of the oil binder, possibly leading to water-sensitivity (la Nasa et al. 2019).

Other techniques

Non-invasive analytical techniques not included in this protocol for the assessment of sensitive paint surfaces, but which will be added to this in the future are: Multispectral Vis-Near Infrared Reflectography, Fibre optics reflectance spectroscopy and laser desorption mass spectrometry (LDMS).

IV: Protocol limitations and advances

Water-sensitivity in oil paints is a multifaceted issue, and it is important to highlight that the setup of the experiment show limitations.

A significant limitation obviously lies in the use of paint samples rather than painted objects of cultural heritage. While the samples used in this study have consistent and simplified formulations, actual historic artworks are far more complex. Therefore, while our tests on paint samples yield important insights, the results can be hard to apply directly to the complex nature of an artwork.

Additionally, the paints were not consistently examined on the exact same surface throughout the study after the ageing had been completed and only a limited number of analyses could be performed. This was because the paint preparations and ageing occurred in one institution, while the subsequent analyses were conducted in different institutions. Furthermore, not all methods produce equivalent levels of results for the model paints, as each technique produces different types of chemical or optical information. For example, while the optical techniques provide some indication for water sensitivity in paint systems, no definite conclusions can be drawn, and results need to be matched with other non-invasive techniques.

Water sensitivity testing using aqueous swabbing also presents certain limitations. Firstly, the method is somewhat subjective, influenced by the individual conducting the test. Variables such as the pressure applied during swabbing and the evaluation criteria can differ. While the tests in this study were consistently conducted by one person, the outcomes may not align with results from other artworks or paints. Engaging multiple testers could mitigate this subjectivity. The second issue is the potential for pigment removal or damage during swabbing, especially with water-sensitive paints. While our tests were on mock-ups, they might not be appropriate for genuine cultural heritage items. However, despite its simplicity—requiring just a solvent, like deionised water, and a cotton swab—this technique provides invaluable data on solvent sensitivity.

The performed analyses with colorimetry, OCT and FTIR showed a range of optical and chemical changes in the model paint systems after ageing. While surface morphology changes were not directly apparent, either visually, or with OCT and microprofilometry, the sensitivity of the paints increased especially under high relative humidity conditions (and SO₂). This was evidenced by the detection of increased amounts of oxalates as well as free fatty acids with GA-FTIR and ER-FTIR. With samples aged at low RH and at higher temperature, the sensitivity decreased after artificial aging of samples that showed some initial water sensitivity.

V: Perspective and future directions

Monitoring water sensitivity in modern oil paintings remains a complex task. The challenge lies in establishing a clear correlation between the data collected through various methods and the actual water sensitivity of the paints. Traditional methods like swab rolling tests with

deionized water or other solvents offer direct answers but come with limitations. While they require only a small test area, they are invasive and can cause visible gloss changes, making them unsuitable for certain artworks in museum or conservation settings.

To address these challenges, a multi-faceted monitoring system appears to be the most effective approach. This system would focus on both optical and chemical changes in the artwork. Colorimetry, for instance, is a valuable tool for tracking early signs of degradation or alterations that could lead to water sensitivity. Although it necessitates close contact with the artwork, it is non-invasive and well-suited for a museum environment.

ER-FTIR spectroscopy is another key technique that has shown promise in monitoring water sensitivity. Its advantages include portability, non-invasiveness, and the ability to identify the presence of free fatty acids and oxalates, which have been linked to water sensitivity. Given its availability and ease of use, ER-FTIR could become a standard tool for assessing the degradation of paints in a museum context.

OCT has also proven effective in detecting 'skins of medium' on paint surfaces, particularly those with a thickness of 5 μm or greater. The presence of these skins has been associated with water sensitivity, making OCT a valuable addition to the monitoring system.

While laser scanning microprofilometry did not yield significant insights in the current study, its potential should not be dismissed. Monitoring physical changes in paint layers could offer valuable clues about underlying chemical alterations.

Other techniques like multispectral imaging and FORS also deserve consideration. Multispectral Imaging can reveal surface changes that are invisible to the naked eye, while FORS can provide intricate details about the paint's composition and layer structure. Additionally, the future potential of mass spectrometry is worth exploring, as it could offer molecular-level insights into the paints, aiding in the prediction of their water sensitivity.

In summary, the successful monitoring of water sensitivity in modern oil paintings will require a multi-disciplinary and multi-analytical approach, making use of a range of non-invasive analytical techniques that are adaptable to a museum or conservation setting.

VI: Access offered

The techniques optical coherence tomography (OCT), ER-FTIR, microprofilometry are offered by MOLAB.

2.1.5 Monitoring of flaking and delaminating in modern paints

I: Concept

This protocol aims to describe the possibilities of detecting adhesion issues between paint layer and support in modern paintings. Delaminations may form in result of formation of metal soaps at the interface of paint layers. Another cause of paint delaminations, inherent to the modern creation process, might be linked to the use of ready-made painting supports, i.e. canvas with preapplied oil ground layer, which have become popular in Europe throughout the 19th c. and are commonly used since. The long time span between applying ground layer and paints (due to storing at art suppliers' and/or at the artists' studios) often resulted in insufficient physical and chemical bond between already dried ground and paint layers. Also the use of poor quality paints as well as employing unorthodox painting techniques has been observed to cause poor adhesion of paint layers.

II: Case study

A representative example for the group of delaminating paints is yellow ochre tempera paint on glass slides. Yellow ochre tempera mock-ups were aged under extreme condition to induce delamination phenomena. Two sets of samples on glass were created (set A and B), with different stages of formation of delaminations (by using additional curation, see below). The samples were prepared by the coordinator (NCU) and sent to the partners.

As a second part of research the delaminations were recreated on a typical painting support (canvas, set C) and sent to the partners. Independently, the partners were each working on their respective set of samples.

The recipe for sample creation:

- Set A: glass substrates: 78 x 60 x 3 mm³, ochre yellow (Fe₂O₃) tempera paint (Maimeri), paint thickness (wet): ca 200 µm, curation in 60 °C for 30 minutes further curation at room conditions (Figure 29a)
- Set B: glass substrates: 78 x 60 x 3 mm³, ochre yellow (Fe₂O₃) tempera paint (Maimeri), paint thickness (wet): ca 200 µm, curation in 60 °C for 30 minutes, further curation in 60 °C, 25% RH for 3 weeks (Figure 29b)
- Set C: cotton canvas, primed, on stretchers, ochre yellow (Fe₂O₃) tempera paint (Maimeri) on titanium white priming, curation in 60 °C for 30 minutes further curation at room conditions (Figure 29c)

The described above model samples recreate a situation where craquelure and voids between paint and support appear due to mechanical stress. Although delaminations may occur in easel paintings due to some other reasons (see par. I), their structure is similar. Therefore, the use of tempera paint in these mock-ups instead of more common oil or acrylic binding media may be justified.

Figure 29. (a) example of a sample from set A, (b) example of a sample from set B after additional curation, (c) example of a sample from set C.

III: Protocol

The proposed instrumental imaging techniques to detect delaminations in easel paintings can be used independently of one another and the results are qualitative. The advantage of using imaging techniques in comparison to point-wise analyses is the possibility to examine a larger area of the object. This results in the increased representativeness of the obtained results. The results are also easier in interpretation, since they may be directly compared to standard scattered and raking light photographs of the analysed object. In this study the following techniques were used: Digital Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DSPI) (Lasyk et al., 2011), 3D confocal X-Ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (3D confocal XRF) (<https://www.e-rihs.it/en/xrf-confocal-mapping/>), laser scanning microprofilometry (Dal Fovo et al., 2021), Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) (www.oct4art.eu, Targowski et al., 2020).

Digital Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DSPI)

The contactless and portable digital speckle pattern interferometry (DSPI) applied by IKiFP PAN offers sub-wavelength sensitivity in displacement measurements. The glass plate with the delaminated paint cured at room conditions (set A) is mounted in stable clamps on the optical table at room conditions (room temperature 22° C, relative humidity (RH) 58%). For the DSPI, two methods of generation of surface displacement generation are proposed to be used: thermally induced deformation and sound-induced vibration.

Thermally induced DSPI

In the first method, the surface of the sample is heated up by an infrared lamp for up to three seconds. During that time the surface temperature increases by 1-2 ° C on average.

As delaminated areas contain air voids between paint and the support, the transport

of heat is less efficient. That leads to the slower cooling of the surface than well-attached paint after switching off the infrared lamp. Therefore, the temperature difference results in larger deformation of the delaminated than those of fully attached paint during cooling. In result, the concentration of the interference fringes is observed in delaminated areas and coded with false colour.

The size of the visualized area is 5.2 cm x 4 cm. The black mask is applied to the areas where paint is lost. The color marks identified delamination.

Exemplary result:

Figure 30. Sample on glass support. (A) a thermally induced interferogram with black mask applied to the areas where paint is lost, red areas highlight identified delamination; (B) The result of the analysis of the thermally induced interferograms with a black mask applied to the areas where paint is lost, red areas highlight identified delamination.

Sound induced DSPI

The sample is exposed to a mono frequency sound from a loudspeaker. Sound frequency is changing from 2250 Hz up to 4900 Hz. Sound pressure level near the sample is 105 dBA.

Sound pressure induces vibrations in the sample. Delaminated areas contain air voids between paint and the support, each delaminated area has its own eigenfrequency depending on the size and geometry of the delaminated area. Frequency of vibrations induced in each delaminated area depends on its eigenfrequency and frequency of the sound. Sound frequency should be such that the frequency of vibrations induced in delaminated areas doesn't match the frequency of vibrations induced in the whole sample. The concentration of the interference fringes is observed in delaminated areas and coded with false colour.

Exemplary result:

A

B

Figure 31. Sample on glass support. (A) A sound-induced interferogram; the black mask was applied to the areas where paint is lost; red areas highlight identified delamination. (B) The result of the analysis of the sound-induced interferograms; a black mask was applied to the areas where paint is lost; red areas highlight identified delamination.

DSPI - conclusions

Two interferometric techniques allow the mapping of delaminated areas that complement each other. A comparison of the delamination maps obtained with the two methods is shown in Fig. 3. As one can see, the sound-induced method detected significantly more delaminations than the thermal method. This is a surprising result as the authors' (Lasyk et al., 2011) previous experience with mapping of delaminations didn't show such a substantial difference. The authors interpret it as the influence of a very high density of delaminations compared to typical paintings or decorated wood.

Figure 32. Sample on glass support. Comparison of the delamination maps obtained using the sound-induced vibrations (red color) and thermal deformations (blue color). Their overlap is represented by the pink color.

3D confocal X-Ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (3D confocal XRF)

The 3D confocal XRF (developed within the XRAYLab, ISPC-CNR, Catania, Italy) is a powerful method for stratigraphic investigations (1D) and elemental imaging in three dimensions (3D) of samples with complex depth profiles. The CXRF method is non-destructive, requires no sample preparation and can be performed in-situ. CXRF is particularly suited for the investigation of layered paints in paintings. Measurement time is about 1000 seconds for 1D measurements, hours for 3D mapping. Spatial resolution is ca 3 μm .

Sample set A and C were subjected to the 3D confocal XRF. The measurement parameters for sample on glass support (sample set A) are:

- Source 50 kV & 600 mA
- Scanning step XY: 250 μm
- Scanning step Z: 10 μm
- Dwell-time per pixel: 100 ms
- Scanning area: 48 mm x 51 mm x 200 μm
- GPU Rendering of 3 models (cubic)

The structural changes within the delaminated paint mockup are visualized as 3D models.

Exemplary result:

Figure 33. Sample on glass support (sample set A). From left: Fe map (XY view), Fe models (Z scaling applied to evidence intra layer structure).

The measurement parameters for sample on canvas support (sample set C) are:

High resolution 3D confocal XRF

- Source 50 kV & 600 mA
- Scanning step XY: 50 mm
- Scanning step Z: 3 mm
- Dwell-time per pixel: 500 ms
- Scanning area: 5 mm x 5 mm x 200 mm
- GPU Rendering of 3 models (cubic)

Exemplary result:

Figure 34. Sample on canvas support (sample set C). From left: Fe map, Fe model rotation (still image from 3D animation, Z scaling applied to evidence intra layer structure).

Laser scanning microprofilometry

The laser scanning microprofilometer developed at CNR-INO comprises a commercial conoprobe (Optimet, Conoprobe 1000), which is moved by a scanning device allowing for measurements on a maximum area of 30 x 30 cm². The profilometer has 1 µm axial resolution, 20 µm lateral resolution, and an 8 mm dynamic range, when equipped with a 50 mm objective. It provides faithful, high-resolution topographic maps of the measured surface, which may be displayed either as a 3D model or as an image. The latter may be further processed through the application of digital filters and rendering techniques to enhance micrometric details and improve their readability.

All samples were measured with a 20 µm spatial sampling in both scanning directions.

Exemplary results:

Figure 35 . Upper row, from left: sample on glass support (sample set A), visible light photography, topography map derived from profilometric data, simulation of raking light image derived from profilometric data. Middle row, from left: Sample on glass support (sample set B, after additional curation for 20 days in $T \approx 6$ °C), visible light photography, topography map derived from profilometric data, simulation of raking light image derived from profilometric data. Bottom row, from left: Sample on canvas support (sample set C), visible light photography, topography map derived from profilometric data, simulation of raking light image derived from profilometric data.

Roughness measurements may be performed as well by means of the laser scanning profilometry setup. For each area (1 cm², sampling step = 20 mm, 500 x 500 pixel), the plane best fitted to data is subtracted to obtain the conditioned surface (without any shape information). Two orthogonal profiles (along x and y directions) are then extracted on which the roughness (Sq) is calculated.

Results on area A1 are reported as an example:

Figure 36. Upper row, from left: sample on glass support (sample set B) before and after curing, topography maps derived from profilometric data with measurement area A1 marked with black square. Bottom row: area A1 after additional curing, topography map derived from profilometric data, surface profiles and roughness measurements before and after sample curing.

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT)

Two OCT setups are proposed:

1. Cross-sectional analysis is performed with a Thorlabs Telesto-II Spectral Domain OCT device, using a superluminescent diode (central wavelength: 1300 nm, bandwidth: about 100 nm) with axial resolution of 5.5 µm in air (ca 3 µm in painting media), and lateral resolution of 13 µm. The maximum field of view (FOV) is 10 x 10 mm², with 3.5 mm imaging depth. The detector consists of a spectrograph made of a diffraction grating and a fast camera. The system is controlled via a 64-bit software preinstalled on a high-performance computer. The 3D scanning path probe with integrated video camera performs high-speed imaging (76 kHz) for rapid volume acquisition and live display. The sample stage provides XY translation and rotation of the sample along

with axial travel of the probe. 3D OCT acquisitions are performed on the measurement area (6 x 7 mm) identified by the paper mask. Difference in both surface profile and inner structure of the sample may be assessed.

Exemplary results:

Figure 37. Sample on glass support (sample set B) before and after additional curing. Upper row, from left: microscopic images of the spot A1 (marked by red square) before and after curing. Bottom row, from left: tomocubes of the spot A1 (marked by red square) before and after curing.

2. Additional structural analysis of the paint delaminations by means of custom designed OCT instrument (built in NCU, PL) is proposed. A high resolution (2.2 μm axial resolution in paint media of refractive index $n_R = 1.5$ and 12 μm lateral resolution) Spectral Domain OCT instrument is used. The delaminated paint is analysed with broadband infrared radiation (750 - 960 nm) of power at the surface not exceeding 0.8 mW and fluence about 30 mJ/cm^2 .

Exemplary result:

Figure 38 Samples on glass support. Left: sample set A, right: sample set B after additional curation (6 °C, 25% RH for 3 weeks).

IV: Protocol limitations and advances

All the proposed techniques provide direct qualitative assessment of the presence and advancement of delaminations of paint layer to some extent, in a non-invasive and contactless way, and in a fairly short time.

In case of OCT technique the limitation of imaging delaminations through paint is in the absorption of near infrared radiation in the material. Delamination in the superficial layers which are semi-transparent to near IR can be visualized directly, whereas in the case of samples executed with ochre tempera the only possibility to detect flaking paint and delaminations was through the glass support.

V: Perspective on future directions

The primary challenge encountered in this project stemmed from the inability to collaborate on identical samples, as the delicate nature of the samples precluded the feasibility of a 'round-robin' examination approach among partners. The next step would be to perform comparative measurements with the same techniques and instruments gathered in the same location. The measurements could be conducted both on model samples and a chosen heritage painting with existing delamination issues caused by natural aging.

VI: Access offered

The techniques: Digital Speckle Pattern Interferometry, Laser Scanning Profilometry and Optical Coherence Tomography described are offered through the TNA Access (MOLAB) of the IPERION HS and through ERIHS infrastructure.

2.2 Topic 2: Monitoring of environmental indoor condition

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- 2.2.1 Preventive Conservation Toolkit
- 2.2.2 Interlaboratory comparison of Oddy Test
- 2.2.3 Particulate and Dust Pollution: chemical composition of airbornePARTICLES
- 2.2.4 Analytical strategies for the detection of organic compounds harmful to oil paintings

2.2.1 Preventive Conservation Toolkit

I: Concept

The purpose of the toolkit was to develop simple environmental monitoring techniques for the purpose of preventive conservation in collections. Ideally, such techniques would not require substantial investment in terms of time and expertise at the point of sampling, even if laboratory instruments are needed for later analysis.

The environmental parameters of choice were organic acids, specifically formic and acetic acid that are often considered as risks to collections either during storage or during display. This research project aimed to develop a sampling method similar to diffusion tubes, that could be deployed in any environment, e.g. a storage box, a display case or a repository, and that would subsequently be sent to laboratory for chromatographic analysis. Prior to the project, no such commercially accessible sampling device existed. The project validated samplers for SO₂ and NO₂, available at low cost from suppliers, for sampling of AcOH and MeOH, and tested them in non-laboratory environments. The final aim was to offer the method (involving the samplers and subsequent analysis) as an IPERION HS service. The service was requested in the frame of the PrevAlex PHS proposal and approved, meaning that it was already tested out.

II: Protocol

SKC UME_x 200 Passive samplers, originally intended for environmental monitoring of NO₂ and SO₂ in workplace atmosphere, consist of a polypropylene casing (i.e. a tag) covering two 2 cm × 2 cm reactive strips (or tapes), treated with triethanolamine. The sample strip is covered by a perforated diffusion barrier and the field blank is covered with a full polypropylene cover. The samplers are low cost and easy to use, and only require for the cover to be slid open before sampling begins.

During validation in the museum atmosphere, sampling was performed in duplicate and the relative standard deviation (%RSD) ranged 7.7–40% (average 23%) for AcOH and 1.5–50% (average 16%) for HCOOH.

The highest observed deviations in the case of samplers in the museum could also be a consequence of their horizontal orientation during sampling, which could lead to deposition of particulate matter with a high content of the investigated analyte or to changes in diffusion rates due to deposition of particulate matter on the diffusion barrier. The %RSD values obtained in our experiments are also comparable to the values obtained by similar means (duplicate measurements in object enclosure) with NILU samplers (21% for AcOH, 19% for HCOOH; www.nilu.com).

The presented sampling method is comparable to other methods in current use with respect to the sampling rates and limit of detections (LODs). The detection limits were determined as $2.1\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for AcOH and $1.9\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, which is suitable for monitoring of less polluted indoor environments. This was demonstrated in a case study at the National Museum of Slovenia, where low concentrations ($2\text{--}54\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) of both compounds were determined in a display case, a storage drawer and the museum spaces with these environments.

Figure 39. A typical exposure microenvironment with several sampling devices and a T/RH data logger. The SKC UMEEx 200 Passive samplers are the ones with green lids.

The analytical protocol consists of the next steps:

- Samplers (SKC UMEEx 200, SKC, UK) are exposed to the monitored environment for 7 days, the environmental conditions need to be reported
- Following sampling, the samplers are packaged in the original packaging, re-sealed and sent for analysis to the Heritage Science Lab Ljubljana at the University of Ljubljana.
- At the laboratory, the sampling strip is removed to a glass vial and ultrasonicated in 2 ml of ultrapure water (MQ; Millipore, USA) for 20 min.
- The extracts are filtered through $0.45\mu\text{m}$ filters (Chrom4, Germany) before injection into an ion chromatograph, Dionex ICS-5000 (Thermo, USA), consisting of a gradient pump, an electrochemical suppressor (Dionex AERS 500 4 mm, set to 56 mA) and a conductivity detector. A Dionex IonPac AS11-HC 4 mm analytical column (Thermo, USA) was used, with the mobile phase composed of MQ and 100 mM NaOH in MQ, 1.5 ml/min flow, $25\mu\text{l}$ sample injection volume. Each sample was injected in duplicate.

- The gradient of mobile phase composition (Phase A = MilliQ; Phase B = 100 mM NaOH in MQ):

□ Time (min)	6	13	16	17	19	21
% B	5	10	40	40	5	5
- The sampling rates were determined to be 16.7 ml/min for AcOH and 17.7 ml/min for HCOOH.
- The development was carried out in collaboration with the EU project APACHE (grant agreement project No 814496), which offered a suitable case study site and covered part of the material and personnel costs.

III: Protocol limitations and advances

Clearly, the developed method is suitable for monitoring where real-time analysis is not required, which is the majority of cases in heritage institutions. The technique compares well with other sampling techniques, e.g. solid-phase microextraction (SPME), however, small spaces with no air movement (e.g. boxes) could represent a challenge as the air could become depleted. Spaces with extreme air velocities, e.g. in repositories under vents could also represent a challenge.

However, it is believed that the sampling method, in conjunction with the subsequent analysis, covers the majority of needs for the determination of organic acids in indoor air in heritage institutions.

IV: Perspective on future directions

Environmental monitoring is often a complex task due to the number of variables of potential interest and numerous available techniques with diverse sensitivities, selectivities, sampling and other technical requirements. On the other hand, good quality environmental data is of fundamental importance for E-RIHS, which is why the RI should offer not just access to such techniques but also offer a decision support system for users, enabling informed selection of the optimal monitoring technique and its deployment, as well as data interpretation. The latter could be achieved through digital tools available through DIGILAB, however, further development of monitoring and sampling tools that can be deployed by non-experts is also essential.

The validated method of monitoring of organic acids utilises accessible, commercially available samplers. Analogous samplers are available for many indoor and outdoor pollutants, which is what could be described as the “Pollution monitoring kit” offered to E-RIHS users in the future.

V: Access offered

The technique is part of access offer by the FIXLAB Macromolecular Heritage Laboratory in Ljubljana, Slovenia.

2.2.2 Interlaboratory comparison of Oddy Test

I: Concept

The Oddy Test (OT) is an accelerated corrosion test developed in the early 1970's at the British Museum to identify materials that are potentially dangerous for the conservation of heritage artefacts due to harmful volatile emissions. Lead, copper and silver stripes are exposed in a small test tube with the material to be tested, at 100% RH and 60 °C for 28 days. Despite its popularity, OT is not really standardized, and issues with its reproducibility are known. Different versions of the test are used by different museums and institutions across the world. The main objective of this work has been to carry out an interlaboratory comparison of the Oddy Test, to assess the reproducibility of the method and advance towards its standardization. Secondary objectives will be to compare different modifications of the protocol, and to propose more objective assessment methods.

II: Protocol

Eight IPERION HS partners have participated in the interlaboratory comparison: National Center for Metallurgical Research (CENIM-CSIC, leading the work), Spain; Institute of Cultural Heritage of Spain (IPCE), Spain; Rijksmuseum Amsterdam (RIJKS), The Netherlands; University of Ljubljana (UL), Slovenia; Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC), National Research Council (CNR), Italy; Institute for Sustainable Heritage, University College London (UCL), United Kingdom; Swedish National Heritage Board (RAA), Sweden; and National Centre for Research and Restoration in French Museums (C2RMF), France.

A bibliographic review and documentation sharing was carried out during summer 2021. After several online discussions, a meeting was carried out in September 2021 to plan the work and agree on a common protocol, namely the British Museum "3-in-1", specifically on points which show discrepancies in the literature. A document with a detailed protocol to be followed was prepared in October 2021. The key points of the agreed protocol were:

- *Glassware cleaning*: use manual or automatic dishwasher detergent. Avoid harsh chemical cleaning
- *Coupon preparation*: use sandpaper or micromesh pads for abrading the metal samples. Use P600 grit or equivalent micromesh pads. Cut samples at 35 x 10 mm.
- *Reaction vessel setup*: keep a constant water to air volume ratio of 1:100
- *Rating of materials*: rate materials as "suitable", "temporary" or "unsuitable" by each participant, following the guidelines in Thickett and Lee (2004), Figurres 4a-4c, page 14. The coupons would be sent back to CENIM for comparison.

It was also agreed that CENIM would prepare *identical samples of 10 materials*, delivered to the participants for testing. Figure 40 shows the image of the materials ready for dispatch. An additional set was delivered to RIJKS for a chromatographic analysis of the volatiles emitted by the materials.

Figure 40. Image of the 10 materials prepared for the Oddy Test.

Materials were delivered to the participating institutions in November 2021. During the first part of 2022, actual tests, visual evaluation of the coupons (according to the standard Oddy Test protocol) and delivery of metallic coupons back to CENIM were carried out (Figure 41).

Figure 41 . Setup for the OT used at CENIM (left) and coupons of copper, silver and lead after testing, ready for evaluation (right).

III: Protocol limitations and advances

Review of current practices of the OT have showed that, although some parameters have been widely adopted by heritage institutions (the 3-in-1 procedure, temperature at 60 °C and 2 g of material), others are not yet standardized. Discrepancies still exists in aspects such as the exact procedure for coupon preparation, glassware cleaning, reaction vessel volume and size and its relation with the amount of water added, preparation of the tested material, etc.

This is the first time, since the wide adoption of the 3-in-1 procedure, that an interlaboratory comparison of the OT has been carried out.

Despite the additional constraints imposed in the OT protocol for this interlaboratory comparison, detailed in section “II: Protocol” some reproducibility issues have been observed, leading to different rating of the same material by some participants. Some discrepancies between participating institutions were due to differences in evaluation criteria (the experience of the evaluator seems to be a relevant variable) and others to methodological differences in the experimental protocols, especially in the procedures for the preparation of the coupons.

As an outcome, some best practices can be recommended to improve the reproducibility of the Oddy Test. The collaborative work and international dimension of IPERION HS and the future E-RIHS ERIC set a privileged framework for advancement in its standardization.

IV: Perspective on future directions

Future activities should continue working in the standardization of the Oddy Test, both in the experimental setup and in the evaluation of the results. Further studies are required to understand the effect of some experimental parameters, such as the amount of water added to the vials, especially in relation with the effect of the hygroscopicity of the material. The effect of the surface finishing of the coupons, both in relation with the reactivity of the surface and with the confounding effect on the visual evaluation, needs to be investigated. The evaluation step stands as one of the main sources of uncertainty/discrepancies. This can be addressed through two different strategies: on one side, improving the visual examination (which is simple and affordable to everybody) by means of better references for comparison; on the other side, by means of quantitative instrumental techniques, such as electrochemical reduction. Finally, comparison of the analysis of volatile compounds from the materials with the results of the OT should be made to understand the potential corrosiveness (or lack thereof) of those volatile substances identified in those materials.

V: Access offered

Oddy test has not been offered as an access through IPERION HS, however it can be conducted using a protocol in a standard laboratory setting.

VI: Additional references

The manuscript, entitled "Review and interlaboratory comparison of the Oddy test methodology", by I. Díaz, A. Alvarez-Martin, S. Norrehed, B. Salvadori, I. Kraševac, D. Duran, J. Grau Bové and E. Cano, was submitted to *Heritage Science* in June 2023.

2.2.3 Particulate and Dust Pollution: chemical composition of airbornePARTICLES

I: Concept

The analysis of particulate matter (PM) in museums enables the identification of pollutants, comprehension of their sources, assessment of their impact on artworks, and the development of strategies to protect cultural artefacts (Chatoutsidou & Lazaridis, 2019, Camuffo et al., 1999). This project aimed to provide a concise overview of instrumental techniques accessible via IPERION HS that can be used to analyse chemical composition of collected airborne particles (PMs). Our objective was to propose an analytical scenario that conforms with current trends in analytical chemistry. This scenario comprises the registration of numerical data and gaining knowledge about the composition of the samples being studied. Quantitative analysis, as defined by IUPAC, involves determining and numerically expressing quantities or concentrations of analytes (“IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology”. 1997) -. Getting precise and accurate results in quantitative chemical analysis requires full understanding and consideration of all aspects of signal detection and quantitation. The calibration of analytical instruments is fundamental to achieve reliable results. This process requires choosing and using the relevant chemical standards for the given task. To achieve this goal, we selected a matrix-matched standard reference material (NIST SRM 1648a Urban Particulate Matter) to test alongside the samples.

II: Protocol

The chemical composition of particulate matter (PM) in museums can fluctuate considerably, depending on the location, exhibits, and environmental conditions. PMs in museums may contain microscopic fibers, dust, organic and inorganic particles, which can originate from various sources, including visitors, construction activities, and the artefacts themselves.

In certain cases, particulate matter (PM) found in museums may comprise of pollutants like heavy metals, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and acids. These pose risk to both museum objects and museum staff or visitors. It is therefore important to monitor and analyze the chemical properties of PMs in museums to comprehend and manage the potential hazards to the collection and ensure a safe and stable environment for preservation.

Instrumental methods offer great potential for the study of airborne particles (Wang et al., 1996, Ogrizek et al., 2022, Chiari et al., 2018, Marchetti et al., 2017, Kyropoulou, 2013, Godoi et al., 2006, Spolnik et al., 2004, Stefaniak et al., 2009, Gligorovski et al., 2008, Wagner et al., 2009, Belfiore et al., 2013, Chin et al., 1999). For a comprehensive understanding of the chemical composition of PM, a combination of methods including molecular and elemental identification would be ideal. Promising options suitable for the cultural heritage field include

application of XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence) (Wang et al., 1996, Ogrizek et al., 2022, Chiari et al., 2018) , SEM-EDS (Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy) (Kyropoulou, 2013, Stefaniak et al., 2009, Belfiore et al., 2013) or LA-ICP-MS (Laser Ablation Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry) (Gligorovski et al., 2008, Wagner et al., 2009, Belfiore et al., 2013, Chin et al., 1999) in combination with FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) (Belfiore et al., 2013), Raman spectroscopy (Godoi et al., 2006, Stefaniak et al., 2009) and GC-MS (Gas Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy) (Fermo, P., & Comite, V. (2022)). However, these methods have different limits of detection (LOD) and it is therefore necessary to carefully consider the feasibility of obtaining qualitative or quantitative sample data. To check the comparability of results obtained by different analytical techniques, it is advisable to test the reference material each time and to append the results obtained to the data recorded for the samples tested. It is important to note that the selected material (NIST SRM 1648a Urban Particulate Matter) expiration date is given in the certificate: 01 October 2027 (NIST Store Website, 2023). Therefore, it is necessary to change the standard reference material to the current one after this date. The proposed analytical approach here concerns investigating the chemical composition of samples that were previously collected on PTFE membrane filters; however, can be equally applied to any solid substrate (not specifically PTFE membrane filters) with collected airborne particles.

The Analytical Framework for Investigating Chemical Composition of Airborne Particles: A Step-by-Step Protocol:

1. Collected Sample Submission:

Airborne particle samples, obtained via air active filtration, should be carefully packed alongside sealed blank samples. These samples are then dispatched to a central laboratory, maintaining a controlled environment.

2. Precise Sample Preparation:

Upon arrival, the collected samples are meticulously sectioned into manageable pieces. This segmentation facilitates subsequent analytical processes while preserving constancy in the composition of the sub-samples. It is also possible to divide the filters at the collection point into an appropriate number of subsamples and distribute them directly to specific laboratories.

3. Protective Packaging:

The sub-samples (shielded by protective paper) are carefully placed within ziplock bags. This ensemble is further secured within a cushioned bubble envelope, ensuring protection during transport to collaborating laboratories.

4. Multi-Laboratory Distribution:

Packaged samples can be sent by post to various collaborating laboratories. By protecting the samples, it is possible to select even distant laboratories with suitable equipment for the determination of both inorganic and organic components of collected airborne particles.

5. Multi-analytical approach to investigation of PMs:

After distribution, samples can be examined simultaneously in different laboratories. Choosing different instrumental techniques can provide complementary information on a chemical composition of particulate matter samples. It is important that all analytical protocols include the use of relevant certified reference materials to ensure the traceability of reported results.

We have tested the use of: XRF, SEM-EDS, FTIR, Raman, GC-MS and LA-ICP-MS. Among these techniques the most promising was the combination of SEM-EDS, LA-ICP-MS and FTIR.

A workflow or figure to support the protocol:

A. Collection of samples on the PTFE filters - samples of paper filters with deposited particles from Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España (IPCE) were evaluated for their elemental composition. The air from the workshop at the IPCE was actively filtered through the filters allowing particulate matter to be deposited with forced ventilation. The samples were sent to the lab for sectioning and distribution between the participants of this task.

B. The filters were divided into sub-samples according to the number of techniques planned. The samples were partitioned like slicing a cake so that the cut triangular pieces covered the filter area from the centre towards the edge.

The same procedure was executed to blank (pure filters) samples accompanying the filters with collected PMs. It is important to note that due to the potential of contamination at the edges of samples cut in this manner, it is recommended to analyse the middle area at a certain distance from the edges of the samples.

C. The sub-samples shielded by protective paper were placed within ziplock bags, then secured within a cushioned bubble envelope and sent to laboratories offering selected instrumental techniques.

D. Analysis of chemical composition of the collected samples by means of XRF, SEM-EDS, LA-ICP-MS, FTIR, Raman, GC-MS should be accompanied with investigations of a matrix-matched standard reference material.

Here, the analysed samples contained: Standard Reference Material (NIST SRM 1648a, blank filters and the real samples collected on PTFE filters).

Data collection and processing

During the study, the analytical capabilities of the selected instrumental techniques were tested for the possibility of performing complementary studies on the same sample.

At the first step a literature review was carried out about theoretical evaluation of usefulness of variable instrumental techniques for particulate matter investigations. The techniques that were selected (XRF, SEM-EDS, LA-ICP-MS, FTIR, Raman, GC-MS) underwent evaluation for their practicality through the analysis of a matrix-matched standard reference material. The purchased material was divided and partly left as powder and partly prepared as pellets (powdered material was pressed under 7 N pressure for 10 min, without additional binder) before being distributed among the laboratories participating in the project. In the initial phase of the research, tests were conducted to achieve analytical outcomes that were as close as possible to the information provided in the standard reference material (SRM) certificate. As a reference material, NIST SRM 1648a was chosen for this task and was analysed in either powdered or palletised form.

On the basis of the NIST SRM 1648a results the use of XRF, SEM-EDS, LA-ICP-MS and FTIR was recommended:

- XRF allowed for a fast screening of elemental composition of the samples;
- SEM-EDS allowed for observations of morphology of collected particles and detection of main elemental composition;
- LA-ICP-MS allowed for determination of even trace elemental quantities;
- FTIR enabled the identification of the chemical compounds within the particles.

Outline the procedures for data collection and processing

Each sub-sample obtained for the overall investigations of collected PMs was individually analysed by means of one (or two) out of the selected instrumental techniques. NIST SRM 1648a and filter samples with airborne particles were analysed without additional preparation as received by the laboratory (unless otherwise stated).

Each sample was divided between 4 laboratories and the following techniques were used successively to examine the chemical composition of the same sample:

- 1st LAB: XRF & FTIR. Note, the order is critical since, while XRF is performed directly on the sample without any manipulation of it, the PTFE filter must be pre-treated with organic solvent to extract the particulate matter from the fibres for FTIR analysis.
- 2nd LAB: SEM-EDS & LA-ICP-MS & SEM-EDS (repeated for the same filters).

- 3rd LAB: Raman spectroscopy (only data for NIST SRM 1648a was reported, no information was obtained from filters due to analytes content below LOD).
- 4th LAB: GC-MS (only data for NIST SRM 1648a was reported, no information was obtained from filters due to analytes content below LOD).

The analysis with *portable XRF* does not suffer from the interference of the substrate when PTFE filters are used, therefore this technique is useful to detect elements in the particulate matter. A fast screening of the major elemental composition of the NIST SRM 1648a (pellet) and filters with collected airborne particles was undertaken. However, light elements are not detected (Na, Mg, Al). To increase sensitivity for light elements usually helium flux is used. The detection limits estimated from NIST SRM 1648a analysis were ca. 120 ppm but the LOD values depend on the element and can be estimated within the range from 0.01 to 0.1 wt.%

FTIR point analysis with ATR mode (flat diamond crystal only) detected gypsum, calcite, quartz, organic material on the NIST SRM 1648a powder, while for samples collected on PTFE membrane filters only the Teflon signal was recognized.

Spectra of the standard reference material have been recorded directly on the dust powder. To chemically characterise particulate matter on a PTFE filter a quarter of the filter was cut, and a modified version of the conventional particulate extraction procedure described in the literature was followed, including a quick rinse with a small quantity of organic solvent.

With FTIR imaging in micro-transmittance mode using KBr pellets, a pre-treatment with organic solvent was required for both dispersing NIST SRM 1648a particles and extracting particulate matter trapped in the porosity of the PTFE membrane filters. The filter was immersed in a vial containing 2-propanol, then left to soak for an hour. After this period, a few drops of the liquid phase were deposited onto a KBr pellet. We were able to view the particles removed from the filter and obtain a chemical distribution map in transmission mode (calcite, some unidentified organic matter and possibly a sulphate were detected). The smallest particles analysed were about 15 microns in size.

SEM-EDS

SEM-EDS allowed for collecting information about the elemental composition of PMs together with the elemental distribution maps. Unlike XRF described as a bulk PM elemental analysis method, SEM-EDS additionally enables micro-analytical investigations at the single particle level (not only elemental composition data, but also visualization of the surface of the investigated material, providing morphology data such as shape and size of each individual particle). In every investigated sample mostly spherical nanoparticles (ca. 50 nm diameter) forming bigger aggregates (few micrometers diameter) were observed.

Limits of detection: depends on the element, estimated based on investigation of NIST SRM 1648a at the level c.a. 0.05-0.1 wt.%

Element detection range: B-U

LA-ICP-MS

Information about the trace elemental composition of PMs together with the elemental distribution maps. The resolution of the obtained maps was at least two ranges lower than the resolution of SEM, but elemental information available for LA-ICP-MS measurements covers elements from Li to U and LA-ICP-MS can provide major and trace element compositions in a sample down to detection limits of 10's of parts-per-billion (ppb).

Micro-invasive measurements leave visible changes in the appearance of the analysed solid samples. However, the residues from line ablation can be strategically designed to preserve material between one ablation line and the next. Repeated SEM-EDS examination at the same spot revealed that the ablation did not alter the elemental composition of the particles trapped in the filter structure. Properties of the particles, like size and shape, also remained unaltered.

The combination of SEM-EDS and LA-ICP-MS seems to hold a lot of potential for in-depth morphological and elemental characterization of airborne particles trapped on filters.

Raman

The measurements taken were qualitative in nature. No information was obtained from filters due to analytes content below LOD. The LOD is related to concepts from quantitative analysis so the LOD is usually lower than the limit of quantification (i.e. the lowest concentration of a product in a specific matrix that can be quantitatively determined with sufficient precision, given specific experimental conditions). Experimental conditions should be defined, as the LOD is dependent of several factors, including, amongst others, the laser wavelength, instrumental properties (type of detector, optics, etc.), measurement time and number of accumulations. When a dispersive Raman spectrometer is used, the sensitivity is inversely proportional to the spectral resolution.

GC-MS

On the reference NIST SRM 1648a powder, the Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) were determined by GC-MS after extraction with Soxhlet in dichloromethane. Qualitative results were consistent with the reference data whereas, at the quantitative level, almost all the mass fraction values were lower than those reported in the Certificate of Analysis. So, no information was obtained from filters due to analytes content below LOD.

Timeline

Providing even a basic time estimate for conducting this research is quite challenging. Splitting samples and sending them to multiple laboratories that conduct tests in parallel using different techniques suggests that time can be saved. The combined data are complementary in their ability to evaluate the content of analytes at different concentration levels, with differing surface resolutions available to perform either morphological observations or studies of inorganic or organic constituents.

III: Protocol limitations and advances

When using PTFE membrane filters to collect PMs, particulate matter is trapped in the porosity of the substrate. This may favour the stability of the sample, avoiding its alteration during the transport (due to loss of particles). Nevertheless, the inclusion of particles in the filter prevents their composition from being characterized directly on the substrate, while direct analysis would be desirable to avoid contamination from the manipulation of the sample.

IV: Perspective on future directions

In order to successfully implement the proposed analytical protocol in a museum, several crucial steps need to be taken.

- Clear objectives and scope of analysis should be established in the beginning, outlining the types of PM components (organic or inorganic ones) to be monitored.
- Next, monitoring sites should be carefully selected throughout the museum. Finally, it is crucial to select the air samplers as well as to use standardised sampling protocols allowing for minimised contamination risks.
- Laboratory analysis should be conducted parallel with quality control measurements to ensure data reliability.
- Collected data should be analysed to identify any potential risks to artefacts, staff, or visitors. Maintain comprehensive documentation and regular reports to promote transparency of the undertaken activity.

In conclusion, it is vital to adopt a systematic approach in monitoring preventative conservation measures to safeguard museum artefacts and ensure a secure preservation environment. Collaboration with appropriate stakeholders can facilitate this process.

In our view, the creation of a comprehensive, long-term research plan that enables its successful implementation is crucial.

V: Access offered

The techniques XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence), SEM-EDS (Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy), ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry), FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) and Raman spectroscopy are offered by either the FIXLAB or the MOLAB.

VI: Additional references:

Manuscript:

“Exploring the chemical composition of airborne particulate samples in museums: An overview of analytical techniques for comprehensive investigations” written by Sofia Brizzi, Barbara Łydzba-Kopczyńska, Cristiano Riminesi, Barbara Salvadori, Tomasz Sawoszczuk, Marcin Strojecki, Olga Syta, Julio Torres, Aleksandra Towarek, Barbara Wagner

2.2.4 Analytical strategies for the detection of organic compounds harmful to oil paintings

I: Concept

In order to develop a suitable collection care strategy for oil paintings, a wide variety of materials that come into contact with them need to be evaluated to ensure that the compounds released by these materials will not cause any damage to the paintings. In this context, the increased accessibility and implementation of new mass spectrometry techniques in cultural institutions demonstrates an ongoing trend to improve upon the traditional strategies, such as Oddy test, Photographic Activity Test (ISO 18916), or microchemical testing, to evaluate materials by characterizing their composition at the molecular level.

By adapting the methodology that is present in conservation science labs, this project seeks to demonstrate the value of incorporating different mass spectrometry (MS) approaches for chemical fingerprint analysis of materials present in museum collections. The protocols optimized here can be integrated into the decision-making process when selecting materials that will be in contact with artwork.

II: Protocol

The main goals of the project are: i) to develop analytical strategies to evaluate the potential hazard of materials that come into contact with oil paintings (e.g. during conservation practice or in exhibition) and ii) to define criteria of analysis that allow to compare results generated by different laboratories and different mass spectrometry techniques. The results generated in this project will be compared to the outcome of Topic 2.2.2 (Interlaboratory comparison of Oddy Test).

The following analytical techniques have been optimized

- A. Headspace sampling tools coupled to Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (HS-GC-MS)
- B. Direct Analysis in Real Time-Mass Spectrometry (DART-MS).

A. Headspace analysis – Gas chromatography-Mass Spectrometry for material analysis and indoor monitoring

Non-invasive screening analysis of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in museum areas has the potential for rapid detection of marker compounds that can damage museum objects and paintings (Lattuati-Derieux et al., 2008; Álvarez-Martín et al., 2020). In this first work section, the protocol for sampling using a new commercialized headspace probe (high-capacity sorptive extraction technique, HiSorb), coupled with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), is explained in detail. The performance of this semi-automatic method was

compared with the complementary and well established sampling tool: solid phase microextraction (SPME).

The protocol described here has been optimized for both: (i) analyzing materials already present or in contact with oil paintings and (ii) sampling VOCs accumulated in museum areas.

A.1. Investigated samples

To optimize and validate the methodology, ten construction materials provided by Topic 2.2.2 (see description of the materials in section “Interlaboratory comparison of Oddy Test”) were used with this aim. In addition, four materials encountered in oil paintings were added in the study: (1) pure beeswax and (2) colophony purchased in Chemiefarma bv Maarsse (The Netherlands). (3) Wax-based material collected during the structural treatment in February 2022 from *The Night Watch*. (4) Lining canvas from an oil painting provided by the Rijksmuseum (SK-A-4140).

Finally, the non-invasive protocol optimized for this project was tested in the headspace of: (i) four exhibition cases at the Rijksmuseum, (ii) the back of the canvas of *The Night Watch* (Rembrandt van Rijn, 1642) and (iii) the glass chamber where the painting is nowadays located.

A.2. Sampling tools

HiSorb probes: H4-AXABC (DVB/CWR/PDMS, inert, short version) and H1-XXAAC (PDMS, stainless steel, standard length) were supplied by Markes International Ltd. SPME fibers: 57308 (PDMS, df 30 μm , needle size 24 ga) and 57328-U (DVB/CAR/PDMS, df 50/30 μm , needle size 24 ga) were supplied by Supelco-Sigma Aldrich. SPME fibers and HiSorb probes were conditioned before each experiment following the supplier's specifications. The conditioned fibers were sealed with a ThermoGreen[®] LB-2 pre-drilled septa with an extremely low leaching to avoid contamination. HiSorb probes were stored in inert-coated stainless-steel tube and sealed with a 1/4" cap.

A.3. Sampling conditions

A.3.1. Reference materials

200 mg of each material were placed in 10 mL headspace vials (Markes International Ltd). For headspace equilibration time, experiments with zero, 1 hour, 24 hours, 48 hours and 7 days were conducted at room temperature. Sampling times of 20 minutes, 1 hour and 24 hours at room temperature were tested (Figure 42).

Figure 42. Headspace sampling of oil paint reference materials using HiSorb probes.

A.3.2. Indoor monitoring: on-site sampling

The SPME fibers and HiSorb probes were taken into the museum in a sealed zip lock bag. The probes were gently placed on the bottom of the exhibition cases and on the back of the canvas, (Figure 43-42). Also, the visual disruption that the instruments could potentially cause in the exhibition cases was taken into account, for this the placement was carefully considered in advance. In every case, one SPME fiber and one HiSorb were exposed close to each other to have the most comparable measurement (Figure 43C).

After sampling, the sampling tools were collected, labelled, sealed and transferred back to the lab for analysis. The analysis took place on the same day that the sampling tools are taken from the museum in order to avoid the loss of analytes adsorbed in the probes.

Figure 43. On-site sampling. (A) Sampling preparation. (B) and (C) HiSorb and SPME probes inside the exhibition case.

Figure 44. On-site sampling. Back of the canvas of *The Night Watch* with (A) HiSorb probes and (B) SPME. Pictures (C) and (D) show the scale of the sampling tools and the possibility of continuing conservation treatments while the sampling is taking place.

A.4. Instrumental conditions

A.4.1. SPME injection

After sampling SPME fibers were inserted and exposed in the split/splitless (SSL) injector at a temperature of 250 °C for thermal desorption with a splitless time of 3 minutes.

A.4.2. HiSorb injection

After sampling HiSorb probes were placed in inert-coated stainless-steel tube and sealed with a 1/4" cap. HiSorb extraction was automated in a Centri Autosampler (Markes International Ltd, UK). The HiSorb probes were conditioned as suggested by the manufacturer prior to the first use. The probes were then thermally desorbed at 250 °C for 10 min in splitless mode. The trap (UT12ME-2S, Markes International, general purpose in the C4 - C32 volatile range) was cooled at 10 °C during desorption of the probe in the injector, then 1 min purge at 20 mL/min was performed before heating the trap to 300 °C. A 10 split was applied after the trap to facilitate the transfer of the analytes into the head of the GC column. Before starting any sample batch, a blank was performed, and was also performed periodically to ensure the absence of carryover between runs.

A.4.3. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

A Thermo Scientific Trace 1310 Gas Chromatograph coupled to a Thermo Scientific ISQ LT Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer was used for the GC-MS analysis (Thermo Fisher

Scientific, USA). The GC separation was achieved using a Supelco SLB5 MS (20 m × 0.18 mm × 0.18 m) capillary column and a constant flow of 1 mL/min helium carrier gas was applied. The initial oven temperature of 40 °C was held for 5 minutes and a ramp rate of 5 °C/min was applied to increase the temperature from 40 °C to 250 °C, when the final temperature of 250 °C was held for 10 minutes. Data analysis was performed Xcalibur software (Thermo Fisher Scientific USA) and the NIST library 2011 Mass spectra Library V.2.0. was accessed to qualitatively identify the chromatographic peaks.

B. Direct Analysis in Real Time - Mass Spectrometry (DART-MS) for material analysis

DART-MS provides qualitative information about chemical composition (Cody et al., 2005). However, the observed mass spectra are dependent on sampling conditions, in particular the DART gas temperature. This report describes two DART configurations for material characterization.

B.1. Investigated samples

Ten construction materials provided by Topic 2.2.2 (see description of the materials in section “Interlaboratory comparison of Oddy Test”) were used to optimize the methodology.

B.2. DART-MS

A DART-100 probe operated by an SVP controller (IonSense, Saugus, MA) was operated in transmission mode in front of an Orbitrap Elite mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) fitted with a differentially-pumped Vapor interface. The DART probe was custom-mounted from above with multi-dimensional translation stages in front of the mass spectrometer (Figure 45). A 40 mm stainless steel transfer tube was used in place of the typical ceramic transfer tube on the Vapor interface. The DART helium was set to 300 or 400 °C. Material sections were mounted in forceps on translations and maneuvered between the DART probe and transfer tube for tens of seconds. MS data was acquired at 120k resolving power with a maximum ion trap fill time of 100 ms.

The DART probe was operated in positive mode and negative mode while the Orbitrap was scanned in positive and negative polarity, respectively.

Figure 45. (A) DART-MS set-up. (B) the sample is placed between the DART source and the transfer tube on a sliding platform.

B.3. Py-DART-MS

Samples (a few mg) were loaded into a quartz sample tube set in the coil of a Pyroprobe 1000 (CDS Analytical Inc., Oxford, PA). The pyrolysis assembly was mounted adjacent to the post-plasma jet floe between the DART and transfer tube (Figure 46). Samples were pyrolyzed by flashing the quartz tube to 650 °C for 1 s, and the vaporized sample was ionized in the DART stream.

Figure 46. (A) Py-DART-MS set-up. (B) the pyrolysis assembly is mounted adjacent to the post-plasma jet floe between the DART and transfer tube.

III: Protocol limitations and advances

Practical considerations to take into account during headspace sampling:

1. As SPME, HiSorb can be used in headspace mode, for both liquid and solid samples, or immersive sampling of liquids. The sampling consists of exposing the probe to the sample matrix or to the headspace of the sample for a set amount of time. At the moment that the probe is exposed the transport of analytes from the sample to the phase will start to take place immediately. Ideally, analyte extraction should occur under equilibrium between the matrix and the extraction phase. In our case, when dealing with big sample volumes (exhibition cases or museum galleries) and in which the air circulation cannot be controlled, the situation of equilibrium is not feasible, making quantification difficult. However, the control of the extraction conditions (e.g., temperature and humidity) and extraction time allows to assure semi-quantitative and reproducible results.
2. Regarding the sampling time required for headspace, the analyst should test different times in order to find a compromise between the volatiles adsorbed in the sampling tools (Figure 47A).
3. If the main goal of the analysis is to perform a non-targeted screening of the volatiles emitted or accumulated, we advise using several types of coatings to cover a large range of analytes. As it can be observed in Figure 47B, HiSorb has higher affinity for long chain fatty acids, terpenes and amines while SPME present higher affinity for long chain fatty acids.
4. After sampling, HiSorb probes are placed in empty thermal desorption tubes for further separation and detection by GC-MS. In the same manner, SPME fibers should be closed with an inert material to avoid contamination until analysis. The sampling tools can be kept at room temperature if the analysis takes place immediately after finishing the sampling. However, if the analysis cannot take place in a few hours after the sampling, it is recommended to keep the sampling tools at 4 °C.
5. Further developments in headspace sampling technology include ongoing efforts in the miniaturization of sampling devices making them less visible when they have to be placed in exhibition areas. In addition, no solvent is required during the extraction and injection of the analytes.

These characteristics make headspace a great candidate as screening sampling tool for oil paintings, where the analysis is not destructive.

Figure 47. (A) Total ion chromatogram of the HiSorb-DVB at sampling time 6 days (top-blue) and 24 hours (bottom-green). (B) Heat map of significant compounds extracted via HiSorb or SPME from *The Night Watch*.

Practical considerations for DART-MS:

- Without chromatography, low-abundance analytes among a great variety of background species may be detected by the instrumentation but overlooked by the analyst unless the ion of interest is known in advance or can be found by combing through spectra. Competitive ionization from compounds in very high abundance may decrease the detection efficiency of analytes of interest at low abundance.
- Large, intact samples surfaces can be analyzed with DART in reflection mode but require special considerations or modifications (Cleland et al., 2019).
- As an ionization method for mass spectrometry, a small amount of material is unavoidably consumed. The high-temperature gas may cause melting, discoloration, or scorching of a sample surface in a conventional experiment, but the degree of destructiveness may be limited or practically non-existent depending on the design of experiment and preparation/ingenuity of the analyst. The exact temperature of the post-plasma gas flow that interacts with the sample material must be measured by the user, as the DART control software only sets the probe internal temperature which is significantly higher (Newsome et al., 2018).
- Signal from an expected analyte that is not detected is often improved by increasing the temperature setting.
- Signal from exposing sample material to the DART gas may be fleeting (<1 s), stable and directly responsive to sample positioning, or tenacious and prone to carry-over

after the sample is removed, depending on the analyte. Some background signal should be collected before exposing sample material for direct comparison.

- The gap between the DART probe and transfer tube in conventional transmission geometry is 1-2 cm wide. Material to be analyzed must be small enough to fit in the gap. The material cannot be so wide as to obscure the inlet completely, and material desorbed from the sample edges is most easily observed.
- The ionization pattern from ambient methods like DART may be affected by changes in laboratory humidity or airborne contaminants like floor cleaners, laboratory chemicals, and personal products (Newsome et al., 2016).

IV: Perspectives on future directions

One of the main goals of the methodologies optimized in this project is to support implementation of Green Chemistry principles in analytical practice. This translates not only to efforts toward the elimination/reduction of organic solvents but also to the on-site implementation of integrated sampling/sample preparation approaches that afford reductions in the consumption of energy and to the overall cost of analysis, in addition to providing rapid information for decision making.

2.3 Topic 3: Digital platform with preventive conservation with decision supportive tools

Table of contents for Topic 3

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2.3.1 Overview of the developed tools

The development of various digital apps grounded in scientific research in the field of heritage science holds a great potential as a toolkit for conservators and curators, or professionals engaged in Collections Management. These applications mostly rely on damage functions, which model the individual or synergistic over time impacts of diverse environmental physical parameters, identified as “Agents of deterioration”, to the physical, chemical or mechanical materials’ properties.

Such apps are designed as assisting tools, intended to support the conservators and museum experts in quantifying or visualizing in a direct manner the projected damage to specific constituent materials or types of heritage objects within a given environment. Their primary purpose lies in facilitating a direct assessment of the anticipated harm. In such manner, they empower professionals to making decisions and proactively undertake necessary measures such as adjusting indoor environmental conditions to prevent or slow-down/decelerate the expected degradation as predicted through the proposed calculations.

The utilization of digital applications has experienced significant progress, thanks to the systematic efforts and ongoing advancements directed by leading institutions in the field of Preventive Conservation.

Several factors currently promote the use and increased the requests of Digital Applications for supporting Decision making and risk assessment approaches:

- Due to the asserted, universally upheld responsibility for Earth’s climate change, and its impact, direct or indirect on all types of cultural heritage, concern and care actions have been upscaled and extended globally. Simultaneously, museums, galleries, and historic houses have embarked on a journey towards increased sustainability recognizing their proper role in addressing climate change concerns. Risk management approaches have been increasingly adopted by the conservation departments of Museums and Collections as part of their collection care policies which, are outlined also upon sustainability principles, encompassing environmental and economic factors. Nonetheless, while smaller museums and collections draw from a wealth of established knowledge, it has become evident that guidelines for safe environmental conditions cannot be universally applied without being tailored to the local climate and to the specific practical collection care needs.
- On the other hand, Museums policies are modernised tending towards openness, extroversion and active public engagement, necessitating strategic outreach endeavors. This mentality acknowledges that the preservation of objects and facilitating or promoting access to them need not be conflicting objectives. Instead, it underscores the significance of public engagement with collections as a

means of underlining their enduring value. Today, visitors are welcome to participate and co-create meaning and value to the heritage objects.

Therefore, restructured/ revised Collection Management policies rely on a comprehensive grasp of the interplay among three equally crucial pillars: preservation, access, and sustainability. In this evolving landscape, the added value and prospective utility of digital tools that aid in risk assessment and environmental monitoring can greatly facilitate challenging decision-making processes inherent in the exhibition planning and the overall management of museum Collections.

Developments in the framework of IPERION HS Project

In IPERION HS Task, aim was to further develop, upgrade and make openly accessible to the E-RIHS Community a toolkit assembling several apps, that are addressing the actual stakeholders' needs in Collections Care.

The digital apps developed or upgraded in IPERION HS project are presented in a single web Site, the E-RIHS - Digital Tools, Services and Resources, <https://e-rihs.io/resources.html>, planned to be merged in E-RIHS - ERIC DIGILAB open services, and all apps have been documented with the same system of core descriptors / metadata.

A list of quality criteria has been defined and elaborated, including with equal importance attention to the solid scientific basis, clear and complete documentation, as well as ease to use.

In parallel, networking activities and two workshops have been organized, to survey stakeholders' needs. Both workshops were online, the first one was held on 24 March 2022 organized by Smithsonian and the second workshop was 15-19 May 2023 organized by Rijksmuseum. The second workshop included hands-on sessions, to get users direct feedback, and test whether these tools outreach the Community engaged in Collections Management.

Apart from valuable outcomes that have been recorded by the apps' developers to be taken into consideration for upgrading the apps, as part of a quality assessment approach a list of general requirements has been formed enumerating the features that an ideal app should include, regarding the User Interface and the Content of the app, without overlooking the importance of tutorials and examples on how to use.

2.3.2 HERIe – a digital preventive conservation platform

Service description

A rational strategy for controlling microclimatic conditions in museums, libraries or archives requires an understanding of the relationship between the magnitude of a threat and the damage caused. In order to support the international community of museum and conservation professionals in assessing the safety of display and storage conditions for collections, a digital preventive conservation platform HERIe providing remote access to quantitative assessment of risks to heritage assets has been developed to support conservation decisions. The platform is organised in the framework of ten independent modules corresponding to ten agents of deterioration following a structure proposed by the Canadian Conservation Institute.

The platform contains modules corresponding to the environmental agents of deterioration:

- **Contaminants.** The IMPACT was developed within the European Commission funded project of the same name. The model predicts indoor concentrations of pollutants. The main output is the Indoor/Outdoor ratio (%), which is the percentage of outdoor pollutant concentrations that we can expect indoors. To find this value, the model estimates the deposition flux of pollutants to surfaces. The deposition flux depends on the type of surface, its area, and the air movement in the room. It also depends on a value known as deposition velocity, which has been experimentally determined for a diversity of common indoor surfaces. This app is also separately described below, as it received an updated interface and functionality during this project.

The model shows the indoor concentration at equilibrium. This means that, in a room with no deposition, the internal concentration will eventually be equal to the external, even if it takes a very long time.

- **Light.** Within the module, there are two tools. One is based on the extrapolation of one-point measurement for several most relevant historical colorants and the second is on multipoint measurements obtained for 108 dyes used by the textile industry. The light damage calculator provides an estimate of the fading of colors exposed to light, based on the best available data. Despite these uncertainties, the calculator can show the wide sensitivity range of colored objects and the influence of exhibitions on the future appearance of collections. Original and faded colors are presented as patches on the computer screen. Since some computer screens and many computer projectors, do not distinguish small changes in color, the height of the faded color patch also changes in proportion to the amount of fading.

- Incorrect temperature. Generally, the tool allows to estimate degradation of chemically unstable heritage materials that leads to loss of mechanical strength and aesthetic quality of objects, diminishing their value – functional, aesthetic or social. When the degradation becomes unacceptable, objects are considered unfit for handling or display and therefore irreversibly damaged. The module uses expected lifetime, that is to say, time until an object is expected to undergo unacceptable change, as a quantitative measure of climate-induced chemical damage risk to the object. Two fundamental characteristics of indoor climate – temperature and relative humidity (RH) – are linked in the formulae for the rate of chemical degradation of materials which allow the expected lifetime of objects in a particular indoor climate to be predicted. Most storage or display spaces have varying climates; therefore, instantaneous expected lifetime values are calculated for consecutive single readings of temperature and RH uploaded by the user and then, the time-averaged ‘long-term’ expected lifetime is calculated for the time interval analysed.

As users are usually interested in the relative change in risk for various events or adjustments of temperature and relative humidity, the module calculates also the relative expected lifetime that is to say the ratio of the expected lifetime in the microclimate conditions provided by the user to the expected lifetime at stable room conditions (20°C, 50% RH).

Three currently available equations can be used by the user to calculate the expected lifetime and the relative expected lifetime for a range of low stability materials: the equation by Strlič et al. applicable to wood pulp-based papers post-1850; the Preservation Index derived by the Image Permanence Institute from the study of chemical degradation of cellulose acetate, a polymer which is the base for most film materials; Michalski’s equation, derived from a review of data on paper, film and dyes, considered applicable to a general category of low stability organic materials – the equation provides only for the relative expected lifetime.

- Incorrect relative humidity. Within the module, the tools allow for the estimation of the:
 - mechanical damage due to environmental variations. The mechanical damage tool is a software transforming climate versus time histories into dimensional change (strain) histories for a quantitative assessment of the climate-induced risk of physical damage for three categories of vulnerable heritage objects - restrained wood, panel paintings, and parchment. Risks from environmental conditions are assessed by analysing data uploaded by the user prevailing in a space in which an object is displayed or stored. The

- effect of moving an object from one environment to another, a frequent problem when loans for exhibitions are made, can be also assessed.
- chemical degradation similar to the incorrect temperature
 - Fire risk. Experiences of museums, libraries and archives - which carried out a risk assessment indicate that fires, despite significant technical progress in the field of fire protection, is among the greatest risks to long-term preservation of collections. Managers responsible for the preservation of collections should also take into account the fact that the priority of fire protection resulting from applicable legal regulations and standards is primarily the protection of human life and health, and then building. To address the lack of an appropriate methodology for selecting an optimal and cost-effective strategy for the preservation of collections, Jean Tétréault of the Canadian Conservation Institute has developed a method of quantitative assessment of the risks caused by fires in museums, archives and libraries, taking into account the statistical frequency of fires and their estimated effects. The analysis, which Tétréault based on statistical data from Canada, was published in 2008 and is the basis of this tool assessing risks caused by fires.

The developed platform, the first of its kind in the world, has been made freely available on the internet under the HERIE name at herie.pl to anyone involved in the preservation of collections. Since 2014, the HERIE platform has been developed in the framework of several projects funded between other by the European Commission and the Getty Conservation Institute. Since 2020, the HERIE platform is being developed in the framework of the EU IPERION HS project. Also, several tools have been implemented on the platform within the IPERION HS project including the fire risk tool, IMPACT tool and chemical degradation tool. The platform is widely used across the international conservation sector, so far there are 600 registered users, and 2000 unique climate data were uploaded and analysed.

Research disciplines

Mechanics, physics, chemistry, material science, art history, conservation

Service Limitations

- Mechanical damage module can evaluate risks of environments with temperatures below 25 °C and RH below 75%

Service Output Description

- IMPACT tool – the Indoor/Outdoor ratio (%).

- Light damage calculator – original and faded colors are presented as patches on the computer screen in time horizon.
- Chemical degradation tool – the expected lifetime and the relative expected lifetime for a range of low stability materials: wood pulp-based papers post-1850 and cellulose acetate. For a general category of low-stability organic materials, the tool provides only a relative expected lifetime.
- Mechanical damage tool – strain versus time histories with the failure criteria.
- Fire risk – expected loss of collection value expressed as a part of the collection in time horizon.

Service Input Description

- IMPACT tool - the volume of the room, the area of every surface where pollutants can deposit and information on the type of the material, T, RH, and the level of ventilation.
- Light damage calculator – light intensity measured over a prolonged period or amount of color sustained in the object, intensity of light, exposure time per day, number of days per year, number of flashes, time horizon.
- Chemical degradation tool – one-year (or multiyear) temperature and relative humidity data which can be measured or simulated, type of the material.
- Mechanical damage tool – one-year (or multiyear) temperature and relative humidity data which can be measured or simulated, the type and characteristics of the object.
- Fire risk – characteristic of the building, number of objects packed or showcased, the sensitivity of the material to combustion and water and time horizon.

2.3.3 DISCOLL: An open-source research tool for modeling paper-based collection discoloration

Service description

DISCOLL, an open-source research application, serves as a valuable tool for predicting discoloration within paper-based collections. It encompasses a wide spectrum, including historical paper, iron gall ink, and color photographs. This resource is designed to aid in the formulation and enhancement of preservation strategies for effective collection management.

DISCOLL comprises two fundamental functional modules: the "Lifetime Explorer (LE)" and the "Uncertainty Analyzer (UA)." LE adeptly forecasts discoloration over time, considering multiple environmental factors such as oxygen concentration ($[O_2]$), temperature (T), relative humidity (RH), acetic acid (AA), and illuminance (E_v). It facilitates the exploration and comparison of diverse strategies tailored to specific display and preservation objectives.

UA diligently assesses how variations in each environmental factor impact discoloration. By identifying the factors with the most substantial influence, it enables focused efforts and resource allocation toward effective reduction of discoloration variation. These modules empower users to visualize the temporal evolution of discoloration, probe the collective impact of environmental factors on discoloration patterns, and gauge the effect of fluctuations in these factors on the degree of discoloration variation.

Research disciplines

Heritage science, chemistry, statistics, conservation

Service Limitations

DISCOLL currently possesses the capability to analyze three types of material categories: historic paper, iron gall ink, and color photographs. For the former two, the analysis encompasses the impact of $[O_2]$, RH, and E_v , while for the latter, it focuses on the effects of T, RH, and AA.

Service Output Description for the Lifetime Explorer (LE)

LE generates isofade plots to illustrate the relationship between discoloration and selected pairs of factors. These plots are constructed as contour plots, which serve as effective visualization tools for exploring how different factors collaboratively influence the response of collections.

In an isofade plot, each contour line signifies an equal amount of discoloration, with contour line intervals set at 0.1 ΔE_{00} units. To obtain the precise level of discoloration, users can simply hover their mouse over the area of interest on the plot and read the corresponding values displayed beneath it.

Furthermore, if monitoring data is uploaded to the model, one can estimate the expected discoloration level in a specific monitored environment. The resulting plot can then be downloaded for inclusion in reports or for further analysis. This data is instrumental in establishing and refining environmental management plans, particularly in determining damage thresholds and optimization strategies.

Service Output Description for the Uncertainty Analyzer (UA)

The UA results are presented through bar plots, wherein the impact direction and relative magnitude for each factor are visually represented by individual bars. A bar positioned on the positive side of the horizontal axis signifies that the factor promotes discoloration, while a bar on the negative side indicates that the factor inhibits discoloration. The length of each bar is proportionate to the extent of its impact, with longer bars denoting a greater influence on the variation magnitude of discoloration. Consequently, factors associated with longer bars should be given higher priority when implementing collection environmental management strategies.

Service Input Description for the LE

- Type of material: the material of the collection to be analyzed.
- Factors: the external factors that affect the discoloration of the material selected.
- Upload data file: upload environmental monitoring data if applicable.

Service Input Description for the UA

- Type of material: the material of the collection to be analyzed.
- Scenarios: the environmental conditions specifying the fluctuations of the factors.

2.3.4 The IMPACT App

Service Description

IMPACT means Innovative Modelling of Museum Pollution and Conservation Thresholds. This is the name of the project where the IMPACT tool originated. The current version (2) was coded by Josep Grau-Bove, in order to continue offering access to this useful model. The original research was carried out by Nigel Blades, Declan Kruppa, May Cassar (UCL Institute for Sustainable Heritage), and Terje Grøntoft (Norwegian Institute for Air research) (Kruppa, 2002).

The model predicts indoor concentrations of pollutants. The main output is the Indoor/Outdoor ratio (%), which is the percentage of outdoor pollutant concentrations that we can expect indoors. To find this value, the model estimates the deposition flux of pollutants to surfaces. The deposition flux depends on the type of surface, its area, and the air movement in the room. It also depends on a value known as deposition velocity, which has been experimentally determined for a diversity of common indoor surfaces.

To run a simulation, you need to input the volume of the room, the area of every surface where pollutants can deposit, T, RH and the level of ventilation. Ventilation is expressed in Air Exchange Rate (AER, 1/h), which indicates the number of times in an hour that the air in the room is refreshed.

The model shows the indoor concentration at equilibrium. This means that, in a room with no deposition, the internal concentration will eventually be equal to the external, even if it takes a very long time. The time to equilibrium can be explored with the plot Concentration Through Time. An important assumption of the model is that it does not consider homogeneous indoor chemistry, that is, it assumes that the reaction rates of these pollutants are negligible. This assumption is incorrect in some cases.

Service Limitations

The impact app is based on deposition rates measured on around 20 different materials. Deposition is highly materially dependent, so it should be applied to different materials with caution. The tool is designed to be used for exploratory analysis and to understand the relationships between input parameters. However, users who intend to use this model to inform decision-making, are advised to compare the predictions with directly measured concentrations in their spaces. Even a single simultaneous measurement, indoors and outdoors, can be useful to evaluate whether the predictions of the model are reasonable for a specific building.

Service Input

The IMPACT tool requires the following inputs: type of air pollutant, RH, T, AER, outdoor pollutant concentrations, interior volume of the museum and the material and area of different surfaces. Users can select the type of pollutant: NO₂, SO₂ or O₃. Users can determine the type of material and surface area for the walls, floor, ceiling and two other surfaces, for

example, paintings or furniture. Users are advised to either measure or obtain outdoor concentrations from reliable sources, such as automatic air quality monitoring stations.

Service Output

The main output of the IMPACT tool is the indoor pollutant concentration in the space of interest. It also provides two visualisations: the percentage of pollutants deposited on each surface and the relationship between AER and I/O pollutant concentration ratio with an interactive curve graph. These two visualisations enable the exploration of alternative scenarios. There are instances where a small improvement in ventilation can have a notable impact on the internal conditions. The IMPACT tool can help identify such scenarios. Another use of the tool is to investigate the amount of deposition that will occur on different types of surfaces, in order to estimate risks to materials. One of the materials of choice in the tool is “canvas paintings”, which is of special interest to conservation.

Brief description of the mathematical model

This section describes the mathematical model behind the interactive app. The equations reported here are previously published only on project reports that are not widely available. Unless otherwise noted, the implementation of this model within the IMPACT tool follows the main ideas laid out by the original authors of the model. Users of the new version should expect identical functionality.

The indoor concentration in a single room is predicted with a mass balance that considers two main fluxes: the rate of deposition of the pollutants on internal surfaces, and the exchange of pollutants with the external environment. The solution of this mass balance leads to the following expression for the Indoor/Outdoor (I/O) concentration ratio:

$$\frac{C_i}{C_o} = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + v_{d1}A_1/V + \dots + v_{dn}A_n/V}$$

where λ refers to the air change rate of the building in air changes per second, A refers to surface area for a specific material in m^2 , V is the volume in m^3 , C_o is the outdoor concentration of a specific type of air pollutant, C_i is the indoor concentration of the air pollutant, v_d is the dry deposition velocity of the air pollutant to a specific material in m/s and n refers to the number of different materials involved. Each material has a characteristic value of v_d , which is determined with

$$v_d = \frac{v_t v_s}{v_t + v_s}$$

where v_s is the surface deposition velocity of the pollutant on a specific material in m/s and v_t refers to the deposition velocity through the boundary layer of the gas phase, also in m/s . The value of v_s can be experimentally determined, and v_t should ideally be determined with a fluid dynamics simulation of transport in the boundary layer. However, this is often not possible. In order to obtain a simple solution, the authors of the model propose that a reasonable estimation is

$$v_t = K_1^2 * 8 * \lambda * L$$

where k_1 refers to the von Karman constant (usually taken as 0.4), λ is the AER of the building in air changes per second and L refers to the dimension of the room in m. The multiplying factor of 8 present in the equation emerges as a way to convert AER into air velocity. This value was derived by the original research team, who use the equivalence that velocity in a room is approximately $8 * \lambda * L$. This estimation has been found to provide good results with several case studies over the years. In cases where discrepancies with the data are found, this is the first assumption that should be revised.

The IMPACT tool uses experimental values of v_s for NO_2 , SO_2 and O_3 for different types of material collected at $T = 22^\circ\text{C}$ for the RH values of 0%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 90%, which are reported in the literature (Grøntoft, 2004). When the T equals to 22°C , values of v_s in other RH conditions are obtained by linear interpolation between the experimental values. Values of v_s when T is different to 22°C are obtained using an interpolation based on the Arrhenius equation, which the authors found to be valid up to $T = 30^\circ\text{C}$. Values of v_s at any T are obtained with:

$$v_s(T) = \frac{v_s(T_2) \left[\frac{(T-T_1)T_2}{(T_2-T_1)T} \right]}{v_s(T_1) \left[\frac{(T-T_2)T_1}{(T_2-T_1)T} \right]}$$

where $T_1 = 22^\circ\text{C}$, $T_2 = 30^\circ\text{C}$, and $v_s(T_1)$ is taken from the table of experimental values. Based on Eq.4, we can conclude that $v_s(T_2)$ is a linear function of $v_s(T_1)$,

$$v_s(T_2) = k v_s(T_1)$$

where the value of k is 1.71 when RH is 50% and 1.38 when RH is 90%. In our implementation of this model, the value k for different values of RH is linearly interpolated. Therefore, by applying Eq.4, value of v_s when T and RH are specified, can be calculated.

2.3.5 The Lux Allowance Calculator

Service Description

The [Lux allowance calculator](#) is used to check the calculated light exposure (in lux hours) for an object or group of objects for a selected period of display. This is based on three parameters:

- The type of objects being lit
- The number of hours of light needed
- The desired light (lux) levels

The period of time can be adjusted, for example, a whole year or just for the duration of a temporary exhibition. The standard example calculations provided are based on figures quoted by Thomson in *The Museum Environment* (Thomson, 1986) and revisited by Saunders in *Museum Lighting - A Guide for Conservators and Curators* (Saunders, 2020)

The output from the calculator represents the total light exposure for the selected period rather than just a target lux value. This total represents a planned cumulative light dose or 'allowance', that must accommodate normal opening hours, maintenance and security arrangements and out-of-hours activities. To keep the calculated light allowance below the limits given for a particular object type, it may be necessary to limit the number and duration of out-of-hours activities and/or reduce the light levels for the duration of such activities.

Lighting guidelines, in the conservation literature, based on **cumulative light exposures** are generally averaged out over a typical year and can be combined with an **absolute maximum lux level** that should not be exceeded. In practice, these limits can be converted into **operational lux level limits (or lux set points)** adjusted to accommodate the required lighting duration. **When preparing a lighting plan, a range of values need to be considered¹.**

The cumulative allowance will need to accommodate

- Public opening hours
- Lighting for additional planned out-of-hours events
- Lighting for daily cleaning and maintenance
- Lighting for overnight and security patrols
- Additional lighting for unforeseen events

Why is it useful?

There is increasing pressure for collections and institutions to extend their opening hours and develop events and activities programmes, with the result that collections are being exposed to more light. This directly results in increased cumulative exposure of a collection to the damaging effects of light and potentially accelerates deterioration processes. This increase in light exposure together with any increases in other 'agents of deterioration' (<https://www.canada.ca/en/conservation-institute/services/agents-deterioration.html>) such

¹ All ultraviolet (UV) radiation with a wavelength of less than 380 nm must also be excluded from the light, whether from natural or artificial sources.

as handling and movement of the collection, activity-induced vibration and increased levels of dirt and pest ingress, can lead to an increased overall risk and potential for damage, not just to collections but also to the building fabric and engineering systems providing environmental controls.

The original calculations (proposed by Thomson) were based on an average 200 lux for 8 hrs per day plus a low level of adventitious and security lighting for the remaining hours of each day (Thomson, 1986). However, many institutions are now open far longer, thus complicating these calculations, and a simple illuminance limit is no longer suitable.

Recent work in preventive conservation research has resulted in a re-examination of the recommendations for cumulative light exposure levels and limits. The overall recommended levels may have been reduced, relative to previous levels, meaning there are potentially less 'light hours' available for out-of-hours activities. This has the potential to impact on how the institutions operates, for example, limiting the number of out-of-hours activities possible with the light allowance available.

Service Limitations

This is an automatic web-based tool, some minor customisation is possible and is described in the instructions, but for more complex adjustments one would need to download the source code (<https://github.com/jpadfield/Lux-Allowance-Calculator/>).

Service output description

A text-based description of the total estimated lux exposure for a defined period of exposure. The description also includes comments related to over exposure, required offsetting and options for exploiting any unused allowance.

Service Input Descriptions

Text and numbers: The dates of the period of interest, the class of objects being considered, the hours of exposure and the relevant lux set points and limits.

2.3.6 Collections Demography App and Box Buffering Capacity App

Service Description for Collections Demography

The app supports preventive conservation decision-making in the context of storage in large archives and libraries.

The fundamental concepts used in this app were developed in the frame of the UK AHRC/EPSRC Collections Demography project (Strlic, 2015).

On the basis of environmental inputs (**temperature, relative humidity**) as well as material properties (**paper pH** and **degree of polymerisation - DP**), the app returns the predicted **remaining useful life** of paper. This is calculated as the time it takes until the particular paper reaches a **critical DP value** that no longer allows safe handling, at the given environmental conditions. A typical threshold value for the degree of polymerisation that allows safe manipulation of a sheet of paper in the context of reading in a library or in an archive, is 300.

If the material properties are unknown, the tool offers a number of pre-set options based on “typical” categories of Western paper, i.e. rag, lignin-containing, bleached and contemporary paper. The average values of pH and degree of polymerisation for these were determined on the basis of a survey of the SurveNIR research collection (Strlic, 2020).

Based on the input **long-term planning horizon**, plots of suitable T and RH are calculated that support the retention of paper material properties that enable safe use into the future. The long-term planning horizon is the period of time for which preservation can be meaningfully planned, e.g. typically 100 – 500 years (Bell, 2018).

The app also enables the calculation of the remaining useful life for entire collections. Users can either input their own data or explore preservation scenarios using sets of data measured in surveys of case study collections (SurveNIR – a research collection of paper, Amsterdam City Archives/The Netherlands (Duran-Casablancas, 2021) , and Classense Library/Italy (Brown, 2020). The plots are output as loss of fitness for manual handling (typical for libraries and archives) in time, i.e., **demographic plots**.

Users can also “construct” their own collections, i.e., input proportions of acidic, deacidified, contemporary and rag paper. This allows the calculation of demography plots for hypothetical collections, such as e.g., a typical Western library collection, consisting of 70% acidic paper and 30% contemporary paper, even without performing a survey.

A supplementary tab allows users to calculate the long-term effect of **deacidification** on collections, specifically on the demographic plots.

The app can also be usefully used for other cellulosic materials, e.g. painting canvases (Oriola, 2015) as well as other types of paper, e.g. Chinese (Luo, in press), Islamic (Mahgoub, 2016) or Tibetan (Luo, in press) paper, and is available at https://hsl.shinyapps.io/COL_DEM_3/.

The development of the app was carried out by the Heritage Science Lab Ljubljana (University of Ljubljana) and UCL Institute for Sustainable Heritage, in collaboration with the Smithsonian Institution’s Museum Conservation Institute and the Library of Congress.

Service Description for the Box Buffering Capacity App

The app supports the estimation of suitability of archival boxes and other enclosures to buffer fluctuations of RH within the box/enclosure, in the context of preventive conservation decision making.

The app calculates the RH within the enclosure on the basis of a mass transfer model assuming that temperature does not have a major effect on the transmission of humidity through structural openings or through the box material (Markelj, in preparation).

The properties of diverse cardboards, as well as boards made of polypropylene, wrapping paper, wrapping textiles etc., such as water vapour transmission rate, were measured using standard techniques (Novak, in preparation). The air exchange rates for diverse materials as well as box construction types, e.g., 2-part boxes, clamshell boxes, with/without ventilation openings, with/without hydrophobic sealant layer application, were also measured.

The app allows us to calculate the **HA index** – humidity attenuation index – an index that describes the buffering capacity of a box, the closer it is to 100, the more stable the RH within the box is, regardless of RH fluctuations outside the box.

Users can explore the properties of boxes either using the pre-set HA indices or they can calculate their own HA index for the material of choice, on the basis of a set of RH measurements within and outside the box of interest.

To model the RH fluctuation within a chosen box, the users need to input the maximum environmental RH fluctuations they would need to buffer, e.g., +/-30% in an exposed environment, such as a church, or +/-20% as experienced in country houses or open, non-purpose built storage areas etc.; and the allowable fluctuation within the box, e.g. +/-10%. The app then calculates whether the selected box has suitable RH buffering properties.

This allows users to select boxes and other enclosure materials that are suitable for sustainable, low-cost management of storage microenvironments.

The app is available at https://hsl.shinyapps.io/ha_index_pub/. Its development was funded by the EU H2020 projects IPERION HS and APACHE (GA 814496).

The development of the app was carried out by the Heritage Science Lab Ljubljana (University of Ljubljana) and UCL Institute for Sustainable Heritage, in collaboration with the Smithsonian Institution's Museum Conservation Institute.

Service Limitations

The service is designed to perform optimally within the following environmental conditions: 20% > RH > 80%; 5 °C > T > 35 °C

Service Output Description

Collections Demography App: (i) remaining useful lifetime of paper: time (at set T, RH) until unacceptable risk of mechanical damage for diverse types of paper; (ii) demographic plots for

collections, consisting of mixed paper types, e.g. rag, acidic, deacidified, contemporary paper;
(iii) effect of deacidification on the demographic plots for collections of paper.

Box Buffering Capacity App: Calculation of the Humidity Attenuation Index for a selected box (material type, size, construction type) and evaluation of the RH buffering capacity in environments with unwanted RH fluctuations.

Service Input Description

Environmental data: RH, T

Material data: paper pH, degree of polymerisation

2.3.7 Shaping future apps, such as one for light

Background

LED-based lighting systems were for a long period in doubt and met with skepticism regarding their appropriateness for Museum lighting. However, recent technology developments and rigorous quality testing have contributed to set the requirements and form a quality assessment framework to reach the balance between visibility and preservation criteria, as well as environmental considerations, allowing their progressive introduction in Museum lighting. Today, LED technology is pertinent in addressing the complex lighting needs and challenges faced in today's museums and galleries, and as long as the quality criteria are met, the energy and cost saving qualities of these light sources ensure a viable option. LED based lighting systems combined with sensors and automatization systems to turn off lights when visitors exit an exhibition space can also contribute to saving lighting costs and comply with sustainability policies. Museum lighting guidelines encourage also the use of existing tools and protocols to acquire light sensitivity data (e.g. MFT) and digital tools to estimate photochemical deterioration (mainly darkening or fading,) caused by a "dose" of light defined as a product of the illumination intensity and duration of exposure, as part of the preventive conservation practices.

The Canadian Conservation Institute's Online [Light Damage Calculator](#) which has been widely used within the Preventive Conservation Community and has been recently integrated in the [HERie platform](#), is intended to provide an estimate of the change of colors exposed to light, based on the best available data.

Motivation

The CCI Light Damage Calculator has been developed, validated and extensively used for museum illumination systems based on incandescent / halogen lamps, for which the light damage estimation can be pertinently calculated based on photometric intensity (illuminance) measurements with a luxmeter and time of exposure (light dose in units of lux × hours).

However, LED-based light sources with a spectral profile, which commonly presents emission maxima outside the limits of the photopic curve², centered at $\lambda = 555 \text{ nm}$, the calculation of the light intensity in terms of lux, may be misleading. The estimation of the total irradiance (W/m^2) of a light source in the entire visible range should be considered for the estimation of the effect of lighting on the fading or color change of photosensitive pigments. Moreover, several earlier and more recent studies, following different approaches and experimental irradiation setups, converge providing evidence on the wavelength dependency of the discoloration of dyes and pigments, to mention few of these previous studies.

Work carried out in IPERION HS

² The photopic curve represents the **luminous efficiency function** that corresponds to the average spectral sensitivity of human visual perception of light in photopic conditions, that is well-lit conditions, in the range of 10^{-10} to $10^8 \text{ cd}/\text{m}^2$.

In the framework of IPERION HS task 5.1, that focuses on monitoring objects and environment for the preventive conservation of paintings, the present project was outlined aiming at

- (a) investigating and proposing improvements on monitoring light-induced color changes of sensitive pigments and dyes
- (b) proposing more appropriate methods for the estimation and mitigation of potential risk of color change due to exposure to light.

This twofold objective was addressed by analyzing the results obtained from the experiments carried out in Project “Monitoring chemical and physical changes of paintings”, section 2.1.1, reported in the same document, investigating detectable damage (color change) upon accelerated aging (in controlled / measurable conditions) and parallel MFT measurements on the same set of mock-ups.

Respectively, two directions of investigation have been identified in this project:

- (a) proposing a new method for monitoring the wavelength-dependent light-induced color changes on pigments in paintings.
- (b) Proposing simple risk assessment methods for the color decay of pigments in paintings/objects exposed to light, based on assessing the spectral emission profile of a selected light source and data on the color change profile (acquired with microfading tests on spots, or already available data) of the photosensitive materials/areas of interest on a specific object.

The goal of this effort is to step forward towards the development of a tool allowing to customize lighting, tailored to the specifications of individual artworks, by selecting a type of lighting source and defining safe limits of light exposure to achieve a balance between minimum risk and optimum rendering of the object on display.

However, due to time limitations in this project, the data obtained were limited and were available for analysis later than initially scheduled, therefore the results presented in this report are considered preliminary and require further work. To reach a point for developing a new tool for light damage estimation or proposing improvements on existing tools, the processing of additional data and continuous discussion with those collecting and interpreting light damage data are still ongoing.

Identifying gaps in the current state of the art

Measuring the intensity of light on the object’s surface (@FORTH)

When measuring the intensity of light incident on an object’s surface with a luxmeter, the illuminance values on the surface can be similar for different light sources, while the respective total irradiance of each light source may differ significantly. If we take for example, four white light sources of different technology and different spectral profiles (Figure 48), the light intensity reaching the object’s surface (illuminance (lx)), may be of the same value, e.g., 10000 lx. However, this value may correspond to very different values of total irradiance (W/m^2), and certainly a different distribution of this irradiance in the entire visible spectral range (380-780 nm).

Figure 48. Comparative graphical representation of the irradiance and illuminance values, respectively, of four light sources of different technology and spectral power distribution.

If we calculate, for example, the respective total irradiance values in W/m^2 (in the visible spectral range (380-780 nm)), that would be measured with a power meter, the values obtained, respectively, would be as follows:

- GE F40W/AD: FL - 6500K = $38.4 W/m^2$
- CREE LRP-38 (Dupe): LED - 2700K = $28.37 W/m^2$
- GE EYC 71W MR16 (Tungsten) 2709K = $66.36 W/m^2$
- SORAA MR16 GU10 7.5W 5000K = $39.5 W/m^2$

This example demonstrates the importance of considering more accurate measurements, based on total irradiance, for the estimation of the exposure of the object to light.

Results of analysis of the data obtained in IPERION HS Project 1 (section 2.1.1) that could be exploitable for further developments.

1. As reported in Project 1 (section 2.1.1) it was possible to work in parallel with two different approaches with microfading (MFT) tests and conventional accelerated lightfastness tests, and obtain comparable results on the estimation of light induced color change, using diffuse reflectance data in the visible range obtained on the same mock-ups made up of light-sensitive pigments (i.e., (a) strontium yellow and (b) Prussian blue mixed with lead white).

This was possible, by following a protocol for adjusting respectively the irradiation time, taking into account the very different fluence rates of the two systems, in order to obtain equivalent total irradiance values for the two different experimental approaches and set-ups: (a) the accelerated photoageing experiments with three different white light sources (a xenon lamp – filtered in the UV (to cut $\lambda \leq 320$ nm) and IR region; a warm white LED source-2700K and a cool white LED source-4000K) and (b) established microfading test protocols using a xenon lamp (with a 400-700 bandpass filter).

2. In addition to the established $\Delta E_{2000}(t)$ plot, an alternative method for monitoring color changes on paints was proposed, by defining a mathematical formula for

estimating the mean change in reflectance $\Delta R_{\lambda}(t)$ over a narrow spectral window versus time. This narrow spectral window corresponds to the wavelength range in which for the specific pigment or paint, the maximum change in spectra is occurring (@NTU).

3. In parallel, an alternative evaluation and processing of the data obtained with accelerated photo-ageing experiments was aimed to the investigation of the photochemical effectiveness of white light sources with different spectral profiles in causing color change for various pigments in paint matrices. Estimation of the wavelength-dependent effective spectral irradiance of light sources causing color change would be a valuable tool for risk assessment and mitigation when setting lighting conditions for objects on display (@FORTH).

As a first step, a simple approach was proposed to provide information about the emission spectrum of a light source and classifying the light sources based on their spectral profile. The proposed classification of light sources (of any technology as LED, tungsten, xenon etc.) is based on their relative emission/per cent of the total emission (400 to 750 nm) in the three spectral bands of the blue, green and red range of the visible spectrum and their total irradiation power in the entire visible range.

Within this project, the selected ranges considered for the calculations are the following, while the exact limits of the spectral bands could be further adjusted, based on the processing of additional data:

- Blue: $400 < B < 500$ nm
- Green: $500 < G < 600$ nm
- Red: $600 \text{ nm} < R < 750$ nm

For a light source the values of the spectral band components are calculated using the equation:

$$B = \frac{\text{Blue spectral range emission}}{\text{Total emission in the visible}} * 100\%$$

$$G = \frac{\text{Green spectral range emission}}{\text{Total emission in the visible}} * 100\%$$

$$R = \frac{\text{Red spectral range emission}}{\text{Total emission in the visible}} * 100\%$$

In figure 49 the values of the RGB components of the emission spectra of two LED sources (WLED 2700 K and WLED 4000 K) used in Project 1,³ are presented. These three values are characteristic of the emission spectrum of each light source.

³ cf. Figure 4, par. 2.1.1., page 18 of the same document

Figure 49. a) the WLED 2700 K emission spectrum and the RGB light source values (9,36,55) calculated from the spectrum and b) the WLED 4000 K emission spectrum and the RGB lights source values (20,41,39) calculated from the spectrum.

*Estimation of the color change effect on a pigment/paint in the $L^*a^*b^*$ color space, based on the spectral profile (RGB spectral components) of a light source.*

Using the datasets obtained through the accelerated lightfastness tests of the most light-sensitive paint mock-ups (namely, those with strontium yellow and Prussian blue (Project 1),⁴ the $L^*a^*b^*$ values calculated from the visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy data, have been plotted versus the values of the Blue, or Green or Red component of the total cumulative irradiance, separately, in comparison with the respective $L^*a^*b^*$ plots versus the total cumulative irradiance over the aging time, as it is in the default plots.

The percentage values of the irradiance at each of the spectral ranges are calculated from the RGB components of the spectral profile of each light source and the total irradiance using the equations below.

$$I_{red} = \frac{R}{100} * total\ irradiance$$

$$I_{green} = \frac{G}{100} * total\ irradiance$$

$$I_{blue} = \frac{B}{100} * total\ irradiance$$

As an example, in Figure 50, the data showing the change of lightness (L^*) over the accelerated aging time (and respective cumulative irradiance) are presented for the strontium yellow mock-up.

In the Figure 50(a), the L^* values measured on the exposed surface over the aging time/total irradiance are plotted versus the cumulative total irradiance dose in the visible spectral range (default). Figure 50(b) represents instead the same L^* values plotted versus the values of the Blue percentage of the cumulative irradiance dose for the three different light sources used in the experiments.

⁴ cf. par. 2.1.1, of the same document

Figure 50. a) L^* values over different total irradiation dose and b) L^* values over the blue percentage of the irradiation dose for the strontium yellow pigment. In both plots, the x axis is in logarithmic scale.

We have observed that the change in $L^*a^*b^*$ values of strontium yellow oil paints exposed to different light sources exhibit a considerably stronger correlation when accounting for their distinct relative power distributions in the RGB spectral bands than for their total power within the visible spectrum. This finding suggests that various light sources can be directly compared by considering their respective “RGB” values. Moreover, standardizing the light sources using the “RGB” values and exploiting available color change profiles obtained through MFTs, as those depicted in Figure 50, it enables estimating the impact of a given light source on the progression of color change over subsequent cumulative light exposure. The proposed approach is notably straightforward, as it only requires providing the ‘RGB’ components of the light sources and measuring the total irradiation power on the artwork/artefact surface.

Furthermore, it offers an opportunity for a quantitative evaluation of color changes throughout the aging process of a paint that can be performed not only by experts in the field of spectroscopy/conservation but also by professionals on museum lighting. These initial findings indicate that the effect of different light sources can be consistently assessed by considering both the relative spectral power distribution and the overall irradiation power of these light sources. However, due to the limited scope of the analyzed datasets, further research is imperative to validate these preliminary results before arriving at actionable conclusions.

2.3.8 Stakeholder engagement and scoping of community needs

The project involved one key stakeholder event, a week-long workshop in May 2023, organised by the developers of the IPERION apps. The event was a combination of technical training on the use of the apps and a feedback focus group. Each app was presented and demonstrated within a 2 hour practical session, which included a two-way dialogue about its functionality. Finally, in a wrap-up moderated discussion session, the participants expressed their informed views on the state-of-the-art and interests in future development.

Results

The event was attended by participants from a diversity of nationalities and levels of expertise, all linked to preventive conservation in GLAMs. The participants reported good levels of satisfaction with the performance of the apps (N = 18). In the question on the ease of use of the apps, the average is large positive, but with a substantial standard deviation and a mode cantered at the middle of the scale. While no participants responded negatively, it is clear that app interfaces are perceived as the area in more need of development. The majority

of participants found them easy to learn and were interested in using them in the future .

Figure 51. Summary of a poll among the attendees of the stakeholder training and engagement event in May 2023. Data in a 5 point Likert scale.

When asked what activities the apps can support, the answers clustered around the following main activities:

- Education, teaching and training, such as learning preventive conservation.
- Supporting policy decisions or decision-making.
- Demonstrating conservation arguments in a quantitative and visual way to non-conservator stakeholders.

It is remarkable that educational purposes featured high in the preferences of participants. This should be taken into account in the development of future digital infrastructures for preventive conservation, bearing in mind that they have the double purpose of educating and supporting decisions. Many respondents also highlighted an interest in using the apps to solve

practical problems. While this is possible and desirable, it should be made with a full awareness of the uncertainties and limitations of the services. Uncertainty, however, was never mentioned as part of the discussion. It is therefore imperative that these apps are presented with a clear statement of their limits of applicability.

When asked how the apps should be presented in a website, this included:

- A desire to have a single platform that unites all the apps.
- Case studies, worked examples, and demonstrations of the performance of the apps.
- Videos and case studies demonstrating the use.
- A wiki where users can share experiences.

Summary of main findings

Apps are seen as resources for education as well as practical preventive conservation

Users see the apps as facilitating communication with decision-makers

An online platform that aggregates all the services is seen as positive, with:

- Forums, with replies by developers
- Manuals and videos
- Examples and case studies

The needs for future development are as related to research gaps as they are to software (e.g. more materials, better data).

2.3.9 Description of the requirements of ideal apps

The following points are the result of the cumulative consensus formed within the many discussions among developers within this project, complemented with the main outcomes of the stakeholder engagement.

User Interface requirements

1. Front page with a clear concise description of the app and its purpose.
2. Visual, user-friendly, easy to use interface. An elegant graphical design is a plus.
3. Instructions for new users: System requirements (operating systems / compute capability), Installation steps (if installation is required)
4. Credits, User License
5. User-profile settings and preferences /user account / authentication
6. Detailed user manual, Tutorials, step by step use guide (+videos), Demo files, examples gallery, real scenarios of use.

Content requirements / key features

7. Clear definition of the target and outcome, to prevent misuse. Tags, keywords, key features, application materials and objects are relevant.
8. Clear and full documentation or reference to the theoretical basis and calculations involved.
9. Clear requirements for input data
10. Input-output data format (import/export) multiple options
11. Provide with available / open datasets, ideally provide access to a knowledge base of approved data (metadata)
12. Possibility to enrich content: (data and metadata specs for data input)
13. Modular calculation – experimenting real-time the impact of changing different parameters.
14. Enabled customization options.

Wish list

15. Data/results visualization with graphs simulating the potential effect of deterioration in the materials of the object and images rendering such change as a preview of the altered appearance of the object (how the object will look like)
16. Risk assessment with the same environmental dataset for different collections / materials
17. Evaluation of predicted change under several agents of deterioration and risk factors
18. Separately, identifying the factors with most significant impact vs materials sensitivity
19. Jointly (combined effect)
20. Cumulatively in a period of time.

Community building

21. Create a virtual research environment including
22. Forum for communication, exchange within groups interested on the same topic
23. Repository of open resources
24. Virtual space for testing new / beta version apps - invite users to test (with or without guidance) new apps and give feedback – reporting bugs - suggestions for improvements)

2.3.10 A validation case-study: the case of El Paular

The cloister of the Monastery of Santa María del Paular (closed) is used as a case study to test a dust deposition model. It is located in a mountain environment (on a plateau of about 1,159 meters of altitude). The cloister has an approximate perimeter of 180 meters. It houses a collection of 52 large (3.45 x 3.15 m) oil paintings on canvas by Vincenzo Carduccio, which are frameless and whose upper part is curved, to adapt to the shape of the cloister arches for which they were originally designed.

The cloister is visited by the public. The fact of being away from the large population centers means that the number of visitors is not very large, which makes it easier to carry out sample collection work or deployment of measuring equipment there. It is also an environment with a complex geometry, which constitutes a challenge for any model related to air movements. The minimum particle diameter that could be measured was about 2 microns.

Protocol

Direct dust deposition on glass slides placed on the cloister walls next to the canvases were collected for a full year. For it:

- Glass slides were thoroughly cleaned in the laboratory
- They were placed together with the canvases on ad hoc supports to keep them in a horizontal position at about 3 m above ground level, which placed them at a distance between 1.2 and 1.5 meters from the base of the canvas.
- After a certain period of time, the slides were collected and photographed in the laboratory with a 10x magnification.
- From the photographs, a count of the size and number of particles deposited was made.
- The deposition patterns were characterized according to the different observation periods (seasons) and positions in the cloister.
- The result was contrasted with the predictions of a model based on fluid mechanics
- All of them were done under normal conditions of visit and operation of the place.
- The count of the size and number of deposited particles was carried out automatically from the photographs obtained through the ImageJ software using various available functions: image inversion, application of an automatic triangle-type threshold, count of particles and their size.

A sample of 40 images was taken per slide collected to establish the distribution of particles by number and size.

Two models were used for comparison with this data: a CFD simulation and a simple, well-mixed model. .

Protocol limitations and advances

The veracity of the particle count results and, therefore, of the estimated distributions of deposition in the cloister space is closely linked to the fact that the distribution of deposition

is uniform over the entire surface of the slide (there is no reason to think it shouldn't be like that).

It was necessary to discard a number of images (around 5%) because they contained particles whose size exceeded or was similar to the area covered by the image (0.567 mm²) or because they were fibers that appeared out of focus for the most part except in the contact points on the glass slides. Given the low number of these incidents (less than 5% of the images), an insignificant affection is estimated.

Comparison between the measurements and the model

The single environment deposition model used in this research is available as a free app, programmed in Shiny R like the IMPACT app (<https://josepgrau.shinyapps.io/dustbis/>). This model was used to estimate the deposition velocity at the conditions found at El Paular.

Figure 52 shows the cumulative particle size distribution at the 7 monitoring locations, after the complete monitoring campaign. There are two main trends to note:

- The median is usually slightly below 2.5 microns, except in locations 6 and 7 where it is slightly higher.
- There is a wide variation of total amounts. The height of the tallest peak (the mode) ranges from 9600 particles per location to 30.000.

The main question that can be explored with modelling is, consequently, why the deposition rate varies by a factor of 3 across the space. There are generally two possible hypotheses in such cases: (1) the increased deposition could be caused by a higher amount of particles in this location, (2) the amount of particles may be constant, but the capacity of the particles to deposit (the deposition velocity) is increased by the local air velocity patterns.

The first hypothesis that can be contested with simulations is (2). The simulations were conducted at the mode of these distributions (approximately 2.5 micrometres). The deposition velocity was calculated assuming different rates of turbulence. The calculations, assuming minimum and maximum turbulence, result all in deposition rates very close to 0.0254 cm/s. In order to obtain a ratio of 3 between the lowest and highest deposition rate caused by turbulence, the particle diameter of the calculations needs to be lowered approximately 0.43 micrometres. In other words, the deposition observed differences are most likely not caused by variations in ventilation and air motion. They must be caused by differences in the amount of suspended particles.

Figure 52. Cumulative particle size distributions over the complete experiment, including a map of the monitoring locations. Analysis by Xilan Wu.

Nonetheless, significant gradients of velocity exist in the space. In order to determine the extent of their impact, a Fluid Dynamics simulation was conducted. The geometry used is shown in Figure 52(2) and 52(3). A simplified building model was used, that retains only the most significant features. The architectural detailing of the vault was considered necessary for the simulation, despite the fact that it complicated the 3D modelling stage. However, the effects of the vault on the flow were considered potentially significant. The main inlets and outlets of air are gaps around and underneath the access doors. These were represented in the simulation as small gaps of 5-10 cm below the doors. Whether this is an appropriate simplification was tested by simulating the same environment with different gaps. This evidence is in preparation for publication.

Figure 52(4) displays an example of one of the CFD simulations. Different scenarios were simulated, changing the orientation of the exterior wind, and reflecting predominant directions and intensities. In this example, the interior air velocity displays a wide variability, with values ranging from 0 to 1 m/s. At the time of writing this report, further analysis is being conducted with the following aims:

- To correlate the local air velocity with the local measurements of dust deposition
- To repeat the analysis with monthly measurements rather than yearly measurements
- To correlate the internal measured deposition with other external factors such as the airborne particulate matter concentration measured in nearby weather stations, or the number of days in a month where saharan dust is detected on the atmosphere (a common phenomenon in Spain).

So far, this comparison has demonstrated that that real life measurements of dust deposition display a complexity and variability that is difficult to integrate in a simple online app. However, the calculations of the well-mixed model are interesting enough to offer some insight on the causes of deposition (at the very least, to discard the hypothesis that the differences in deposition are caused by differences in air motion). This example will be integrated in the manual of the online tool to demonstrate its advantages and limitations.

Figure 53. General view of the simplified geometry.

Figure 54. Detail of the internal architecture.

Figure 55. Average air velocity in one of the scenarios.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this deliverable outlines the next steps for advancing art conservation practices for preventative conservation. A set of analytical techniques have been systematically applied to a broader range of paint mock-ups and environmental parameters. The advances, limitations and future perspectives of each technique are described in this deliverable. The newly described or improved protocols carried out on paint mock-ups serve as the foundation and starting point for actual implementing in authentic paintings. High quality environmental data are crucial for preventive conservation and the protocols described in this deliverable provide a user-friendly information for the selection and deployment of monitoring techniques. Most of the analytical techniques discussed in the deliverable are offered via the IPERION HS catalogue of services. Decision support systems require in most cases environmental data are compiled in a digital platform for preventive conservation. The digital apps are presented in a single website, the E-RIHS - Digital Tools, Services and Resources, <https://e-rihs.io/resources.html>, planned to be merged in E-RIHS - ERIC DIGILAB open services.

Overview project partners

Abbreviation	Institute	Country
CNR-SCITEC	Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche	Italy
CNR-ISPC	Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale	Italy
CNR-INO	Istituto Nazionale di Ottica	Italy
CNR-IFAC	Istituto di Fisica Applicata	Italy
NCU	Nicolaus Copernicus University	Poland
JHI	Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry Polish Academy of Science	Poland
AGH	AGH University of Science and Technology	Poland
UW	University of Warsaw	Poland
UL	University of Ljubljana	Slovenia
UCL	University College London	UK
NGL	National Gallery London	UK
IQFR-CSIC	Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano	Spain
NTU	Nottingham Trent University	UK
FORTH	The Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
OF-ADC	Ormylia Foundation, Art Diagnosis Center	Greece
IPCE	Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España	Spain
UiO	University of Oslo	Norway
CENIM-CSIC	Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Metalúrgicas	Spain
CNRS-C2RMF	C2RMF	France
IPCHS	Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia	Slovenia
RCE	Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands	Netherlands
RMA	Rijksmuseum	Netherlands
SI MCI	The Smithsonian Institution – Museum Conservation Institute	USA
UNAM	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Mexico

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Appendices

Appendix 2.1.1

1 Paint mock-ups preparation. Samples described in section II were prepared UiO in collaboration with MUNCH Museum (NOR).

2 Microfading tests (partners involved: NTU, UK; AGH, PI).

NTU

MFT.

The illumination source used was an Ocean Optics HXP-2000 Xenon light source. To allow visible transmission only a 400 nm to 700 nm bandpass filter was applied in front of the illumination. The optical set-up for the system was of 45°/45° retroreflection. The focusing procedure, which should be applied before measurement of any standard and for each measurement of a painted sample, consists of an autofocus mechanism running with a reduced illumination intensity of around 10%. The time taken for autofocus in this case is <10 s.

The source has a PC controlled TTL shutter mechanism for the precise control of color change times. The total power incident on the material was measured as 0.24 mW using a Thorlabs S121C Si based detector, and assuming the average wavelength of the illumination is 600 nm (a good approximation if using a Xe source with 400-700 nm bandpass filter). It should be noted that thermal detectors, such as Thorlabs 302C, are not reliable at such low power level. The spot size (μm) and area (cm^2) were measured directly with a CCD/CMOS mono detector with known pixel size and was found to be $202 \mu\text{m} \times 266 \mu\text{m}$. The total irradiance incident on the material at a given time was calculated to be 0.56 W/cm^2 over 400-1100 nm or 0.45 W/cm^2 over 400-700 nm, equivalent to 1.1 Mlux. For more details on the general instrument set-up for the NTU MFT see Liang et al., 2011. The post-processing was carried out using in-house developed routines written in Matlab and Python. Spectral calibration was carried out using a Labsphere calibrated Spectralon white standard (99%).

AGH

MFT.

The instrument was produced by Instytut Fotonowy/Poland; (Chan et al., 2022; Łojewski et al., 2019) it is equipped with a 6-position WLED revolver that allows selecting WLEDs of different color temperatures, that are installed according to clients' specification.

Microfading tests with 5500K WLEDs (power: 12.4 mW; 14.7 Mlx) were performed for 12.2 min, such as to obtain a final total irradiance value of ca. 1.32 W/cm²·h (3 Mlxh). Experiments with 2700K WLEDs (6.68 mW, 8.40 Mlx), were instead carried out for 21.4 min so to obtain a total irradiance value of 1.04 W/cm²·h (3 Mlxh). Main instrumental features: automated focusing, 0.5-0.55 mm spot (depending on the selected LED), macrocamera, software allowing to set all test parameters – data collection interval, power setting, conditions for test duration (dose/time/total color change), visualisation of measured color changes. User-configured reports generated by the instrument controlling software (a pdf file with tables, figures, photos and comments written by the used during or after measurements).

3 Conventional accelerated lightfastness test and monitoring of color (chemical) changes(partners involved: CNR-SCITEC, CNR-ISPC, CNR-IFAC, UniPg – Ita).

Two identical sets of samples were subject to comparable accelerated aging conditions by using three different lighting systems (cf. Figure 4) located at laboratories of CNR-SCITEC (Perugia), Unipg and CNR-ISPC (Firenze). Paint samples were monitored using UV-vis-NIR and SWNIR reflectance spectroscopy (in diffuse reflectance mode) and colorimetry at subsequent steps of aging. At CNR-ISPC paints were also studied by FTIR spectroscopy (in reflectance mode). The aging time were calculated by assessing similar final total irradiance for the two irradiation campaigns. This experimentation was aimed also at testing the compliance of the samples with reciprocity principle.

The characterization of all sources was performed by an irradiance calibrated AvaSpec-2048-2 spectrometer (Avantes, NL) provided with a 200 mm diameter optical fiber (FC-UVIR200-2 ME, Avantes) and a 8 mm active area cosine corrector (CC-UV-VIS/ NIR, Avantes). The spectrometer operates in the 171–1100 nm range (300 lines per mm grating) and is equipped with an AvaBench-75 optical bench, a 25 mm slit which produced 1.2 nm FWHM spectral resolution and a 2048 pixel CCD detector. Measurements were performed at the sample position (distance of ca. 35-40 cm from the source) using a 7–1000 ms integration time and with 20–50 accumulations. The lamp profiles (cf. Figure 4) and the corresponding photometric/radiometric quantities were obtained by averaging 4–25 spectral data that were collected throughout the experiment

Experiments at CNR-SCITEC (Perugia) and UniPg.

Experiments were performed using the following set-ups: an in-house made aging chamber equipped with a Xenon lamp filtered in the UV and IR region (irradiance: 0.030±0.01 W/cm²; total irradiance: 0.21±0.01 W/cm²·h); an in-house made aging set-up with two WLEDs (color temperature: 4000 K and 2700 K; ≈irradiance: 0.019-0.020 W/cm² and total irradiance: ≈0.177-194 W/cm²·h; cf. Figure 4 produced by a tunable W-LEDs prototype developed by F&M Progetti srl (Prato, Italy).

A JASCO V-570 spectrometer, which allowed UV-Vis-NIR-SWIR diffuse reflectance spectra to be recorded. The instrument is equipped with a deuterium lamp (190-350 nm) and a halogen lamp (330-2500 nm) as sources and with a photomultiplier tube as a detector in the UV-Vis range, while a Peltier-cooled PbS detector is suitable for the NIR region. Spectra were

recorded in the 210–2400 nm range using 2 nm and 40 nm spectral bandwidth in the UV–visible-NIR and SWNIR region, respectively.

Colorimetry was carried out by a Konica-Minolta CM700D instrument furnished with a pulsed xenon lamp emitting in the visible spectral range, an integrating sphere with a 40 mm internal diameter and a silicon photodiode array detector. A D65 standard illuminant and 2° angle observer were used for the conversion of the spectra (recorded in the 360–740 nm range and with 10 nm spectral resolution) into CIEL*a*b* chromatic coordinates.

Experiments at CNR-ISPC (Firenze) and CNR-IFAC.

Photoaging treatments were performed using the following set-ups: (i) a SolarBox 3000e chamber (CO.FO.ME.GRA Srl) equipped with a xenon lamp filtered in the UV and IR regions (irradiance: 0.00088 W/cm²; total irradiance: 0.185 W/cm²·h); (ii) an in-house made aging chamber furnished with the same tunable WLEDs prototype used at CNR-SCITEC laboratories (see above). The same WLEDs with temperature of 4000 K and 2700 K were selected for aging treatments (≈irradiance: 0.00054–0.00055 W/cm² and total irradiance: ≈0.187–189 W/cm²·h).

The Konica-Minolta CM700 colorimeter was used to control the color changes (see above for the description). Diffuse reflectance UV-vis-NIR and SWNIR spectroscopy measurements were performed using a double-beam and double-monochromator bench-top spectrophotometer mod. Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050, which operates in the 200–2500 nm range with spectral resolution of ±0.05 nm in the UV-vis range, and ±0.2 nm in the NIR and SWNIR regions. The instrument is equipped with an internal 60-mm integrating sphere. Measurements were performed with exclusion of reflectance specular component. As white reference a certified target Spectralon 99% reflectance was used.

FTIR spectroscopy investigations were performed in reflection mode by means of a portable ALPHA spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Germany/USA—MA), equipped with a SiC global source and a DLaTGS detector. Spectra were acquired in the spectral range of 7000–375 cm⁻¹, at a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and using 128 scans. Spectra from a gold flat mirror were used as background. Three spectra were acquired on three areas of each mock-up. All data were collected using Opus software.

Micro-spectroscopy FTIR measurements in imaging mode were carried out by a Bruker LUMOS II FTIR microscope (Bruker Optics GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany), equipped with a liquid-N₂ cooled 32×32 element Focal Plane Array (FPA) detector. FPA-FTIR images were acquired in reflection mode within a 4000–750 cm⁻¹ spectral region, each as a single FTIR image (1024 spectra) covering a sampling area of ca. 150×150 mm², with resolution 4 cm⁻¹ and 128 scans. A single spectrum in each FTIR image represents molecular information acquired from ca. 5×5 μm² area on the sample plane. The collected FTIR spectra were processed using OPUS 8.2 software.

4 Multi-technique characterization of paint mock-ups.

Partner	Technique, instrumentation/technical feature	Access
CNR-ISPC (Catania)	<p><u>Confocal XRF.</u> Custom built device developed at the XRAYLab (Catania). It consists of a spectrometric head composed of a microfocus X-rays source (Mo anode, 30W) coupled with a strong focusing polycapillary (spot dimensions 7 μm at the Mo-K). The detection of the induced fluorescence by the primary beam is performed by using a SDD equipped with a semi-lens having a focus dimension of 10 μm. The two foci permit to map in 1D (elemental profiling) and 3D (elemental mapping) the samples under study with a resolution of about 10 μm. The 1D/3D scanning is provided by a 3-axes (XYZ) motorized system. An ancillary SDD allows us to combine micro-XRF and CXRF on the same samples. Finally, a long-distance microscope is used for video guided investigations.</p> <p><u>XRD (spot and mapping).</u> The device is based on the use of a copper source operated at grazing angles (10deg) and a 1D Si-strip detector for covering in one shot the Bragg angles from 16 to 45° (in 2 theta). An ancillary SDD is used to take XRF data on the same XRD spot. The scanning of samples is performed by a motorized 3-axes system allowing to detect the mineral phase distribution images of the investigated samples.</p>	MOLAB
CNR-INO	<p><u>FORS.</u> Two Zeiss Multi-Channel Spectrometer (MCS) devices: the MCS601 UV-NIR C extended module (spectral range 210-1015 nm) and the MCS611 NIR 2.2 module (spectral range 910-2200 nm), with an acquisition step of 0.8 nm/pixel and 5 nm/pixel, respectively, and spot size of about 2 mm. Data are acquired with a 45°/0° illumination/detection geometry, and a 100% reflecting reference standard (Spectralon) is used for calibration.</p> <p><u>OCT.</u> Spectral-domain OCT (Telesto II, Thorlabs) instrument operates at 1300 nm (center wavelength) with an axial and a lateral resolution of 5.5 μm (in air) and 13.0 μm, respectively. The detector consists of a spectrograph made of a diffraction grating and a fast camera. The system is controlled via 64-bit software preinstalled on a high-performance computer.</p> <p><u>Raman.</u> Portable Bruker Optics BRAVO spectrometer. The device allows fluorescence mitigation and background-free spectra collection thanks to patented sequentially shifted excitation (SSE™). The instrument has two excitation diode lasers (DuoLaser™, 785 and 852 nm) with a spot size of 0.1 x 0.5 mm². The lasers were detected by different areas of a CCD detector (spectral resolution 12 cm⁻¹).</p>	MOLAB
CNR-SCITEC	<p><u>XRF-Vis-NIR scanning.</u> IRIS instrument produced from XGLab (Bruker). The instrument is equipped with a compact and lightweight measuring head composed of an X-ray source with Rh anode and a</p>	-

	<p>Silicon Drift Detector (SDD) interfaced to extremely fast digital electronics (operative conditions: 40kV, 200 μA, spot diameter of 0.5mm, 40ms of acquisition time). In the measurement head, an optical fiber system is located for simultaneous Vis-NIR reflection measurements in the spectral range of 400-2500nm with spectral resolution <2nm (400 nm -1000 nm) and <9.5nm (1000 nm -2500 nm).</p> <p><u>SWIR hyperspectral imaging.</u> Photon Etc camera ZephIR™ 2.5. The ZephIR 2.5 is a deep-cooled, SWIR camera sensitive from 1000 to 2500 nm. It is equipped with a HgCdTe FPA (320 x 256 pixels, pixel size 30 μm). Wavelength dispersion is obtained by holographic filters with a spectral resolution of about 5 nm.</p>	
IPCHS	<u>EPR.</u> Benchtop spectrometer Bruker EMXnano operating in CW mode, magnetic field range 500 G – 4000 G, microwave frequency 9.6 GHz.	-
IQF-CSIC	<u>UV-laser induced fluorescence (LIF) spectroscopy.</u> Carried out using laser excitation at 266 nm (4 th harmonic of a Q-switched Nd:YAG laser (Quantel), 6 ns pulses, 10 Hz repetition rate) and a 0.30 m spectrograph with a 300 grooves/mm grating (TMc300 Bentham) coupled to an intensified charged coupled detector (2151 Andor Technologies).	FIXLAB
UniPg	<u>Vis hyperspectral imaging.</u> SOC710 produced by Surface Optics Corporation, San Diego (USA). The system utilises a whiskbroom line scanner producing a 696x520 pixels hypercube covering the range of 400-1000 nm with 128 spectral bands. The spectra are defined by one point approximately every 4.5 nm. The spatial resolution can be continuously modulated by adjustable focal length of the mounted objective. Two Elinchrom Scanlite 350W Halogen lamps with diffusing umbrellas are used for reflectance measurements, while two Honle Ledline 500 led systems emitting at 405 nm are employed for luminescence measurements.	MOLAB
UiO	<u>Far infrared FTIR spectroscopy (transmission mode).</u> Measurements performed at IRIS beamline at the Bessy II electron storage ring, HZB in Berlin by means of a Bruker V70v spectrometer equipped with a FIR detector (Cryogen-free THz Bolometer) and synchrotron radiation as an external FIR source which provided higher flux and a smaller sample spot on the sample. The spectra are collected in transmission mode using a Spectra-Tech Micro-Compression cell by pressing a small amount of sample between two diamonds windows (~2 mm diameter). Typically, 128-256 scans are averaged at 4 cm^{-1} spectral resolution.	-
OF-ADC	<u>UV-vis mapping.</u> A system with two sources (one for the UV and the other for the vis and NIR spectrum area) is used for radiation from 200 nm up to 800 nm combined with a monochromating system and	-

	<p>a photodiode array for receiving the diffused reflectance at the point of measurement. In both cases, the incident beam is inserted in a suitable fiber optic bundle. After the fiber optic bundle the beam is condensed to the measurement area using a lens system installed on external integration spheres. In the case of the UV-vis module the reflected power is injected into another optic fiber to be guided into the monochromating system and then to the Photo Diode Array (PDA). Light sources: AvaLight-D(H)-S Deuterium-Halogen light sources combined with deuterium and halogen light sources (measurement range: from 190 to 2500 nm). Optical fibers: made of synthetic fused silica (amorphous silicon dioxide), that permit to work in the 250 nm to 2500 nm spectral range, while the jacketing of stainless steel is added for protection with minimum bending radius 35 mm. Probe: integration sphere of barium sulfate covered surface. The spot size of the probe is a circle with a diameter of about 2 mm. Spectrometer: AvaSpec-2048TEC thermo-electric cooled fiber optic spectrometer. The instrument is equipped with a CCD detector, provided with an AD converter and a one-stage Peltier cooling device.</p>	
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Appendix 2.1.2

Appendix 1: Model system preparation

An unprepared linen canvas (Van Beek Art Supplies “Antwerp” 220 g/m²) stretched onto a wooden stretcher was sized twice with an 8 % w/w rabbit skin glue (Gerstaecker). The canvas was further prepared with a chalk-glue ground, applied in three layers with a broad brush. The ground consists of 100 g Champagne chalk (Gerstaecker) which was added to 200 mL 4% rabbit skin glue solution while stirring. Next, the ‘active layer’ was applied. This layer contains 1.0 g margaric acid (heptadecanoic acid, 98%, Alfa Aesar), 1.0 g lead (II) acetate trihydrate (Merck) and 8 mL cold-pressed linseed oil (de Kat). The margaric acid was dissolved in acetone before adding to the linseed oil. The lead acetate was ground in a mortar with a pestle. After the acetone was left to evaporate from the linseed oil mixture, the lead acetate was added and briefly mixed with a palette knife. The mixture, which became viscous upon adding the lead acetate, was applied onto the prepared canvas with a draw down bar (wet thickness 50 mm). Four days later, two different types of paint layers were applied on top of the active layer, applied with the draw down bar (wet thickness 100 mm). A paint layer containing smalt prepared by grinding 2.5 g smalt (de Kat, 0.2-0.3 mm particle size) in 2 mL linseed oil with glass muller on a glass slab for 20 minutes. A second batch of smalt oil paint was prepared in the same manner with 1.3 g smalt in 1 mL linseed oil. A paint layer containing iron oxide was prepared by grinding 4.0 g red iron oxide (120 M, synthetic iron oxide >3 mm, Kremer Pigmente) to 4 mL linseed oil. These two types of pigments were chosen to create one opaque and one translucent paint layer. Small pieces ($\pm 2 \times 2$ cm) were cut from the canvas three days later, while the paint was still sticky. Carefully pinned onto board and wrapped in plastic zip lock bags, the model systems were sent via mail to all partners. In addition to a smalt and iron oxide model system, each partner also received reference pieces of plain sized canvas, sized canvas with ground, and sized canvas with ground and active layer.

Appendix 2: Monitoring conditions

The distributed model systems were stored under the same conditions at 30 °C and 50% relative humidity (RH) in the dark. This environment was maintained by placing the model systems in a closed container holding a cup of saturated solution of magnesium nitrate hexahydrate in an oven at 30 °C. Some variation in conditions in the different laboratories was reported (RH between 46 and 60%, T between 27.5 and 30 °C). The model systems were removed periodically for analysis. The first six weeks of the monitoring campaign (21 February to 4 April 2022), measurements were performed weekly. From week seven onwards, the measurements were performed monthly for the next three months (May, June, July). The final measurement was performed mid-September. This makes a total of 11 measurements.

Appendix 3: Instrumental parameters

External reflection infrared spectroscopy

External reflection FTIR for the monitoring experiment was performed with a compact, transportable FTIR spectrometer (ALPHA, Bruker Optics, Germany/USA—MA) equipped with a SiC global source, a “rock solid”-design interferometer (with gold mirrors) and a DLaTGS detector. The external reflectance module has an optical layout of 22°/22°. The spectrometer can be fixed on a tripod to perform measurements with a painting on an easel adapting the instrumental orientation orthogonal to the surface. Pseudo-absorption spectra ($\log(1/R)$; R = reflectance) were acquired from areas of about 20 mm², in the spectral range of 7000–375 cm⁻¹, at a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and using 144 scans. Spectra from a gold flat mirror were used as background. Three spectra were acquired on different areas of the sample. All data were collected using Opus software (v7.2).

Colorimetry

Colour measurements were performed with standard illuminant D65 and observer 10° (EN15886). A spectrophotometer (Konica Minolta mod. Chroma Meter CM-700d) registered the colour coordinates L*, a* and b* on selected areas (5 mm in diameter) for each monitoring step. The calibration against a SPECTRALON® white reference was performed before any measurement. Each colorimetric value (L*, a*, b*) was the auto-averaging of three subsequent measurements. Measurements were taken on each model system by using a transparent mask, designed with five areas. Thus, the colour coordinates of each specimen corresponded to the mean value of five measurements. The mask was also used for repositioning the instrument on the same areas.

Visible to near-infrared multispectral imaging colorimetry

Colorimetric coordinates (L*a*b*) were calculated from the visible range of the reflectance spectrum measured with a multispectral visible to near-infrared (VIS-NIR) scanner, developed in-house at the Italian National Institute of Optics. The CIELAB 1976 colour-space and D65 illuminant with observer at 2° were used. L*a*b* coordinates were reported as average values related to the entire area of the model system (30 × 30 mm²) or to a specific region of interest. The VIS-NIR scanner acquires, in a point-by-point modality, the backscattered radiation from a surface with a spatial sampling of 250 μm (~4 point/mm), generating 32 monochromatic images in the visible (from 380 to 780 nm) and in the infrared region (790 to 2500 nm) with a spectral sampling step of 20–30 and 50–100 nm, respectively. The constant motion of the optical head, which acquires a single point in circa 1 ms, prevents the surface of the painting from being heated significantly. The instrument works at 12 cm distance from the surface in a 45°/0° (illumination/detection) configuration according to CIE standards. The system is operated through a custom-developed software, with a simultaneous control of movement of scanner head, autofocus and images acquisition. The pixel size of the acquired VIS-NIR images is 250 × 250 μm² which corresponds to the highest spatial resolution in point-like colorimetric measurements.

Technical photography

Images were taken using a Canon EOS 7D (18 megapixels, CMOS sensor) camera body, operated in manual mode. The lens used is a Canon EFS 18-135 mm f/3.5-5.6 IS mounted with B+W 468 UV/IR cut filter. Ultraviolet induced luminescence (UVL) acquisitions were performed using two Flash Quantum T5D with B+W UV black 403 filters. The same setup was used for acquiring visible incident light images (VIS) mounting B+W 468 UV/IR cut filter on two flashes. For the raking light images (RL) the flashes were positioned at approximately 30 cm distance and at an angle of 10 to 30 degrees relative to the plane of the model system surface.

Optical coherence tomography

The 850 nm OCT setup was developed in-house at the Department of Biophotonics and Optical Engineering, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland, as a portable instrument for examination of cultural heritage objects. The instrument contains a broadband source (Broadlighters Q-870-HP, Superlum, Ireland) and a spectrograph (Cobra CS800-840/180 spectrometer, Wasatch Photonics) as detector. The instrument is fitted with a telecentric lens (LCM04 from Thorlabs, $F = 54$ mm) and two HR CCD cameras for locating. An area of 17×17 mm² of the model systems was scanned at a distance of 43 mm and a working bandwidth of 770 nm – 970 nm. The duration of one B-scan (cross-sectional brightness scan) was approximately 200 ms. The lateral resolution was 13 μ m and the axial resolution ca. 2.2 μ m (in paint) and 3.2 μ m (in air). Detailed instrument description with standard post-processing for visualisation of cross-sections can be found elsewhere (Targowski et al. 2020). The OCT measurements at 1310 nm were performed with a Thorlabs Telesto system. The axial resolution in air was 3.2 μ m, although the practical resolution was lower due to strong sidelobe. Cubes of $500 \times 500 \times 1024$ pixels (x, y, z) were collected with a pixel size of $20 \times 20 \times 3.48$ μ m (x, y, z). These cubes were subsequently cropped for analysis to a size of $391 \times 451 \times 350$ pixels (x, y, z).

Micro-profilometry

Laser Scanning Interferometric Micro-profilometry was performed with a device built in-house at the Italian National Institute of Optics. It is composed of a distance meter (655 nm, Conoprobe 1000, Optimet, Jerusalem Israel) with a 25 mm lens mounted on an XY scanning system. The model systems were glued to a wooden panel with epoxy resin and positioned vertically in front of the micro-profilometer. The scanned areas (45×50 mm²) were acquired with a 20 μ m lateral step size at a 3 μ m resolution in depth. The laser (680 nm wavelength) has a 27 μ m spot size and power set to 0.17 mW for the iron oxide model system and 0.78 mW for small model system. The data was processed with an in-house software.

X-radiography

The x-radiographs of the model systems were imaged in transmission using a Balteau Baltograph X-ray system (Baltograph generator xsd225 with X-ray tube tsd225/0). The images were recorded at 32 kV and 2.5 mA with a focal spot size of 1mm (640W) and a dwell time of 60 s. The distance between the X-ray source and the image plate was 112 cm. The image plate (resolution 25 μ m) was scanned using a Duerr hd-cr 35 ndt cr-scanner. Midway through the monitoring period, the X-ray tube was replaced (Comet MXR-320HP/11).

Acoustic microscopy

In this study, a 175 MHz piezoelectric transducer (Panametrics-NDT model V3965) is utilized to achieve a lateral and axial resolution of micrometric order while a 1G sample/s analog-to-digital converter (Acquisition Logic Data Acquisition card AL8xGT 2.0) is used. The area of investigation was approximately 15 mm². The lateral resolution of the setup used here was 50 x 50 µm and depth resolution approximately 20 µm. A hydrogel was applied to the surface of the model systems to function as a transmission agent.

Appendix 2.1.3

Details of some equipment used for this project:

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT)

Optical Coherence Tomography measurements were carried out using two different devices. OCT is based on the concept of low-coherence interferometry. A narrow beam of light of low temporal coherence (to obtain high axial resolution) and high spatial coherence (to ensure high sensitivity) is scanned over the object. The depth of penetration is determined by the absorption properties of the medium examined. This defines the major constraint of the application of OCT to the examination of artworks: only transparent and semi-transparent layers, like, for instance, varnishes and glazes, may be imaged. After the registration of an interference signal and its numerical processing, this amplitude information is often referred to as an A-scan by analogy to ultrasonography, and when converted to intensities it forms one vertical line of the tomogram. By parallel transfer of the penetration beam to consecutive, adjacent positions, the whole image of the cross-section (B-scan) is built up. By repeating such images in parallel, adjacent planes volume data is collected.

Results of the OCT examination (B-scans) are usually presented in a false colour scale, where areas from which no signal is detected (perfectly transparent or beyond the range of penetration) remain black, whereas areas which weakly scatter or reflect the probing beam are shown in cold colours (from blue to green), while those highly scattering or reflecting are represented by warm colours (from yellow to red).

In OCT tomograms, the vertical scale is elongated for better readability and to reflect the difference in axial (higher) and lateral (lower) resolution. Additionally, the depths recovered by OCT tomography represent optical distances. Therefore, axial distances within the imaged structure may be obtained from the vertical scale bar provided by dividing the obtained distance by the refractive index of the medium (usually ≈ 1.5).

Light usually approaches from the top and the first strong line in a tomogram is thus the airvarnish boundary. The varnish layer is usually visible as a dark strip (it practically does not back-scatter the probing light), whereas glazes and semi-transparent paint layers (if present) are reproduced usually in tints of blue. The last visible layer is an opaque one. The way it is reproduced depends on its scattering properties: materials strongly scattering the probing light (usually containing bright pigments) are shown as layers of gradually fading

colour due to the multiple scattering effects. Materials containing strongly absorbing pigments are shown as narrow strips.

Device 1. The examination has been made with a prototype high-resolution portable Sd-OCT instrument built under EU FP7 CHARISMA Programme.

Major technical parameters of the OCT instrument:

- spectral range of the probing light: 770–970 nm,
- axial resolution in varnish: 2.2 μm ,
- axial imaging range: 1.4 mm,
- lateral resolution: 15 μm ,
- power of probing light at object: no more than 800 μW ,
- distance to the object: 43 mm.

Device 2. Cross-sectional analysis was performed with a Thorlabs Telesto-II OCT device, using a superluminescent diode (central wavelength: 1300 nm, bandwidth: about 100 nm) with axial resolution of 5.5 μm in air, and lateral resolution of 13 μm . The maximum field of view (FOV) is 10.0 x 10.0mm², with 3.5 mm imaging depth. The detector consists of a spectrograph made of a diffraction grating and a fast camera. The system is controlled via 64-bit software preinstalled on a high-performance computer. The 3D scanning path probe, with integrated video camera, performs high-speed imaging (76 kHz) for rapid volume acquisition and live display. The system provides fine XY translation and rotation of the sample along with coarse axial travel of the probe.

For each sample 2D and 3D OCT acquisitions were performed on the sample area identified by the respective paper mask (Figure 10). Thickness values for each material layer were obtained as an average of 5 axial measurements on the XZ slice, after correction for $n = 1.5$.

Figure a1. Telesto II during the acquisition

Laser scanning microprofilometry

The laser scanning microprofilometer developed at CNR-INO comprises a commercial conoprobe (Optimet, Conoprobe 1000) moved by an XY scanner allowing for measurements on a maximum area of 30 x 30 cm². The profilometer, which is equipped with a 50 mm objective lens resulting in a 1 µm axial resolution, 20 µm lateral resolution, and 8 mm dynamic range, provides faithful, high-resolution topographic maps of the measured surface, which may be displayed either as a 3D model or as an image. The latter may be further processed through the application of digital filters and rendering techniques to enhance micrometric details and improve their readability.

All samples were measured with 50 µm sampling step in both X and Y directions.

Multispectral Vis-NIR reflectography

The multispectral scanner developed at the National Research Council–National Institute of Optics (CNR-INO) allows for the simultaneous acquisition of 32 narrowband images (16 VIS and 16 NIR images) through whiskbroom scanning in the range of 395–2500 nm. A square-shaped fibre bundle collects the reflected light from a single point of the scanned surface and delivers it to a set of Si and InGaAs photodiodes, each of them equipped with an interferential filter. The optical head, comprising the lighting system and the catoptric collecting optics, is placed in a 45°/0° illumination/observation geometry and moves with a step of 250 µm and speed of 500 mm/s. During the scanning, the autofocus system maintains the optimal target-

lens distance, thanks to a high-speed triangulation distance metre and a custom-made control software. The result is a set of perfectly superimposing monochromatic images free from aberrations and metrically correct. The 16 monochrome images in the Vis spectral range are combined with custom-made software, using the standard CIE D65 illuminant and the 2° observer, to obtain the RGB image (i.e., color image) of the scanned surface.

Spectra were extracted with a purposely developed software as an average over an area of 2 mm diameter on each sample. For samples presenting a layer of dirt on half surface, 2 spectra were extracted: one on the paint without dirt, and the other on the dirt layer.

Samples with only a layer of varnish (A, B, G, H) were not measured.

UV Laser Induced Fluorescence (UV-LIF)

Laser induced fluorescence (LIF) measurements were carried out using laser excitation at 266 nm (4th harmonic of a Q-switched Nd:YAG laser, 6 ns pulses, 10 Hz repetition rate) and a 0.30 m spectrograph with a 300 grooves/mm grating (TMc300 Bentham) coupled to an intensified charged coupled detector (2151 Andor Technologies). The temporal gate was operated at zero-time delay with respect to the arrival of the pulse to the surface of the sample and with a width of 3 μ s. The varnish samples were illuminated at an incidence angle of 45° with pulses of around 0.1 mJ using a laser spot size of 1 x 2 mm. LIF spectra were recorded at 300 nm intervals in the wavelength range of 300–700 nm using a 300 lines/mm grating. Cut-off filters at 300 and 360 nm were used to reduce the scattered laser light from the surface of the varnish mock-up samples and to avoid second-order diffraction. Each spectrum resulted from the accumulation of 50 LIF signals acquired at different points in each varnish sample zone.

Multi-Photon Excitation Fluorescence (MPEF)

In-depth analysis of varnish layers was performed with a non-linear optical microscope developed at Instituto de Química Física Blas Cabrera (IQF-CSIC, Spain) that allows the collection of the MPEF signals from the focal volume at the sample plane in the reflection mode, as depicted in Figure below. The excitation light source is a mode-locked Ti:Sapphire femtosecond laser emitting at 800 nm, with average power of 680mW, delivering 70 fs pulses at a repetition rate of 80 MHz. A variable neutral density filter (NDC-50C-2M, Thorlabs) was used to control the laser power reaching the sample. For the present measurements, the average power was in the range of 7–15 mW, values far from the damage threshold of the paint grisaille layers (as monitored through CCD online visualization of the sample surface during the femtosecond laser excitation). The laser beam was modulated using a shutter at frequency of 130 Hz and conducted to the sample through the aperture of a microscope objective lens (M Plan Apo HL 50 \times , Mitutoyo, NA 0.42) by using a dichroic beam splitter (FF750-SDi02-25 \times 36, Semrock) with high reflection at 800 nm. The laser focal plane was selected with motorized translation XYZ stages (Standa 8MVT100–25-1 for XY and Standa 8MTF for Z). The lateral and in-depth resolutions achieved are of 1 and 2 μ m, respectively. A

LabVIEW interface was used to control both scanning and data acquisition procedures. The MPEF signals were collected in the backward direction through the microscope objective lens and a beam splitter (70/30) and measured using a photomultiplier tube (9783B, ET Enterprises) connected to a lock-in amplifier (SR810 DSP, Stanford Research Systems) to ensure high amplification and signal-to-noise ratio. A short pass filter (335–610 nm, Thorlabs FGB37S) was placed at the entrance of the photomultiplier to cut off the reflected laser light. The remaining 30% of the MPEF signal was sent to a CCD camera (Thorlabs DCC1645C) for online visualization of the sample surface and the signal collection process. The thickness value of each varnish layer was obtained by averaging the values obtained in Z-scans carried out at five different points of each sample.

Figure a2. Nonlinear optical microscope setup. Dichroic beam splitter (DBS), beam splitter (BS), optical filter (OF), photomultiplier (PMT), microscope objective (MO). The sample or object is placed on an XYZ motorized stage.

Hybrid OCT/microscopic hyperspectral imaging system

A newly developed hybrid OCT (1250 nm) and microscopic hyperspectral system (405-845 nm with 10 nm bands) has been used.

The OCT and hyperspectral imaging resolution in the plane of the object was 8 μm . The OCT axial resolution into the object (normal to the plane of the object) was 12 μm in the air or 8 μm in a polymer.

The microscopic hyperspectral image gives both the hyperspectral image cube from which reflectance spectra can be extracted, but also the true colour image derived from it, assuming D65 daylight illumination and 1932 standard observer (2 degrees).

The combination of the spectral reflectance and varnish thickness per pixel allowed to extract the corresponding extinction coefficient.

Appendix 2.1.4

Colorimetry:

Minolta spectrophotometer CM 2600d with a 3 mm diameter aperture set to give results in CIELAB1976 colour space, using the standard 10° observer and CIE light source D65. The light source is a xenon lamp filtered to give a wavelength range from 360 to 740 nm, with a 10 nm interval between data points, dispersed by diffraction grating. 100% UV range was selected. The light-receiving element is a silicon photodiode array (dual 40 elements). Illumination is d/8 (diffuse illumination, 8-degree viewing). Simultaneous specular gloss inclusive and exclusive (SCI and SCE) measurements were made. For a matt surface such as A-D strips the differences are small. The device was dark calibrated against a distant non-illuminated background and then white calibrated on a CM-145 white reflection disc. Three readings are made for calibration, set on SCI and SCE, 100%, and 3 mm (SAV) using a target mask $\Phi 3$ mm. Spectra-Magic NX colour data software CM-S100W was used to control the instrument remotely and results were recorded for L^* , a^* and b^* .

Optical Coherence Tomography (NCU):

The examination has been made with a prototype high resolution portable Sd-OCT instrument built under EU FP7 CHARISMA Programme.

Major technical parameters of the instrument:

- spectral range of the probing light: 770–970 nm,
- axial resolution in varnish: 2.2 μm ,
- axial imaging range: 1.4 mm,
- lateral resolution: 15 μm ,
- power of probing light at object: no more than 800 μW ,
- distance to the object: 43 mm.

Spectral-Domain Optical Coherence Tomography (CNR-INO):

Cross-sectional analysis was performed with a Thorlabs Telesto-II OCT device, using a superluminescent diode (central wavelength: 1300 nm, bandwidth: about 100 nm) with axial resolution of 5.5 μm in air, and lateral resolution of 13 μm . The maximum field of view (FOV) is 10.0 x 10.0 mm², with 3.5 mm imaging depth. The detector consists of a spectrograph made of a diffraction grating and a fast camera. The system is controlled via a 64-bit software preinstalled on a high-performance computer. The 3D scanning path probe, with integrated video camera, performs high-speed imaging (76 kHz) for rapid volume acquisition and live display. The system provides fine XY translation and rotation of the sample along with coarse and fine axial travel of the probe.

For each sample, 2D tomograms (XY slices) were acquired across the edge of the paint layer (Fig. 1 and 2). For each material layer, thickness values were obtained by measuring the geometrical distance, based on the signal intensity plotted as a function of depth (the two main peaks correspond to the air/paint and air/support interfaces), as the average over 5 axial measurements on the XZ slice.

All tomograms (x= 8.53 mm; z = 1.5 mm) were acquired with a 3.55 μm^2 pixel size.

Laser Scanning Microprofilometry (CNR-INO):

The laser scanning microprofilometer developed at CNR-INO comprises a commercial conoprobe (Optimet, Conoprobe 1000) moved by an XY scanner allowing for measurements on a maximum area of 30x30 cm². All samples were measured using a 50 mm objective resulting in a 1 μm axial resolution, 40 mm working distance and 8 mm field depth. All samples were measured with a 50 μm sampling step in both X and Y directions. The profilometer provides faithful, high-resolution topographic maps of the measured surface, which may be displayed either as a 3D model or an image. The latter were further processed through the application of digital filters and rendering techniques to obtain the equivalent of raking light images, which allows enhancing micrometric details and improving their readability. Finally, roughness measurements were performed in Matlab environment on each sample surface to highlight changes due to the different ageing regimes and stages.

For the roughness measurements, the arithmetical mean height of a surface, S_a , is used and expresses, as an absolute value, the difference in height of each point compared to the arithmetical mean of the surface. It is calculated following the equation:

$$S_a = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N |z_{ij}|$$

where M ed N are the numbers of sample points in the X and Y directions, and Z is the surface height relative to the mean plane in the (i,j) point.

The root mean square roughness, Sq , represents the root mean square value of ordinate values within the defined area. It is equivalent to the standard deviation of heights. It is calculated following the equation:

$$Sq = \sqrt{\frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N (z_{ij})^2}$$

External reflection FTIR spectroscopy (CNR-SCITEC):

External reflection FTIR for the monitoring experiment was performed with a compact, transportable FTIR spectrometer (ALPHA, Bruker Optics, Germany/USA—MA) equipped with a SiC globar source, a “rock solid”-design interferometer (with gold mirrors) and a DLaTGS detector. The external reflectance module has an optical layout of 22°/22°. The spectrometer can be fixed on a tripod to perform measurements with a painting on an easel adapting the instrumental orientation orthogonal to the surface. Pseudo-absorption spectra ($\log(1/R)$; R = reflectance) were acquired from areas of about 20 mm², in the spectral range of 7000–375 cm⁻¹, at a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and using 144 scans. Spectra from a gold flat mirror were used as background. Three spectra were acquired on different areas of the sample. All data were collected using Opus software (v7.2).

Grazing-angle reflectance FTIR spectroscopy (IPCHS):

FT–IR analysis were performed on a Hyperion 3000 FT–IR microscope coupled with a Tensor spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Inc.) with a liquid nitrogen cooled MCT detector. The microscope is combined with GIR “Grazing Incidence Reflection” angle objective, which is suitable for analysing thin layers on highly reflecting substrates. The infrared spectra in the range of 4000 - 600 cm⁻¹ were acquired with 32 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Background was collected on a gold mirror. Three spectra were acquired from each sample and averaged after baseline correction and normalisation. The system was operated by the proprietary 32-bit software OPUS 8.1 (Bruker Optik GmbH) during measurements and analyses.

Reference samples were investigated by means of transmission FTIR spectroscopy. Transmission spectra were acquired on Hyperion 3000 FT–IR microscope coupled with a Tensor spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Inc.) with a liquid nitrogen cooled MCT detector. The infrared spectra in the range of 4000 - 600 cm⁻¹ were acquired with 64 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Three spectra were recorded from each sample, which were subsequently baseline corrected and normalised. The system was operated by the proprietary 32-bit software OPUS 8.1 (Bruker Optik GmbH) during measurements and analyses.

Appendix 2.1.5

- Digital Speckle Pattern Interferometry: Sergii Antropov, Leszek Krzemień, Łukasz Bratasz - IKiFP PAN, Kraków, Poland. All technical specifications of the equipment can be found in (Lasyk et al., 2011).
- 3D Confocal XRF: Francesco Paolo Romano – XRAYLab, ISPC-CNR, Catania, Italy. All technical specifications of the equipment can be found in (<https://www.e-rihs.it/en/xrf-confocal-mapping>).
- Laser Scanning Profilometry - Raffaella Fontana, Alice Dal Fovo, CNR-INO, Florence, Italy. All technical specifications of the equipment can be found in (Dal Fovo et al., 2021).
- Optical Coherence Tomography: 4.1. Raffaella Fontana, Alice Dal Fovo, CNR-INO, Florence, Italy. All technical specifications of the equipment can be found in (Dal Fovo et al., 2021).
- Magdalena Iwanicka, NCU, Toruń, Poland. All technical specifications of the equipment can be found in (Targowski et al., 2020).

Appendix 2.2.1

- During the PrevAlex IPHS project, the sampling devices were deployed in several indoor locations, as well as outdoors. As the same sampler can be used also for the determination of SO₂ and NO₂ in air, it is also very efficient.
- Figure 2 shows the three indoor and one outdoor monitoring location at the Museum of Fine Arts in Alexandria, Egypt, and an image showing the samplers during exposure.

Figure a3. PrevAlex sampling plan and a photo depicting the exposure at the Museum of Fine Arts in Alexandria, Egypt during the access project.

Appendix 2.2.2

Oddy test has been carried out using the “3-in-1” configuration. Lead, copper and silver stripes have been prepared by abrasion with P600 grit sandpaper or 1500 grit Micromesh pads. Metals have been hang in the top section of a closed vessel (inserted or hanged from silicone stoppers or hanged from nylon wire) with a 2 g sample of the material to be tested, except in Material 1, in which the low density only allowed to use 1 g. Water was added into a small vial to obtain a high relative humidity, in a ratio of water to air volume of the vessel of 1/100. Vessels where hermetically closed using silicone stoppers (or glass lid in one of the institutions). The prepared vessels were kept at 60 °C for 28 days. Upon completion of the essay, metallic stripes were removed and visually inspected to classify their aspect regarding the corrosion underwent during the test, in comparison with a blank vessel (without any material). Samples with no visible corrosion were rated as “Suitable” (for use in display or storage cases); those with slight tarnish or a thin corrosion layer as suitable for “Temporary” use; and those with visible corrosion, as “Unsuitable” for use in these applications.

Appendix 2.2.3

Description with equipment details and relevant instrumental parameters, data collection and processing

Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (p-XRF)

Instrumentation: Bruker handheld TRACER III-SD XRF equipped with a Rh X-ray tube and an SSD energy dispersive detector (10 mm²) was used for a fast screening of major elemental composition of NIST SRM 1648a (pellet) and filters with collected airborne particles.

Operating parameters: 40 kV, current 12 μA, acquisition time: 60 seconds.

Spectra have been processed using software Artax.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Molecular information on inorganic and organic compounds has been obtained using an FTIR Alpha (Bruker Optics) instrument equipped with SiC Globar source and DTGS detector, operating with a diamond crystal ATR. Spectra of the standard reference material have been recorded directly on the dust powder in the range 4000 - 400 cm⁻¹, with 24 scans and resolution 4 cm⁻¹. Spectra have been processed using software OPUS 7.2

Chemical imaging was performed with a Bruker LUMOS II FTIR microscope (Bruker Optics GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany), equipped with a liquid-N₂ cooled 32 x 32 element Focal Plane Array (FPA) detector. FPA-FTIR images were acquired in transmittance mode within 4000–750 cm⁻¹ spectral region, each of them (1024 spectra) covering a sampling area of ca. 150 x 150 mm², with resolution 4 cm⁻¹ and 128 scans. A single spectrum in each FTIR image represents molecular information acquired from ca. 5 x 5 μm² area on the sample plane. The collected FTIR spectra were processed using OPUS 8.2 software.

Scanning Electron Microscopy equipped with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS):

Instrumentation: Zeiss Merlin FE-SEM equipped with a XFlash detector 5010 125eV Bruker Quantax Measurement parameters: 3 kV, 30 pA (SEM imaging) and 15 kV, 500 pA (EDS analysis). Sample preparation: plasma-sputtered with Au/Pd layer of ca. 3 nm thickness

SEM images were collected from at least 10 different areas of the sample with the following magnifications for each area: 200kx, 100kx, 50kx, 25kx, 10kx, 5kx.

Single SEM image acquisition time was 20 seconds.

Apart from morphology analysis, size of single particles (around 50-100) was measured using Zeiss software.

EDS spectra (single EDS spectrum acquisition time = 60 seconds) were registered for single particles from exactly the same area as previously analyzed in terms of morphology. Additionally, few elemental distribution maps were acquired (each map = 5 minutes).

Summing up total SEM-EDS analysis of each filter took around 45 minutes.

Laser Ablation Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS)

Instrumentation: quadrupole spectrometer ICP-MS NexION 300D (Perkin Elmer) coupled to laser ablation system LSX-213 (CETAC).

The LSX-213 combines a 213 nm UV laser (Nd:YAG, solid state, Q-switched) with the high sampling efficiency, variable 1-20 Hz pulse repetition rate and maximum energy up to 5mJ per pulse. For measurements, the samples were placed inside the ablation cell together with the selected reference materials (NIST610 and NIST1648a). The calibration material was measured twice in the beginning and twice in the end of each run to correct for instrumental drift.

Transient signals were recorded during ablations of the NIST SRM 1648a pellets and the filters and were evaluated for subsequent elemental quantification. The LA-ICP-MS signals were background corrected and integrated using Excel. Visualization of elemental distribution maps was done using LabView software.

LA-ICP-MS settings and data acquisition parameters

ICP-MS conditions:

RF power	1350 W
Carrier gas (Ar) flow rate	0,9 l/min
Sweeps	1
Readings	695-4501
Replicates	1
Dwell time for each monitored isotope	5 ms

Laser ablation conditions:

Laser wavelength	213 nm
Laser energy	3 mJ
Spot diameter	150 μ m
Repetition rate	20 Hz
Ablation mode	multi-line (n=13)
Scan rate	5 μ m·s

List of monitored isotopes: ^7Li , ^{11}B , ^{23}Na , ^{26}Mg , ^{27}Al , ^{29}Si , ^{31}P , ^{35}Cl , ^{39}K , ^{43}Ca , ^{45}Sc , ^{49}Ti , ^{51}V , ^{53}Cr , ^{55}Mn , ^{57}Fe , ^{59}Co , ^{60}Ni , ^{65}Cu , ^{66}Zn , ^{71}Ga , ^{75}As , ^{79}Br , ^{82}Se , ^{85}Rb , ^{88}Sr , ^{89}Y , ^{90}Zr , ^{93}Nb , ^{95}Mo , ^{109}Ag , ^{111}Cd , ^{115}In , ^{118}Sn , ^{121}Sb , ^{133}Cs , ^{137}Ba , ^{139}La , ^{140}Ce , ^{141}Pr , ^{143}Nd , ^{147}Sm , ^{153}Eu , ^{157}Gd , ^{159}Tb , ^{163}Dy , ^{165}Ho , ^{166}Er , ^{169}Tm , ^{173}Yb , ^{175}Lu , ^{178}Hf , ^{181}Ta , ^{182}W , ^{197}Au , ^{208}Pb , ^{209}Bi , ^{232}Th , ^{238}U

A single LA-ICP-MS spectrum acquisition time < 60 s, but the calculation and data visualization take always much longer.

Summing up total LA-ICP-MS analysis of each filter took around 1 hour.

Gas Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS)

The Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) were determined by gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Prior to analysis, the PAH fraction was extracted with Soxhlet from 5 mg of sample in dichloromethane for 20 h. The analysis was performed by the Gas Chromatograph Agilent Technologies 7809B equipped with a TOF HP 5 column (5%-phenyl-methylpolysiloxane nonpolar column).

While analysing NIST SRM 1648a, the Mass fraction values are lower than those reported in the Certificate of Analysis, with exception of 2-Methylphenantrene, Benzo[a]pyrene and Picene which are in quite good agreement. Content of PAHs in the filters with deposited PMs were below the limit of detection, therefore no data are reported for the real samples.

Raman spectroscopy

Instrumentation: the micro-Raman spectroscopy analysis performed using the Horiba Yvon Jobin T64000 spectrometer equipped with a confocal microscope with 50_ and 100_ objectives.

The Ar/Kr ion laser line at 514 were employed for the Raman excitation, and the laser power at the exit was below 1,5 mW. The spectra were dispersed using a diffraction grating (1800 line/mm) and detected by a CCD camera (1024 _ 256) with the spatial resolution of 200–1100 nm, and a notch filter was used to separate the Rayleigh signal. The spectra were recorded at room temperature in the range 100–3800 cm^{-1} with a spectral resolution of ca. 2 cm^{-1} . The integration time and accumulations (minimum 2) were chosen separately for each analyzed spot.